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Institute for Family and Social Studies

**Machine Translation in Media Subjects - A Case Study on
Quality Assessment in Various Selected Short Articles**

**A thesis Submitted in Fulfillment of the Requirements for a Degree of
Ph.D. in General Translation**

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بِسْمِ اللّٰهِ الرَّحْمٰنِ الرَّحِیْمِ

In the name of God, Most Gracious, Most
Merciful

(Quranic Verse)

Meaning Translated by: “Abdullah Yusuf Ali”

الاستمّال

(أَمَّنْ هُوَ قَانِئٌ أَنَاءَ اللَّيْلِ سَاجِدًا وَقَانِئًا يَحْذَرُ الْآخِرَةَ وَيَرْجُو رَحْمَةَ رَبِّهِ ۗ قُلْ هَلْ يَسْتَوِي

الَّذِينَ يَعْلَمُونَ وَالَّذِينَ لَا يَعْلَمُونَ ۗ إِنَّمَا يَتَذَكَّرُ أُولُو الْأَلْبَابِ)

سورة الزُّمَر، آية (9)

{Is one who worships devoutly during the hour of the night prostrating himself or standing (in adoration), who takes heed of the Hereafter, and who places his hope in the Mercy of his Lord - (like one who does not)? Say: "Are those equal, those who know and those who do not know? It is those who are endued with understanding that receive admonition}

Surah 39: Zumar, Verse: 9

Meaning Translated by: "Abdullah Yusuf Ali"

Dedication

To all those who helped me accomplish this research, especially my wife for her support and sincere help, and to my mother who has always been encouraging me.

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First, I would like to thank Omdurman Islamic University, and the Institute for Family and Social Studies; I am also grateful to my supervisor, associate prof. Mohamed Al Hassan Al Sayed who guided me in producing this research, and provided me with valuable advices, and helped me in the difficult times I have experienced; he contributed tremendously to the successful completion of the research.

Abstract

This study aims to Identify the problems of Machine Translation MT in media, by analyzing selected short political, economic, art and culture, sports, scientific, and legal articles from English to Arabic and vice versa, examining the changes and problems in the TL articles produced by MT, and suggesting solutions to such problems and changes, The importance of this study depends on increasing need to translate and transfer knowledge and exchange information between people around the world, who speak different languages, which make MT one of the selected solutions to this dilemma, in the age of the unlimited flow of information, The study examins sample text of different selected types in media articles, i.e. political, economic, scientific, culture/art, sports and legal texts, from Arabic to English and vice versa, The study find out that the MT output quality is high, but it needs to be re-edited sometimes, also discloses that there is no significant difference in the quality level between such types of article, The researcher recommends researchers and relevant translation institutions to use the Google Translate safely, depending on the reliability of the high quality performance proved by this study, also recommended on more studies that are similar to help MT programs designers to develop these technologies.

المستخلص

تهدف هذه الدراسة إلى التعرف على مشاكل الترجمة الآلية في وسائل الإعلام، من خلال تحليل موضوعات سياسية اقتصادية وعلمية وفنية وثقافية ورياضية وقانونية مختارة وقصيرة من الإنجليزية إلى العربية والعكس، مترجمة آلياً، واقتراح حلول لهذه المشاكل والتغيرات التي تطرأ على النص في اللغة المترجم إليها (اللغة الهدف)، تكمن أهمية هذه الدراسة في الحاجة المتزايدة لترجمة ونقل المعرفة وتبادل المعلومات بين الناس حول العالم، الذين يتحدثون لغات مختلفة، مما يجعل الترجمة الآلية هي أحد الحلول المختارة لهذه المعضلة، في عصر التدفق غير المحدود للمعلومات، تناولت الدراسة عينة نصوص مختارة مختلفة الأنواع في المقالات الإعلامية، السياسية، الاقتصادية، العلمية، الثقافية والفنية، الرياضية والقانونية، من العربية إلى الإنجليزية والعكس، توصلت الدراسة إلى أن جودة مخرجات الترجمة الآلية عالية، ولكن يلزم إعادة تعديلها أحياناً، كما كشفت أيضاً عن عدم وجود اختلافات كبيرة في مستوى الجودة بين هذه الأنواع من المقالات، يوصي الباحث الباحثين والمؤسسات ذات الصلة بالترجمة باستخدام مترجم جوجل، لموثوقيته اتلي كشفتها نتائج هذه الدراسة، كما يوصي بالمزيد من الدراسات في نفس المجال لمساعدة مصممي برامج الترجمة الآلية، يوصي الباحث الباحثين والمؤسسات ذات الصلة بالترجمة باستخدام مترجم جوجل لما أثبتته هذه الدراسة من دقة وجودة عالية لأدائه، كما يوصي بإجراء مزيد من الدراسات في المجال لمساعدة مصممي برامج الترجمة الآلية لتطوير هذه التقنيات.

Terms and Abbreviations

S	Abbrev.	Description
1	ALPAC	Automatic Language Processing Advisory Committee
2	CAT	computer assisted translation
3	CBT	Culture-Bound Term
4	CMS	Content Management System
5	CT	Connotative Translation
6	DC	Desktop Computer
7	DT	Denotative Translation
8	DTP	Desktop Publishing
9	FAMT	Fully Automated Machine Translation
10	HAMT	Human Aided Machine Translation
11	IA	Information Acquisition
12	KBMT	Knowledge-based machine translation
13	LPS	Local Provisioning System
14	MT	Machine Translation
15	NMT	Neural Machine Translation
16	SL	Target Language
17	SMT	Statistical Machine Translation
18	ST	Source Text
19	TL	Target Language
20	TM	Translation Memory
21	TQA	Translation Quality Assessment
22	TQA	Translation Quality Assessment
23	TT	Target Text

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Chapter one

Introduction

Chapter one

1. Introduction

This introductory chapter describes the background and overview of the study, the statement of the problem, objectives, hypotheses, methodology, study limits, study questions, significance of the study, and study structure.

1.1: Background and overview:

Translation, originally is a human activity, it is a kind of human communication, involving two parts, and many elements, naturally working from a side (sender), to another (recipient), using a message through a tool (medium).

Many translation theories were adopted to deal with specific obstacles that face translators, because of the cultural and linguistic differences between SL and TL, these hinders mostly can be solved by tools provided by these theories, and because of the uniqueness of human mental abilities, which can deal with words, sentences, and texts in their most vague meanings, and dig deep to reach the core of the meaning, which cannot be done alone by any alternative, machine, or other sophisticated software using computer and smart phones.

Machine Translation (MT) emerged as a result of the technical advance, as well as educational need, that translation in the age of information revolution can't meet the quality that journalists and researchers they want, but MT can't be used as a final product, man needed to take part in this process as assisting factor to rectify misinterpretation occurred, in the structure of the text and its original meaning. This study tries to find a way to put a hand on the main problems that face the machine in converting meaning from SL to TL, and find the possible solutions to fix it.

The research discusses MT in the light of advanced communication and information technology, and the increasingly need to transfer information,

sciences, and all types of knowledge, among nations, and this will be so difficult to keep pace with speedy rhythm of information revolution that swift the globe, and this research is a trial, to find a way to check a better MT quality used in the Media.

The study includes four chapters, the first one is an introductory, that contains a background and overview of the study, the statement of the problem, the objectives of the study, the significance of the study, the hypotheses, the methodology, the questions, the limits of the study, and the structure of the study.

Chapter two deals with the theoretical concepts (Theoretical Framework) on translation and literature review of media translation, which handles in its seven sections in details a background of the Islamic and Arab history of translation, and Western history of translation, besides definitions of translation, and theories concepts, studies, methods, strategies and type of translation, in addition to this chapter gives a quick glance to Machine Translation, and there is a review of some of previous studies on Machine Translation.

Chapter three emphasizes on the methodology of the study, focusing on data collection, and data categorization, besides discussion and analyzing of data. While chapter four discusses the findings, and results of the empirical, and study, suggests some recommendations.

1.2: Statement of the problem:

The field of Machine Translation MT is widely unknown in the Arab World, as well as in Sudan, especially for linguists and journalists, besides neglecting/ignoring it from the specialists in technology and information technology, because of the great leap in this field during the last 10 years, translators wouldn't be able to deal with the flow of information come through the Media and the Internet, therefore translators have to use supporting tools, such as online dictionaries, electronic lexical services,

computer applications. Despite these assisting tools, the output of the processed texts is not accurate according to linguistic criteria, which raises a question: how can people who work in Media get the most of MT, and handle errors in this process?

1.3: Objectives of the study:

The study trying to realize the following objective:

- a/ Identify the problems of MT in Media, by analyzing short political, economic, art and culture, sports, scientific, and legal articles from English to Arabic and vice versa.
- b/ Examine the changes and problems in the TL articles processed by MT.
- c/ Suggest solutions to some problems occur when using MT in Media.

1.4: Significance of the study:

The importance of this study depends on the following facts:

- a/ The increasing need to transfer knowledge and exchange information between people around the world, in an age witnesses a limitless flow of information every day, and every second, through the internet and other media tools.
- b/ There is a great need to the translation as a profession, while the professional translators can do few of this task, there must be a helping tool to meet the great demand on this field by using MT as machine-aided human translation MAHT, by editing the output of the MT process.
- c/ Advanced information technology provided a sophisticated programs and applications in the field of MT, such as Google Translate Toolkit translation service, Babylon live Translation, Yahoo Translation Service, some are free, and others are paid, this makes translation an easier task, more profitable, and sparing time and effort.

1.5: Hypotheses of the study:

- a/ MT output according to syntactical rules, from English to Arabic and vice versa is inaccurate.
- b/ The output of MT needs to be re-edited to rectify for more accuracy.
- c/ The output of MT accuracy is not at same level in the different fields, such as scientific, arts and culture, economic, and legal texts.

1.6: Study Questions:

- a/ Is the output of MT from English to Arabic and vice versa accurate syntactically and semantically.
- b/ Shall, MT output, be re-edited to rectify for more accuracy?
- c/ Is the accuracy of the output of MT is not at same level in the different fields, such as scientific, arts and culture, economic, and legal texts?

1.7: Method of the Study:

The suitable method of this study is a descriptive and analytical method, which provides tools needed to collect and analyze data, and compare the results of TL to SL, to find out the differences and changes in the selected sample, the researcher provides detailed information about this point in chapter 3 "methodology of the study".

1.8: Limits of the Study:

The study discusses same sample of political, economic scientific, sports, and art and culture, and legal short articles of each field, and analyze its MT output (Arabic into English, and vice versa), using Online Google Translate service, and compare the source language SL to the target language TL, to detect changes and errors.

Chapter Two

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

Chapter Two

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1: Introduction

Translation is a human activity; it is a type of communication between nations, and people, through which knowledge and sciences transferred, in this section discusses the history of translation in the Arab world, and Islamic civilization, by reviewing many stages of this history, besides, the research discusses the Western history of translation, and in the last part of this section, also there is a detailed review of the history of machine translation; section two sets many definitions of translation, while section three discusses the theories, concepts and studies of translation, section four covers the methods, strategies and types of translation, after that the study introduces machine translation from a technical viewpoint, the last part of the chapter a review of some related studies.

2.2: Historical Background

2.2.1 Arab-Islamic History of Translation:

2.2.1.1: pre-Islam era and early days of Islam:

The translation movement in the Arab-Islamic civilization vital artery, extended by the wisdom of China, India and Persia, and the culture of Greece, and Romans, to the ancient Eastern mysticism, the Christian monasticism and so on was (Gregory.2011, p.299)¹. It has preserved its religious faith, exposed deviant doctrines and superstitious ideas, and provided humanity with a distinctly Islamic civilization. It is not an exaggeration to say, that the Arab-Islamic civilization had no rival in the modern European era or in its advanced technical and nuclear age,

¹Gregory S. Aldrete, History of the Ancient World: A Global Perspective, University of Wisconsin–Green Bay, The Teaching Company, (2011).

Gregory, 2011, *ibid*, In general, modern Europe is still obliterating the facts of its renaissance based on the science and civilization of Muslim Arabs.

Abdul Aziz Sharif (2016)² says: the conquests of Alexander the Macedonian known as the largest to the spread of Greek civilization in Western Asia and Egypt and Syria, Which gave the region a special character that historians call the Hellenistic period on the period from the death of Alexander in 323 BC, until the Arab Islamic conquest in the seventh century AD, and at that time found in that region several centers of Greek civilization, most notably Alexandria, Antioch, Nisibin and Jundisapur.

"According to Prince, 2002³, translation movement in the Arab World has started during the reign of Assyrian, in the second century", who (Prince) translated their heritage into Arabic. Jaber. F, 2015. P: 129⁴, says: yet the appearance of Islam in the seventh century a significant turning point for the Arabic translation movement.

In the early times before Islam, people in the Arab Peninsula have a connection with other nations around, such like Roman, and Persian, even the Arab relations extended to far Asia (China and India). "In the pre-Islamic era, it was cited that some Arabs have spoken the languages of their neighboring countries", (Hala & Basma, 2015: p: 569⁵. As well as what was told about another poet, Umayya bin Abi Al-Salt, (died 5 AH/ 626

2 Sharif, Abdul -Aziz, Translation movement and its role in the rise of Islamic civilization, article, 2016.

3 Prince, Chris. The historical context of Arabic translation, learning, and the libraries of medieval Andalusia. Library History (2002).

4 Jaber. F. the Landscape of Translation Movement in the Arab World, from the 7th century until the beginning of the 21th century. Arab World Journal, vol.6, No. 4, December (2015).

5 Khalidi, H. &Dajani, A. B, Facets from Translation Movement in the Classic Arab, the 6th Conference on Psychology and Guidance, in 16th May, 2015, University of Jordan, Amman, Jordan, (2015).

AD) who recited the stories of prophets and could read books written in languages other than Arabic. This enabled him to introduce foreign words that were never used before into Arabic. Later, with the advent of the Prophet of Islam, Muhammad, it is reported that he ordered Zaid bin Thabit (died 45 AH / 665 AD) to learn Hebrew and Syriac languages to communicate with Jews in their own language (ibid.,2015, 569).

At that time, "Arabs used to travel and move one place to another, during winter and summer, for trading, they use the Arabic language in everyday contexts, and used a variety of languages, such as Syriac, and Aramaic, they had to learn those languages in order to communicate with other people during their voyages, at that time, there was no Arabic writing system", (Mehawesh. 2014, p: 685)⁶.

Hala & Basma, Ibid., 2015, p: 569, mentioned that, "this makes us understand how Imro Al-Qays, "an Arab poet), could ask for the help of the king of Romans, and visited Constantinople "561 AD" to recover his father's lost monarchy.

This confirmed by Rababah H, 2015, p: 124⁷, when he says: these journeys, "Arabs have made contact with at least three nations at that time; Persians in the East, Romans in the North and West, and Ethiopians in the South, and these nations had different languages, Pahlavi language (old Persian) for Persians and Old Latin for Romans and Greek for Byzantines and Ethiopic for Ethiopians, which is still used today as the liturgical language in the Ethiopia and part of Eritrea. Therefore, a journey with such length and different communication modes or languages", it is logically

6 Mehawesh, M. I. History of Translation in the Arab World, an overview. US- China Foreign Language, vol. 12, No. 8, 684-691, (2014).

7 Rababah, Hussein Abdo The Translation Movement in the Arab World: From the Pre-Islamic Era Until the end of Umayyad Dynasty (Before 610-750 A. D.), International Journal of Language and Linguistics, 2015.

impossible to make such economic and commercial relationships without having a certain sort of translation facilities and proficient translators, who helped those travelers and merchants to communicate with other peoples.

Rababah H, *ibid.*, 2015, p: 125, stated that Islam existed in 610 A.D with its new basic principle urging people to search for knowledge and understanding this universe, because Islam believes that the possession of knowledge is the best way of understanding this world; by which a man can understand and realize the relationship between the creation and creator. This in turn will help in discovering and solidifying the truth and faith of Allah, who is the creator (God) of this universe, and people will glorify Him in accordance with this understanding. So, Islam adopted this principle and tried to disseminate this belief into the world. The time of the prophet Mohamed (Peace be upon Him) is significant and important in the translation history, because new Islamic and religious terms have been introduced to Arabic and later translated to other languages in the world. The spread of Islam and the communication with non-Arabic speaking communities as Persians, Assyrians, Romans and others motivated the prophet to look for translators and to encourage the learning of foreign languages. One of the most famous translators at that time was Zaid Ibnu Thabet, who played a crucial role in translating letters sent by the prophet to kings of Persia, Syria, Rome, and the replied letters sent by those kings to the prophet.

2.2.1.2: Umayyad dynasty era:

In the Umayyad dynasty era, Al-Naqla, A. Ibrahim⁸ says: the translation movement actually began in the time of of Mu'awiya Ibn Abi Sufyan, but during the ruling of Khalid Ibn Yazid, who have many translators, suck like his Meryanos, and a monk, called Astefn Al-husari, translated some books

8 Al-Naqla, A. Ibrahim, Translation in the Umayyad Dynasty, from 660-729 A.C.

from Greek for him. Also Gabala Ibn Salim translated him many books from Persian,. But during the rule of Murwan Ibn Alhakam and his son Abdu Malik books translated from Syriac into Arabic, such as optical medicine, by Masarjawayeh.

Mehawesh.2014, *ibid.*, p: 686, says "the Umayyad period (661-750) witnessed a number of developments, which laid the long-term foundations of the Islamic Empire. Translation activity gained impetus during this period. There is a general agreement that the first translations carried out during this period were from Greek and Coptic into Arabic". Isa and Qadri, 2017, p: 12⁹, think that the actual beginning of translation refers back to the onset Umayyad era, it was mentioned more than one time that Khalid Ibn Yazeed sent to people in Alexandria asking for some books in medicine and chemistry to translate into Arabic. Ibn Khilikhhan, Isa and Qadri, *ibid.* 2017, said that Khalid Ibn Yazeed was the first who rewarded translators and philosophers.

2.2.1.3: Abbasid dynasty time:

The Abbasid dynasty acquired a hola, in popular imagination, becoming the most celebrated in the history of Islam, due to the unparalleled intellectual awakening that culminated the Al-Ma'mun patronage, Algariani, & Mohadi. 2017. P:2¹⁰. The House of Wisdom, (Bayt Al-Hikmah), was one of the leading Libraries that distinguished the Abbasid times, (Isa and Qadri, *ibid.* 2017,).

9 Abdul khaliq Isa and RanaQadri, Translation of Thoughts, Literature and Philosophy, form Al-jahiz's Perspective: Possible or Impossible, Al-Lisaniyyat, Vol. 23, No. 3., 2017.

10 Algariani, A.A. &Mohadi. M. The House of Wisdom (Bayt Al-Hikmah) and its civilizational impact on Islam Libraries, A historical perspective. Doi. 10:1515. Mjss-2017-0036. (2017).

The early Abbasid Caliphs, adopting a religious philosophy that encouraged learning and debate, promoted the establishment of universities and libraries throughout their Empire. Early beginnings were made under Al-Mansur (754-775) and Harun Al-Rashid (785-809) of Arabian Nights fame, but Al-Mamun (813-833) brought the "House of Learning" House of Wisdom or university at Baghdad into prominence. With libraries, laboratories, subsidized scholars, a translating service, and even an astronomical observatory, this institution attracted scholars from Spain to India (Harris, 1999, p: 79)¹¹.

Salma Fadllala, 2019, p: 14¹², said that the Abbasid translators worked in groups, and their methods and organization based on the division of labor, considering the abilities and skills of each translator, and Salma explained that they systemized their work as following:

- Studying and analyzing the original text.
- Translating the text.
- Editing the translation, by dealing with stylistic matters of the target language.
- Then, revising the final output.

The figure of Hunayn ibn Ishaq, presents an example of translation that was integrated into Abbasid society, he was one of the more prolific, and well-known translators of all Abbasid ear, whose works set the standard for translators after him (Goodin, 2014)¹³.

11 Harris, Michael, History of Libraries in the Western World, 4th ed, Scarecrow Press. ISBN 978-0-8108-7715-3, (1999).

12 Salma Fadllala, Grammatical and Structural Problems Encountering Translating from Arabic into English, and Vice Versa, 2019.

13 Goodin, K. S. Translation Theory and Practice , in the Abbasid Era. The University of Texas at Austin, (2014).Jaber, Fadi. *The Landscape of Translation Movement in the Arab World: from the 7th Century Until the Beginning of the 21st Century*, Arab World English Journal (AWEJ) Vol.6. No.4 December 2015.

Hunayn was, without doubt, the greatest and most productive of all translators, as well as reviser of many others done by his predecessors as they were inaccurate, and many of them has translated the Greek with Syriac or Arabic letters (Johna (2002)¹⁴.

Aljahiz thinks that (Isa and Qadri. Ibid. 2017, p: 15), the translator should have some characteristics, which are: 1) the translator's knowledge in the subject he is dealing with, shouldn't be less than his knowledge in translation as a science; 2) A translator must be the most eloquent figure among others in the two languages they are dealing with, in other words, a translator must be fluent in both languages.

2.2.1.4: translation from 10th to 19th century:

From the middle ages to the modern era, members of the Jewish communities living in the Arab countries used the local dialect of spoken Arabic to communicate in daily life, as did the rest of the population. Mahmoud Khayal, 1998, p. 2,¹⁵ referred to this by saying that: the only a small number of religious leaders and other educated Jews had mastered classical Hebrew, the language of worship. Thus, there was a need to translate certain basic Jewish texts written in classical Hebrew into Arabic or Judeo-Arabic (Arabic language written in Hebrew characters). Naturally, these Jewish communities devoted most of their translational attention to the Bible and its exegeses. Various translations and adaptations of the Bible were prepared in both Arabic and Judeo-Arabic; most of the translators relied heavily on Sa'adiah Gaon (882 to 942 CE), the Egyptian-born Jewish

14 Johna, Samir, HunayninbIshaq: A forgotten Legend, The American Surgeon. 08 (5): 497-9(2002).

15 KhayalMa'hמוד, Hebrew-Arabic Translations in the Modern Era: A General Survey, Translation and Interpreting in Israel, Vol. 43, No. 1, mars 1998. Publisher(s) Les Presses de l'Université de Montréal, (1998).

scholar who had translated the Bible into classical Arabic in the 10th century.

But it is only under Abd al-Rahman III (889-961 CE) and his son al-Hakam (915-976 CE) that the Golden Age of Andalusia rose, the former being comparable to al-Rashid in the unification of his territory and the latter to al-Ma'mun in his taste for scholarship and books. So much so that al-Hakam built the greatest library of Andalusia where copyists, scientists, philosophers, artists and poets converged, an obvious reminder of Baghdad's House of Wisdom. However, "the difference between Cordoba and Baghdad was that there was little in the way of a translation movement here, for most of books that al-Hakam acquired were in Arabic already, (*Basalamah. Salah, 2019*¹⁶).

Nevertheless, despite the uncatchable advance of the Abbasids over the Umayyad's in collecting manuscripts and their translations, as well as in scholarship and cultural production in general, it is remarkable that the translational momentum that Baghdad created was such that it did actually extend as far as Andalusia and brought about scientific figures as prominent as Ibn Firnas/Afernas (810-887 CE), Ibn Hazm (994-1064 CE), Ibn al-Haytham/Alhazen (965-1040 CE), al-Zaraqali/Arzachel (1029-1087 CE), Ibn Bajja/Avempace (1095-1138 CE) and the even more famous Ibn Roshd/Averroes (1126-1198 CE). *Basalamah. Salah, ibid, 2019*¹⁷.

16 *Basalamah Salah, 2019, THE NOTION OF TRANSLATION IN THE ARAB WORLD: A CRITICAL DEVELOPMENTAL PERSPECTIVE, School of Translation and Interpretation, University of Ottawa. Chapter 8, pp. 169-192. (The notion of translation in the Arab world: A critical developmental perspective). Published in Y. Gambier & U. Steccconi (2019) a World Atlas of Translation, Amsterdam: John Benjamins.*

17 *Basalamah Salah, 2019, THE NOTION OF TRANSLATION IN THE ARAB WORLD: A CRITICAL DEVELOPMENTAL PERSPECTIVE, School of Translation and Interpretation, University of Ottawa. Chapter 8, pp. 169-192. (The notion of translation in the Arab world: A critical developmental perspective). Published in Y. Gambier & U. Steccconi (2019) a World Atlas of Translation, Amsterdam: John Benjamins.*

(Ragab, 2017, p:6)¹⁸, referred to the establishment of modern European-style schools in Egypt in the early twentieth century, under the auspices of Mohamed Ali Basha, (r. 1805- 1848), the Ottoman viceroy of Egypt, saying that it was accompanied by the translation of textbooks, and teaching materials, from European languages into Arabic.

2.2.2: Western history of translation:

When we review the history of translation in the West, this means we are mainly talking about Europe, its early days, renaissance, and its modern history which starts in the nineteenth century, that witnessed a great leap in the West in all aspects of life.

2.2.2.1: Translation in the ancient Greek and Roman times:

Moatti, Claudio, 2006¹⁹, cited that: first we may say that, the Romans brought the principle of translation to its fullest development, Latin literature, was from its beginning translated not only from Greek to Latin, but also from Latin to Greek.

Betlem Soler Pardo, 2013²⁰, mentioned that Eugene Nida places the beginning of translation with the production of the Septuagint which seems to have been the first translation of the Hebrew Old Testament into Greek. It was carried out by seventy-two translators, and it provides us with the basic categories of the history of this practice. This American scholar states

18 Ragab, A. In *A clear Arabic Tongue: Arabic and the Making of Science- Language Regime*. *Isis*, 103 (3) 612-620, (2017).

19 Moatti, Claudia. *Translation, Migration, and Communication in the Roman Empire: Three Aspects of Movement in History*. *Classical Antiquity*, Vol. 25, Issue 1, pp.109—140, (2006).

20 Betlem Soler Pardo, *Translation Studies: An Introduction to the History and Development of (Audiovisual) Translation*. Universidad Alfonso X el Sabio 28691 – Villanueva de la Cañada – Madrid, 2013.

that translation itself was a «science», a theory that was subsequently rejected by others in the second half of the century.

Dean P. Lockwood, 2019, p: 115²¹, tries to dig deep in the history the literature which was the main topic of translation in Europe says: the story begins with a motif which is peculiar - perhaps unique - in the history of the world's literature, about the middle of the third century B.C.

The intellectual intercourse between Greek and Latin in the third and the fourth centuries, of which the most striking example outside religion was the spread of the knowledge of Plotinus doctrines, led to the need for Latin texts of some works considered basic by Greek (*Encyclopedia.com*).

The arts of language, or trivium (*an introductory course at a medieval university involving the study of grammar, rhetoric, and logic*), were well provided for by the works of Donatus, Priscian, Cicero, Quintilian (*Marcus Fabius Quintilianus: Roman rhetorician, known for his Education of an Orator, which means "the comprehensive treatment of the art of rhetoric, and the training of the orator"* – and Boethius. Boethius (ca. 480–524/5) succeeded in transmitting to the Latin several translations of, and commentaries on, Aristotle's works on dialectic. But he also intended to translate or adapt the basic Greek texts on each of the subjects of the quadrivium (*a medieval course involving the mathematical arts of arithmetic, geometry, and music*), into Latin, (Charles Burnett, 2001, p:9)²². The Roman people were 'initiated' into artistic literature. This was accomplished by a Greek, Andronicus, who, after translating the Odyssey into the native non-Hellenic verse of the Latin, carried the process of

21 Dean P. Lockwood, Two Thousand Years of Latin Translation from the Greek, Source: Transactions and Proceedings of the American Philological Association, Vol. 49(1918), pp. 115-129. The Johns Hopkins University Press. Accessed: 17-11-2019.

22 Burnett, Charles, the Coherence of the Arabic-Latin Translation Program in Toledo in the Twelfth Century, 14(1/2), 249–288 Cambridge University Press, (2001).

naturalization to its logical conclusion by rendering tragedy, comedy. All the main traditional forms of Greek literature were soon transplanted to Roman soil, probably within the lifetime of Andronicus, Lockwood P:115 and 119, *ibid*, he also explained the third epoch which we are to consider may be called the Patristic period. More strictly it is the period of the decline of the traditional culture - a decline which did not affect the pagans or semi-pagans until long after it affected the Christians. Christian translations were made in response to a demand which the pagan Romans never felt,

Galvis, S. Jairo, 2013. p:3²³ stated that in the third century B.C, Roman Soldiers returning from Greece, had acquired a taste for Greek theater and translators, including Livius Andronicus, generated free translations of these plays, also states that in the second century B.C. Publius Terentius Afer, better known as Terence, produced Latin texts by translating passages from several Greek texts.

Ghanooni, R. Ali 2012²⁴, says: in fact, the very pioneers of the field "translation" are luminary Roman *Commentators*, such as Cicero, Quintilian, who deem translation as pedagogical exercise, whose debate on translation practice, pertains to word-to-word, and sense-to-sense translation. Cicero (first century B.C) in composing Latin versions of speech, by the Greek orators, writes (I did not translate as an interpreter, but as an orator, keeping the same ideas and the forms, or as one might say, the figures of thought, but in a language which conforms to our usage and in so doing).

23 Galvis, S. Jairo, A Dialectical Reading of the History of Translation, ISSN, 1889-4178, 2013.

24 Ghanooni, R. Ali, A Review of the History of Translation Studies. Yerevan State University, Yerevan. Armenia, 2012.

2.2.2.2: Translation before Renaissance era:

Latin was the lingua franca of the Western world throughout the Middle Ages. There were few translations of Latin works into vernacular languages. Lebert. Marie 2019²⁵, states that in the 9th century, Alfred the Great, King of Wessex in England, was far ahead of his time in commissioning translations from Latin to English of two major works: Bede's "Ecclesiastical History of the English People", and Boethius' "The Consolation of Philosophy". These translations helped improve the underdeveloped English prose.

The Renaissance was a revolution in many ways, and Gutenberg's Modern Printing Press, used since 1449, represents a breakthrough for the world of translation. Thanks to the press, a new class of readers would emerge and translations would multiply (Galvis, S. Jairo, *ibid.* p:6, 2013)

The translation of the Hebrew Bible into Greek is regarded as the first major translation in the Western world. Most Jews had forgotten Hebrew, their ancestral language, and needed the Bible to be available in Greek to be able to read it, Lebert. Marie, *ibid.*, 2019.

Charles Burnett, *ibid.*, P:41, 2001: says: "no dedication exists associated with any translation of the greatest of the Toledan translators, Gerard of Cremona (1114–87), to whom over seventy translations are ascribed, in subjects ranging from mathematics, through medicine to Aristotelian philosophy".

Dina Bacalexi. 2014²⁶, mentioned the three following translators, saying that they were figures in translation in the medieval ages, the Renaissance, they have a great role in translating Galen medical works:

25 Lebert. Marie. A short History of Translation and Translators. Essay, (2019).

26 Dina Bacalexi. Ancient medicine, humanistic medicine: the Renaissance commentaries of Galen, transmission and transformation of knowledge, International Conference Scientiae 2014: Disciplines of knowing in the Early Modern World, Scientiae International Research Group, Apr 2014, Vienne, Austria. Halshs-01639720, 2014.

"Guillaume Cop (or Copus), 1450-1532, was born in Basel, but he spent almost all his life in France and took an active part in the French humanistic movement: as a teacher, teaching medicine in French in Paris. Copus' translation of Galen and of other medical treatises (Hippocrates, Paulus of Aegina) is a faithful one, but also a Latin text emancipated from its Greek original, a regenerated language".

"Francois Valleriole (1504-1580) is a commentator using the translation of Cop. he became a professor of medicine in Torino. Studying medicine in Montpellier undoubtedly played an important role concerning his interest in Galen, as well as in Arabic treatises which he seems to know fairly well: Galenism has been developed since the Middle Ages, thanks to Arnaldus de Villanova (1240-1311) who, as a university rector, introduced the concept of "the new Galen", a rationalistic and scientific approach to medicine through the study of some 35 works either written by Galen or attributed to him".

"Leonhart Fuchs (1501-1566), born in Tubingen where he spent almost all his life teaching medicine in the university, is a Hellenist and a Hebraist, taking an active part in the Lutheran Reformation where ancient languages had to be a part of the theological education, of the new religious ideas".

Sawan, 2014. P, 5, says: 16th century marked a good turn in translation other than the Bible translation only. George Chapman (1559? -1634) translated Homer's Iliad and Odyssey in metrical form (iambic pentameter and iambic heptameter) which became his most famous works, from 1598 he published his translation of Iliad in installments and in 1616 the complete Iliad and Odyssey appeared in The Whole Works of Homer, the first English translation, which until Pope's was the most popular in the English language and was the way most English speakers encountered these poems. His translation of Homer was much admired by John Keats. Chapman also translated the Homeric Hymns, the Georgics of Vergil, the works of Hesiod (1618, dedicated to Francis Bacon), the Hero and Leander of Musaeus (1618) and the fifth Satire of Juvenal (1624).

Chapman's translation of Homer's epic the *Odyssey*, originally published in folio, 1614—16, has become as rare as to be inaccessible to the general reader and comparatively unknown to the more curious student of old English Literature (translation). Martin Luther (1483-1546) had published his German translation of the New Testament in 1522 and, he and his collaborators completed the translation of the Old Testament in 1534, when the whole was published. He continued to refining the translation until the end of his life. Others had translated the Bible into German, but Luther tailored his translation to his own doctrine. Luther's translation used the variant of German spoken at the Saxon Chancellery intelligible to both northern and southern

Germans. Luther Bible made a significant contribution to the evolution of German language and literature, and of course to translation²⁷.

2.2.2.3: Post Renaissance era:

In 1660 the Dutch philosopher Benedict (Baruch) Spinoza wrote in Latin his *Short Treatise on God, Man, and His Well-Being*. A few months later, at the request of some friends "whose Latin was less than fluent", he translated his text into Dutch. Although originally written in Latin, like all of Spinoza's other writings, the work has only come down to us in a Dutch translation, and it was not published or generally known until its discovery in the nineteenth century.

From the twentieth century until this time considered as the most prosperous period in the history of translation of the West, which represents the center of the modern civilization, new and many studies were performed, and new theories were emerged, in this time all efforts and word done thanks to the Western scholars such like Eugene A. Nida, 1914-

²⁷ Sawant, Datta G. *HISTORY OF TRANSLATION, Toshniwal Arts, Commerce & Science Co. January 2013. Uploaded to author site Feb. 2015.*

2011, Peter Newmark 1916-2011, James S. Holmes 1924-1986, Jeremy Munday "B. 1960, and Muna Baker B. 1953, all those and many others have great contributions in the varied language sciences, which represent a immense human heritage.

2.2.3: History of Machine Translation MT:

2.2.3.1: Early times of MT:

Even though Machine Translation (MT) has been a practical process only since the 1950's, the idea of machine translation has been alive for more than 300 years.

In the 17th century Rene Descartes introduced the idea of a universal language, a language that in different tongues shared both the same content and symbols. Today there isn't such a wide spread language apart from perhaps the mathematical symbols. But we can find universal languages in smaller universes. For example, the Chinese writing system, where there are many different dialects but each and every one of them uses the same writing system. English could also be considered as a form of a universal language, Maria Hedblom, 2010, P: 5²⁸.

Nabeel T. Alsohybe, Neama D. and Fadl Ba-Alwi, 2017²⁹, cited: Unfortunately, translation is a difficult task, because of its dependency on the Natural Language Processing (NLP) and the structure of the languages. The only way to make sense was by using the artificial intelligence because it merges the different required types of sciences during the translation

28 Hedblom, Maria. Machine Translation, A Rosetta stone for the 21th century?, Kognitionsvetenskap 2, 2010.

29 Nabeel T. Alsohybe, Neama Abdulaziz Dahan, and Fadl Mutaheer Ba-Alwi, Machine-Translation History and Evolution: Survey for Arabic-English Translations. Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology. 23(4): 1-19, 2017; Article No.CJAST.36124. ISSN: 2231-0843, 2017.

process. A new field of the Machine Learning was to develop algorithms for the Natural Language Processing (NLP).

Daniel Stein. 2013³⁰, says: the most likely the first thoughts on MT emerged out of two philosophical schools that dealt with the nature of language and resulted in similar insights, although stemming from different directions. The first was directed at creating secret languages and codes in order to communicate in secrecy. The second evolved from the ideal of a universal language, which would allow communication without borders in the times after Babylonian language confusion.

2.2.3.2: The beginning of Twentieth Century:

The first known proposal for transfer-based mechanical translation can be traced to a 1933 patent a special purpose mechanical translation device. Trojanski (1933) proposes a three-part translation process broadly similar to the analysis-transfer-generation paradigm Lane Schwartz, 2016, p: 26.

To the best of our knowledge, none of these machines give precise translation like the human translation, (Nabeel T. Alsohybe, Neama D. and Fadl Ba-Alwi: *ibid*).

The earliest known suggestion that a machine could be made to translate languages was a patent application filed in Moscow in 1933 by Smirnov-Trojanski, (Allen, Harold, and Jay, 1975, p: 418)³¹.

Although the first systems of Machine translation MT were built on the first computers in the year's right after World War II, the history of MT does not begin, as often stated, in the 1940s, but some hundred years ago.

30 Daniel Stein. Machine Translation, Past, Present and Future. Translation: Computation, Corpora, Cognition. Special Issue on Language Technologies for a Multilingual Europe, Vol. 3, No. 1. ISSN 2193-6986, (2013).

31 Allen Kent, Harold, Lancour, Jay E. Daily, New York: Marcel Dekker, Machine Translation, From: Encyclopedia of Library and Information Science, ed.] 1975.

In order to judge current developments in MT properly, it is important to understand the historical development.

In World War II, the decipherment of the German ENIGMA code regarded as a crucial point. The British team around Alan Turing, located in Bletchley Park, was responsible for this urgent project and achieved the breaking of the code by means of statistical methods that were processed on computing machines. Without their knowledge, the scientists laid the foundations for practical MT, (Stein 2013, *ibid*).

In the next few years Booth with others, notably Kathleen H. V. Britten at the Institute for Advanced Study in Princeton and Richard H. Richens of the Commonwealth Bureau of Plant Breeding and Genetics, Cambridge, England, did some experimenting. Booth and Richens worked out a simple word for word translation program in 1947, Allen, Harold, and Jay, 1975, p: 418 P: 419, *ibid*.

In 1948 Richens suggested an improvement, an ordinary dictionary, he reasoned, contains only the basic forms of words, the nominative singular of nouns, the infinitive of verbs; yet the case and number of noun forms and the person and number of verb forms are essential to real comprehension.

Peter, Kastberg. 2012³²: says: ever since machine translation, related research truly took off in the 1930s primarily because technological advances made it possible, the dream has been to develop a machine capable of translating without any other human interference than the actual order to translate a given text from language A to language B. Directed by the Allies' successful attempts at breaking the German military codes during World War II, attempts were made to develop FAMT-programs from the middle of the 1940s.

32 Kastberg, Peter,. (2012) Machine Translation Tools – Tools of the Translator's Trade. Communication & Language at Work, Issue No. 1.

2.2.3.3: From the 50s to 70s of Last Century:

Hutchins, W. 1994, p. 2322-2332³³, expresses that a breakthrough was achieved in the middle of the 1950s when a team of scientists from Georgetown University, during a large-scaled American analysis dubbed ALPAC (Automatic Language Processing Advisory Committee), voices within the area expressed doubts as to the possibility of ever being able to develop a fully automated translation program.

Hutchins, W. 1994:P: 431-445, stated that some researchers bluntly said that Fully Automated Machine Translation FAMT was impossible.

Allen, Harold, and Jay,1975 (p: 223) explained that on July 15, 1949 Weaver sent his "Translation" to some 200 of his acquaintances. To most it was the first suggestion they had ever heard that a computer might be used to translate languages.

Bar-Hillel at Massachusetts Institute of technology MIT became in 1951 the first full-time worker in the field. He soon wrote a paper describing the current state of MT research. The first published paper also appeared in 1951. This was by Oswald and Fletcher. Convinced that German word order must be rearranged for an adequate translation to English, the authors proposed tentative ways of doing it Allen, Harold, and Jay, *ibid.*, pp: 418, 421,1975.

Consequently, research and development of fully automated machine translation FAMT-programs was either assigned a lower priority or completely terminated. Practically, this meant that FAMT 'hibernated' throughout the 1970s; and it was not before the development within information technology gained serious momentum in the 1980s (especially

33 Hutchins, W. John. (1994), MACHINE TRANSLATION: HISTORY AND GENERAL PRINCIPLES. The encyclopedia of languages and linguistics, ed. R.E.Asher (Oxford: Pergamon Press, 1994), vol. 5.

in regard to storage capacity and processing speed), that FAMT again was taken seriously.

Many pieces of research discuss the Machine Translation, which comes in the following three categories: statistical machine translation (SMT), Machine Translation using Semantic Web, and neural machine translation (NMT) ,(Nabeel T. Alsohybe, Neama Abdulaziz Dahan, and Fadl Mutaheer Ba-Alwiibid., 2017,).

During the 1950s and the development of computers, MT had prime years and the expectations were very high. Surprisingly little of the early MT was based on theoretical linguistics. Instead, the approaches focused on word-for-word translation and statistical methods. After a couple of decades, it was found that the expectations may have been a bit overrated and the business was rather drawn back for some time.

The first real successful MT after the first wave was in the 1977's when the METEO evolved (*METEO System – machine translation system, especially designed for the translation of the weather forecasts, issued dially by "Environment Canada"*) by the TAUM group (*Traduction Automatique a l'Universite' de Montere'al*) it is (*a research group which was set up at the university of Montreal in 1965*), at the university of Montreal, (Maria Hedblom, *ibid.*, P: 5, 2010).

The MIT conference had its intended effect of stimulating further activity in MT. In September 1952 the first discussion of MT was held at the Seventh International Congress of Linguists in London with forty presents. Through 1952 there had been only one published paper, that by Oswald and Fletcher; in 1953 there were nine; in 1954, eight more; and for the next 10 or 15 years a gradually increasing number each year Allen, Harold, and Jay, 1975, p:418, and 422. The 1960s in the United States and in the USSR were stimulating times for all science, and MT was accepted as a fledgling science. English was the language of the largest number of scientific

publications; Russian was second. Reading each other's publications was of the highest priority, Allen, Harold, and Jay, *ibid.*

In the United States and in the United Kingdom few could read Russian and many translations were published, whereas in the USSR a knowledge of English was widespread and important books and journals were as likely to be reprinted in the original as to be translated.

2.2.3.4: The 80s and the 90s of the 20th centuries:

In 1980, Martin Kay called for a re-examination of the role of humans and machines in the translation process, away from the lofty goal sought by many during the mid-20th century of fully automatic high-quality machine translation, and towards a gradual partnership between human translators and well-designed computer programs built to modestly assist their human counterparts, Lane Schwartz 2016, p:2³⁴.

Olivia Craciunescu, 2004³⁵, cited: The beginning of the 1990's witnessed vital developments in machine translation with a radical change in strategy from translation based on grammatical rules to that based on bodies of texts and examples (for example, the Reverso Program "*program/website specialized in online translation aids and language services*").

Language was no longer perceived as a static entity governed by fixed rules, but as a dynamic corpus that change according to use and users, evolving through time and adapting to social and cultural realities. To this day machine translation continues to progress. Large companies are now using it more, which also increases software sales to the general public. This situation has led to the creation of on-line machine translation services such as AltaVista (web search engine, established in 1995), which offer rapid email services, web pages, etc. in the desired language, as well as to

34 Schwartz, Lane , *The History and Promise of Machine Translation*, 2016.

35 Olivia Craciunescu. *Machine Translation and Computer-Assisted Translation: a New Way of Translating?*, *Translation Journal*, Volume 8, No. 3 July 2004.

the availability of multilingual dictionaries, encyclopedias, and free, direct-access terminology databases.

The French Textile Institute also used MT to translate abstracts from and into French, English, German and Spanish; Brigham Young University started a project to translate Mormon texts by automated translation; and Xerox used Systran (founded by Dr. Peter Toma in 1968, it is one of the oldest MT companies, Systran software enables individuals to communicate with each other in multiple languages, "*from Wikipedia and SYSTRAN technology website*") to translate technical manuals. Beginning in the late 1980s, as computational power increased and became less expensive, more interest was shown in statistical models for machine translation. Various MT companies were launched, including Trados, which was the first to develop and market translation memory technology. The first commercial MT system for Russian/English/German-Ukrainian was developed at Kharkov State University.

MT on the web started with SYSTRAN Offering free translation of small texts, followed by AltaVista BabelFish (online translation service), which racked up 500,000 requests a day. More innovations during this time included MOSES, the open-source statistical MT engine, a text/SMS translation service for mobiles in Japan, and a mobile phone with built-in speech-to-speech translation functionality for English, Japanese and Chinese. Recently, Google announced that "Google Translate" translates roughly enough text to fill 1 million books in one day (Wikipedia, free encyclopedia).

2.3: Definition of Translation:

This part is answering the question: what is Translation? this term connected to the meaning, it shows how different ideas, methods, and theories have emerged because of these disagreements among scholars on this issue.

The term ‘translation’ has several meanings: it can refer to the product (the translated text) or the process (the act of translating). The ‘process of translation’ between two different written languages involves the translator changing the original text from the ‘source language’ (SL) into a ‘target text’ (TT) in a different verbal language or ‘target language’ (TL). This corresponds to interlingual translation and is one of the three categories of translation described by the Russo- American structuralist Roman Jakobson (1974) in his seminal paper “On Linguistic Aspects of Translation”.

Etymological meaning: translate- 'carry across', past participle of transfer, from the Latin transferre, from trans-'across'+ferre 'to bear'³⁶.

2.3.1: Lexical Definition:

1- The Longman Dictionary of Word Origins (1983³⁷), mentions that the word ‘translate’ originates from the Latin word translatus (trans+latus), which means ‘to carry over’; implicitly meaning to carry over meaning from one word to another.

2- Oxford Dictionary of English, 2018, defines translation as follows:

- The process of translating words or text from one language into another, like "*the translation of the Bible into English*".
- A written or spoken rendering of the meaning of a word or text in another language, like "*a Spanish translation of Calvin's great work*".

³⁶ Oxford Dictionary of English, version: 11.1.511, 2019.

³⁷ Longman Dictionary of Word Origins (1983).

- The conversion of something from one form or medium into another, such as "*the translation of research findings into clinical practice*".

The first definition refers to a "series of actions or steps" dealing with words or texts, while the second gives more details about this process "written or spoken", the third definition shows the "change or adaptation" occurred, because of this process.

3- Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary & Thesaurus defines it as "*the communication of meaning from one language (the source) to another language (the target). Translation refers to written information, whereas interpretation refers to spoken information*"³⁸.

2.3.2 : Other Definition Attempts :

1- Preliminary definition: Sonia Colina, 2015, p: 4³⁹, tries to set a preliminary definition, saying that translation refers to the process of, or the product resulting from transferring or mediating written text(s) of different lengths (ranging from words and sentences to entire books) from one human language to another.

This definition attempts to capture the essence of the concept of translation, i.e., the core elements that most scholars and practitioners will agree are present in the concept of translation, from one natural language to another, as summarized below.

These core elements are:

- written texts
- transfer or mediation
- from one natural language to another

38 *Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary*.

39 Colina, Sonia, *Fundamentals of Translation*, Cambridge University Press 978-1-107-03539-3, 2015.

It is important to stress that translation deals with the transfer of written text. When the text or the medium is oral, however, the term used is interpreting or interpretation. In lay circles, one can sometimes hear the terms translation and translator being used to refer to interpreting and interpreter, with no distinction being made concerning medium.

2- In translating, Sonia Colina, *ibid*, 2015 p: 6, remarked that the language from which a text is translated is known as the source language (SL) and the language of the translated product is the target language (TL). What is also referred to as the original text is generally known as the source text (ST) and the translated text is the target text (TT). For instance, in a translation of Shakespeare's Hamlet into Spanish, the ST would be the English original text and the Spanish translation the TT.

3- Andy Bayu, 2016, p: 1, defines translation as a process of rendering meaning, ideas, or messages of a text from one language to other language.

4- According to Nida and Taber (Shiyang Ran, 2009)⁴⁰, "Translating consists in reproducing in the receptor language the closest natural equivalent of the source-language message, first in terms of meaning and secondly in terms of style".

5- Yaroslav V. Sokolovsky, 2010, p: 286⁴¹, categorized translation according to his own classification:

a) Translation is a process:

- *Translation is a specific oral or written activity aimed at the recreation of an oral or written text (utterance) existing in one language into a text in another language, accompanied by keeping the invariance of content, qualities of the original and author's authenticity.*

40 Shiyang Ran, Philosophical Interpretation on E. A. Nida's Definition of Translation, Asian Social Science, Vol. 5, No 10, Oct. 2009.

41 Yaroslav V. Sokolovsky. On the Linguistic Definition of Translation, Siberian Federal University, 2010.

- Translation is a type of speech activity, aimed at transmitting a message, doubling the components of communication in those cases, when there is a discrepancy between codes used by the sender and the receiver of the message

b) Translation is a process and a result of this process:

- *Translation is an activity*, which consists of variable re-expression, converting of the text in one language into the text in a different language, which is carried out by a translator, who creatively chooses variants depending on language variability resources, text type, translation tasks, and under the influence of his (her) own personal individuality; translation is also a result of this activity
- *Translation is a process (and its result)* caused by social necessity of information (content) transmitting, expressed in a written or oral text in one language by the means of an equivalent (adequate) text in another language.

c) Translation is a communication:

- *Translation can be defined as a way to provide inter-lingual communication* by the means of creation of a text in TL (target language), intended to fully replace the original text.
- *Translation is a social function of communicative mediation between people, who use different language systems.* This function is carried out as a psychophysical activity of a bilingual person aimed at the reflection of reality on the basis of his (her) individual abilities as an interpreter, accomplishing, transition from one semiotic system to another with the purpose of equivalent, i.e. maximally complete, but always partial transmission of a system of meanings, contained in a source message, from one communicant to another.

d) Translation is a skill:

- *Translation is a craft consisting of the attempt to replace a written message and/or statement in one language by the same message and/or statement in another language.*

6- Wang, Zheng, 2017. P: 628⁴², thinks that the communicative translation according to Newmark is an attempt to produce on its readers an effect as close as possible to that obtained on the readers of the original.

7- For Kashgarym, 2008⁴³, translation "as a subject" is defined as all the processes and methods used to convey meaning of the source language into the target language by means of the verb "translate" has been equated with synonyms such as "reader", "rephrase", "transmit", "re express" "replace, that We "render", "reproduce", "convey", and "transfer".

These definitions agree on are the following:

- *Translation involves determining two extremes at the same time; the SL demands and the TL demands.*
- *Translation involves thinking and rethinking, expressing and re-expressing.*

8- Long, Jixingm 2013, P: 108⁴⁴. said that Catford attempts to describe translation in terms of a specific linguistic theory (functional linguistics), he defines it as: *the replacement of textual material in one language (SL) by equivalent textual material in another language (T)*. There are two key words in this definition: textual material and equivalent. To begin with textual material, it means only one level or some levels of a language and it is used here to stand for a part or some parts of the source text. In normal conditions, it is quite difficult to translate an entire text, so textual material,

42 Wang Zheng, Exploring Newmark's Communicative Translation and Text Typology, Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research, volume 185, 2017.

43 Kashgarym, Amira, Introduction to Translation, Lecture Notes, 2008.

44 Long Jixing, Translation Definitions in Different Paradigms. Canadian Social Science, 9 (4), 107-115, 2013.

to some extent, reflects just a part or some parts of the source text for it is equivalent only on the level of lexis and grammar. This raises the question of equivalence.

9- Julianne House, 2015, pp: 3-4⁴⁵, suggests that translation can be defined as the result of a linguistic-textual operation in which a text in one language is re-contextualized in another language. As a linguistic-textual operation, translation is, however, subject to, and substantially influenced by, a variety of extra-linguistic factors and conditions. It is this interaction between 'inner' linguistic-textual and 'outer' extra-linguistic, contextual factors that makes translation such a complex phenomenon. J. House, 2015, *ibid*, mentioned 11 interacting factors need to be considered when looking at translation, which are:

- *the structural characteristics, the expressive potential and the constraints of the two languages involved in translation;*
- *the extra-linguistic world which is "cut up" in different ways by source and target languages;*
- *the source text with its linguistic-stylistic-aesthetic features that belong to the norms of usage holding in the source lingua-cultural community;*
- *the linguistic-stylistic-aesthetic norms of the target lingua-cultural community;*
- *the target language norms internalized by the translator;*
- *intersexuality governing the totality of the text in the target culture;*
- *traditions, principles, histories and ideologies of translation holding in the target lingua-cultural community;*
- *the translational "brief" given to the translator by the person(s) or institution commissioning the translation;*

45 Julianne House, *Translation Quality Assessment, Past and Present*, Routledge, Taylor and Francis Group, London and New York, 2015.

- *the translator's workplace conditions;*
- *the translator's knowledge, expertise, ethical stance and attitudinal profiles as well as her subjective theory of translation;*
- *the translation receptors' knowledge, expertise, ethical stance and attitudinal profiles of the translator as well as their subjective theories of translation.*

10- Translation, according to B. Sowndarya, and S. Lavanya⁴⁶, is an interpretative *process*; they explained that the nature of translation depends upon the nature of the document. Translation of a technical or promotional document is easier and requires less skill and expertise than the translation of a text of literature. The vocabulary, grammatical rules and the sentence structures would match with the nature of the document, the source language and the target audience. A successful translation satisfies the needs of the target audience, either in terms of suitable structures or forms or in terms of the appropriate transfer of meaning from the source text to the target text.

11- Long Jixing, *ibid.*, 2013, p: 110, referred to André Lefevere's work "*Translation, Rewriting and the Manipulation of Literary Fame is a classic*" of translation studies saying that Lefevere views translating as "*a process of rewriting*", and points out that "*rewriting is basically determined by two factors—ideology and poetics*". Unlike the traditional translation theorists, Lefevere shifts the focus of translation to the relationships among politics, culture and translation, which present a new perspective for translation study.

46 B. Sowndarya, and S. Lavanya. Nature and Scope of Translation. IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS) e-ISSN: 2279-0837, p-ISSN: 2279-0845. PP 07-09, 2007.

2.3.3: The Scope of Translation

B. Sowndarya, and S. Lavanya, *ibid.*, 2007, in their work "Nature and Scope of Translation", stated that; in the earlier days, translation was considered to be a sub-branch of linguistics, and gradually it developed into an inter-disciplinary field of study. In the last three decades of the 20th century, Translation Studies started functioning as an autonomous branch of study. Today, in this age of globalization, the scope of translation is immense. The significance and relevance of translation in our daily life is multidimensional and extensive. Translation helps us to know about the developments in the field of creative arts, education, literature, business, science and politics. In the post-modern world, translation has become so relevant that people visualize it as a socio-cultural bridge between communities and countries. People now feel the importance of interacting and remaining connected with the people of other socio-cultural communities, both in their respective countries as well as countries across the world. In this backdrop, translation has acquired an increasing importance and satisfies individual, societal and national needs.

2.4 Theories, Concepts and Studies of Translation:

For specialists in language sciences, or, at least in translation, the "term" Translation, doesn't merely mean substitute or transfer a text in a natural language, into another, it is something more complicated than it appears, that many factors interact in this "process", this section trying to give a concrete idea about this issue, by discussing "theories, concepts, and studies" that emerged in this field.

2.4.1 Theories and Concepts of Translation:

Peter Newmark, p: 19⁴⁷, said that translation theory is a misnomer, a blanket term; in fact, translation theory is neither a theory, nor a science,

47 Newmark, Peter, *Approaches to Translation*, Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press, 2001.

but the body of knowledge that we have, and have still to have about the process of translating. He adds that translation theory's main concern is to determine appropriate translation methods, for the widest range of texts, or text categories, and it provides a framework of principles, restricted rules, and hints for translating texts and criticizing translations.

We are going to review the most prominent translation theories, the linguistic theory, cultural theory, equivalence theory, and the general theory.

2.4.1.1: Linguistic Theory:

First, we have to shed a light on Linguistic theorizing, and the aspects it covers, it is as follows:

- 1) Theories in the fields of grammar (including phonology, morphology, and syntax) and lexicology are formulated to understand the nature and structure of language(s). Theories in linguistic semantics aim at scientific accounts of the rather elusive phenomenon of how linguistic elements and structures can convey meanings.
- 2) Cognitive-linguistic theories try to model what speakers know about language and how the structure of languages relates to other cognitive abilities like perception and attention allocation.
- 3) Psycholinguistic theories try to model what goes on in the minds of language users during ongoing processing and how children acquire languages.
- 4) Theories in linguistic pragmatics model how communication works and how understanding comes about.
- 5) Theories in variational linguistics and sociolinguistics explain patterns of variation (accents, dialects, register, etc.) and investigate parameters influencing these patterns (age, sex, social and regional background.
- 6) Theories in historical linguistics try to model why and in which ways languages change and are related to each other historically.

Schmid, Hans-Jörg., 2012, p: 7-17-21-22⁴⁸ cited Saussure and Noam Chomsky major contributions to linguistic theorizing:

First, Saussure contribution:

- *Language is a socially shared system of signs*
- *In the study of language, usage (parole) and the system (langue) have to be kept a part. The target of linguistics should be the generalizations made on the level of langue, rather than the individual, physically real usage-events taking place in parole.*
- *Linguistic systems should (also) be studied from a purely synchronic perspective.*
- *Signs only have significance in the system by virtue differences (oppositions) to other signs; this gives rise to structure, which is of more fundamental importance than the individual elements of the system.*
- *The oppositions making up the system are tacitly agreed upon by the members of the speech community by way of convention; individual speakers have tacit knowledge about them.*

Second, in his 1957 book, *Syntactic Structures*⁴⁹, Chomsky argues for an approach to linguistics that does not stop at the description of existing sentences and utterances but aims to come up with an explanation of the knowledge required by speakers for them to be able to potentially generate syntactic representations of all sentences that are considered grammatical in their native language and to decide which sentences are ungrammatical.

The key characteristics of Chomsky's approach can be summarized as following:

48 Hans-Jörg Schmid, München, *Linguistic theories, approaches and methods*, Stuttgart-Weimar- Metzler, 371-394, 2012.

49 Noam Chomsky. *Syntactic Structures*, Mouton & Co. 1957

- *Generativism and productivity: the target of linguistic theorizing is the description of grammar, largely defined as the generative capacity, i.e. competence or I language – of an idealized native speaker to produce and understand an infinite number of sentences and to judge whether sentences are grammatical or ungrammatical.*
- *Derivation: sentences are the product of derivations of more complex structures from simpler structures carried out by means of a limited number of clearly defined operations.*
- *Innateness: the acquisition of linguistic competence builds on innate knowledge about linguistic structure common to all languages and known as Universal Grammar.*
- *Autonomy: language is a very special human faculty; grammar, in the sense of ‘linguistic competence’, does not rely on non-linguistic cognition, and grammar, in the sense of ‘model of linguistic competence’, must not rely on models of non- linguistic cognition.*
- *Modularity: within grammar, the generative capacity mainly resides in the syntactic component; the lexicon is, by definition, not rule-governed and therefore of much less interest to linguistic modeling.*
- *Focus on context-free structure, form and formalization: linguistic modeling has to focus on structural and formal aspects of language rather than functional ones and strive for formalized accounts of structures; functional considerations such as ‘what is the communicative impact of a sentence?’ or ‘what are the purposes that syntactic structures serve?’ are irrelevant.*

2.4.1.2: Cultural Theory:

Translation is a kind of activity, which inevitably involves at least two languages and two cultural traditions. Toury 1978, p:200⁵⁰ as this statement implies, translators are permanently faced with the problem of how to treat the cultural aspects implicit in a source text (ST) and of finding the most appropriate technique of successfully conveying these aspects in the target language (TL). These problems may vary in scope depending on the cultural and linguistic gap between the two, or more languages concerned (Nida 1964, p: 130)⁵¹.

The cultural implications for translation may take several forms ranging from lexical content and syntax to ideologies and ways of life in a given culture. The translator also has to decide on the importance given to certain cultural aspects and to what extent it is necessary or desirable to translate them into the TL. The aims of the ST will also have implications for translation as well as the intended readership for both the ST and the target text (TT).

Considering the cultural implications for a translated text implies recognizing all of these problems and taking into account several possibilities before deciding on the solution which appears the most appropriate in each specific case. Before applying these methods to the chosen text, this essay will examine the importance of culture in translation through a literature review. The different general procedures of treating the cultural implications for translation will be examined as well as analyzing the ST and the aims of the author. The translation process will also be

50 Toury, G. "The Nature and Role of Norms in Translation." In Venuti, L. *The Translation Studies Reader*. London: Routledge, 1978, revised 1995.

51 Nida, E. "Principles of Correspondence" In Venuti, L. *The Translation Studies Reader*. London: Routledge, 1964.

treated using specific examples found in the ST before discussing the success of aforementioned theoretical methods applied to the TT.

The definition of "culture" as given in the Concise Oxford Dictionary varies from descriptions of the "Arts" to plant and bacteria cultivation and includes a wide range of intermediary aspects. More specifically concerned with language and translation, Newmark 1988, p:94⁵², defines culture as "the way of life and its manifestations that are peculiar to a community that uses a particular language as its means of expression" thus acknowledging that each language group has its own culturally specific features. He further clearly states that operationally he does "not regard language as a component or feature of culture" (Newmark 1988, *ibid.*, p:95,) in direct opposition to the view taken by Vermeer who states that "language is part of a culture" (Newmark, 1988, *ibid.*, p:222).

According to Newmark, Vermeer's stance would imply the impossibility to translate whereas for the latter, translating the source language (SL) into a suitable form of TL is part of the translator's role in transcultural communication.

The notion of culture is essential to considering the implications for translation and, despite the differences in opinion as to whether language is part of culture or not, the two notions appear to be inseparable. Discussing the problems of correspondence in translation, Nida confers equal importance to both linguistic and cultural differences between the SL and the TL and concludes that "differences between cultures may cause more severe complications for the translator than do differences in language structure" (Nida, 1964, p:130)⁵³. It is further explained that parallels in culture often provide a common understanding despite significant formal

52 Newmark, Peter .. A Textbook of Translation. New York: Prentice Hall, 1988

53 Nida, E. "Principles of Correspondence." In Venuti, L. The Translation Studies Reader. London: Routledge, 1964.

shifts in the translation. The cultural implications for translation are thus of significant importance as well as lexical concerns.

Lotman's theory states that "no language can exist unless it is steeped in the context of culture; and no culture can exist which does not have at its centre, the structure of natural language (Lotman, 1978:211-32)⁵⁴. Bassnett, 1980: 13-14,⁵⁵ underlines the importance of this double consideration when translating by stating that language is "the heart within the body of culture," the survival of both aspects being interdependent. Linguistic notions of transferring meaning are seen as being only part of the translation process; "a whole set of extra-linguistic criteria" must also be considered. As Bassnett further points out, "the translator must tackle the SL text in such a way that the TL version will correspond to the SL version... To attempt to impose the value system of the SL culture onto the TL culture is dangerous ground" (Bassnett, *ibid.*,1980, p:23,). Thus, when translating, it is important to consider not only the lexical impact on the TL reader, but also the manner in which cultural aspects may be perceived and make translating decisions accordingly.

A variety of different approaches have been examined in relation to the cultural implications for translation. It is necessary to examine these approaches bearing in mind the inevitability of translation loss when the text is, as here, culture bound. Considering the nature of the text and the similarities between the ideal ST and TT reader, an important aspect is to determine how much missing background information should be provided by the translator using these methods. It has been recognized that in order

54 Lotman, J., Uspensky, B. "On the Semiotic Mechanism of Culture," *New Literary History*, pp. 211-32, 1978.

55 Bassnett- McGuire, S *Translation Studies: First Edition 1980. Revised Edition*, London, Routledge, 1991.

to preserve specific cultural references certain additions need to be brought to the TT.

Thus the cultural implications for translation of this kind of ST do not justify using either of these two extremes and tend to correspond to the definition of communicative translation, attempting to ensure that content and language present in the SL context is fully acceptable and comprehensible to the TL readership. (Newmark, *ibid.*,1988,).

2.4.1.3: Equivalence Theory:

The comparison of texts in different languages inevitably involves a theory of equivalence. Equivalence can be said to be the central issue in translation although its definition, relevance, and applicability within the field of translation theory have caused heated controversy, and many different theories of the concept of equivalence have been elaborated within this field in the past fifty years.

The theory of equivalence that interpreted by some of the most innovative theorists in this field such as Vinay and Darbelnet, Jakobson, Nida and Taber, Catford, House, and finally Baker. These theorists have studied equivalence in relation to the translation process, using different approaches, and have provided fruitful ideas for further study on this topic. Their theories will be analyzed in chronological order so that it will be easier to follow the evolution of this concept. These theories can be substantially divided into three main groups. In the first there are those translation scholars who are in favour of a linguistic approach to translation and who seem to forget that translation in itself is not merely a matter of linguistics. In fact, when a message is transferred from the SL to TL, the translator is also dealing with two different cultures at the same time. This particular aspect seems to have been taken into consideration by the second group of theorists who regard translation equivalence as being essentially a transfer of the message from the SC to the TC and a pragmatic/semantic or

functionally oriented approach to translation. Finally, there are other translation scholars who seem to stand in the middle, such as Baker for instance, who claims that equivalence is used 'for the sake of convenience—because most translators are used to it rather than because it has any theoretical status' (Kenny, 1998, P: 77)⁵⁶.

Catford's approach to translation equivalence clearly differs from that adopted by Nida since Catford had a preference for a more linguistic-based approach to translation and this approach is based on the linguistic work of Firth and Halliday. His main contribution in the field of translation theory is the introduction of the concepts of types and shifts of translation. Catford proposed very broad types of translation in terms of three criteria:

- 1- *The extent of translation (full translation vs partial translation);*
- 2- *The grammatical rank at which the translation equivalence is established (rank-bound translation vs. unbounded translation);*
- 3- *The level of the language involved in translation (total translation vs. restricted translation).*

House, J. 1977⁵⁷ is in favor of semantic and pragmatic equivalence and argues that ST and TT should match one another in function. House suggests that it is possible to characterize the function of a text by determining the situational dimensions of the ST.

In fact, according to her theory, every text is in itself is placed within a particular situation which has to be correctly identified and taken into account by the translator. After the ST analysis, House is in a position to evaluate a translation; if the ST and the TT differ substantially on situational features, then they are not functionally equivalent, and the

56 Kenny, Dorothy, 'Equivalence', in the RoutledgeEncyclopaedia of Translation Studies, edited by Mona Baker, London and New York: Routledge, 77-80, 1998.

57 House, Julianne, A Model for Translation Quality Assessment, Tübingen: Gunter Narr, 1977 .

translation is not of a high quality. In fact, she acknowledges that 'a translation text should not only match its source text in function, but employ equivalent situational-dimensional means to achieve that function' (House, *ibid.*, 1977, p:49).

Central to House's discussion is the concept of overt and covert translations. In an overt translation the TT audience is not directly addressed and there is therefore no need at all to attempt to recreate a 'second original' since an overt translation 'must overtly be a translation' (*ibid.*:189). By covert translation, on the other hand, is meant the production of a text which is functionally equivalent to the ST. House also argues that in this type of translation the ST 'is not specifically addressed to a TC audience' (House, *ibid.*, p.:194).

New adjectives have been assigned to the notion of equivalence (grammatical, textual, pragmatic equivalence, and several others) and made their appearance in the plethora of recent works in this field. An extremely interesting discussion of the notion of equivalence can be found in Baker (1992) who seems to offer a more detailed list of conditions upon which the concept of equivalence can be defined. She explores the notion of equivalence at different levels, in relation to the translation process, including all different aspects of translation and hence putting together the linguistic and the communicative approach. She distinguishes between:

1- Equivalence that can appear at word level and above word level, when translating from one language into another. Baker acknowledges that, in a bottom-up approach to translation, equivalence at word level is the first element to be taken into consideration by the translator. In fact, when the translator starts analyzing the ST s/he looks at the words as single units in order to find a direct 'equivalent' term in the TL (Baker, 1992: 11-12).

- 2- *Grammatical equivalence, when referring to the diversity of grammatical categories across languages. She notes that grammatical rules may vary across languages and this may pose some problems in terms of finding a direct correspondence in the TL.*
- 3- *Textual equivalence, when referring to the equivalence between a SL text and a TL text in terms of information and cohesion. Texture is a very important feature in translation since it provides useful guidelines for the comprehension and analysis of the ST, which can help the translator in his or her attempt to produce a cohesive and coherent text for the TC audience in a specific context.*
- 4- *Pragmatic equivalence, when referring to implicatures and strategies of avoidance during the translation process. Implicature is not about what is explicitly said but what is implied. Therefore, the translator needs to work out implied meanings in translation in order to get the ST message across. The role of the translator is to recreate the author's intention in another culture in such a way that enables the TC reader to understand it clearly.*

The notion of equivalence is undoubtedly one of the most problematic and controversial areas in the field of translation theory. The term has caused, and it seems quite probable that it will continue to cause, heated debates within the field of translation studies. This term has been analyzed, evaluated and extensively discussed from different points of view and has been approached from many different perspectives. The difficulty in defining equivalence seems to result in the impossibility of having a universal approach to this notion.

2.4.2 Translation Studies:

This part discussing the efforts by scholars in the fields of language sciences to found bases, on which translation can be dealt with through well –organized thoughts and ideas built on scientific theorization, below

the research details the varied contributions of the specialists in the field of "Translation Studies" in the 20th century.

2.4.2.1: An overview:

The following scholars have great participation in the field of translation studies, their efforts in this area formalized the scientific theorization of this important language studies.

2.4.2.2: Munday J. and Hatim B:in his book (2004, p:5)⁵⁸ said that its main aim is to introduce the reader to major concepts and models of translation studies. Because of the rapid growth in the area, particularly over the last decade, difficult decisions have had to be taken regarding the selection of material. We have decided, for reasons of space and consistency of approach, to focus on written translation rather than oral translation (the latter is commonly known as interpreting or interpretation), although the overlaps make a clear distinction impossible.

Munday, *ibid.*, 2004, going on that the term "translation" itself has several meanings: it can refer to the general subject field, the product (the text that has been translated) or the process (the act of producing the translation, otherwise known as translating). The process of translation between two different written languages involves the translator changing an original written text (the source text or ST) in the original verbal language (the source language or SL) into a written text (the target text or TT) in a different verbal language (the target language or TL).

In their work "Translation: An advanced Recourse Book, 2004, Basil Hatim and Jeremy Munday cited Jakobson's discussion on translation center around certain key questions of linguistics, including equivalence between items in SL and TL and the notion of translatability. These are

⁵⁸Munday Jeremy, *Introducing Translation Studies, Theories and Applications*, 2nd edition, Routledge, 2004.

issues which became central to research in translation in the 1960s and 1970s. They think that this budding field received the name 'Translation Studies' favor to the Netherlands-based scholar James S. Holmes in his paper "The Name and Nature of Translation Studies", which presented in 1972, but widely published only much later, Holmes mapped out the new field like a science, dividing it into 'pure' Translation Studies (including descriptive studies of existing translations and general and partial translation theories) and 'applied' studies (covering translator training, translator aids and translation criticism, amongst others). More priority is afforded to the 'pure' side, the objectives of which Holmes considers to be bilateral:

- 1- To describe the phenomena of translating and translation(s) as they manifest themselves in the world of our experience, and;*
- 2- To establish general principles by means of which these phenomena can be explained and predicted.*

2.4.2.3: Roman Jakobson: the types of translation are three categories described by the Russo-American structuralist Roman Jakobson in his seminal paper 'On linguistic aspects of translation' (Jakobson 1959/2004, p: 139)⁵⁹, Jakobson's categories are as follows:

- (1) intralingual translation, or 'rewording': 'an interpretation of verbal signs by means of other signs of the same language';
- (2) interlingual translation, or 'translation proper': 'an interpretation of verbal signs by means of some other language';
- (3) intersemiotic translation, or 'transmutation': 'an interpretation of verbal signs by means of signs of non-verbal sign systems'.

⁵⁹ Jakobson, R. On linguistic aspects of translation, in L. Venuti (ed.), PP. 138–43. 2004.

Routledge Translation Studies in its series (Main issues of translation studies) gives a review of Translation studies, and described it as an "academic research area" that has expanded massively in recent years. It was formerly studied as a language-learning methodology or as part of comparative literature, translation "workshops" and contrastive linguistics courses.

2.4.2.4: James S. Holms: The discipline owes much to the work of James S. Holmes (2 May 1924 – 6 November 1986, an American-Dutch poet, translator, and translation scholar) who proposed both a name and a structure for the field. The interrelated branches of theoretical, descriptive and applied translation studies initially structured research. Over time, the interdisciplinarity of the subject has become more evident, and recent developments have seen increased specialization and the continued importation of theories and models from other disciplines.

2.4.2.5: Vinay and Darbelnet: The series mentioned that in the 1950s and 1960s Jean-Paul Vinay and Jean Darbelnet produced their *Stylistique comparée du français et de l'anglais* (1958), a contrastive study of French and English which introduced key terminology for describing translation. It was not translated into English until 1995; Alfred Malblanc (1944/1963) had done the same for translation between French and German; Georges Mounin's *Les problèmes théoriques de la traduction* (1963) examined linguistic issues of translation; Eugene Nida (1964) incorporated elements of Chomsky's then fashionable generative grammar as a theoretical underpinning of his books, which were initially designed to be practical manuals for Bible translators.

2.4.2.6: Other contributions: The surge in translation studies since the 1970s has seen different areas of Holmes's map come to the fore. Contrastive linguistics generally fell by the wayside, but has resurfaced thanks to the advances in corpus-based studies. The linguistics-oriented

‘science’ of translation has continued strongly in Germany, but the concept of equivalence associated with it has been questioned and reconceived.

The late 1970s and the 1980s also witnesses the rise of a descriptive approach that had its origins in comparative literature and Russian Formalism. A pioneering centre was Tel Aviv, where Itamar Even-Zohar and Gideon Toury pursued the idea of the literary polysystem in which, among other things, different literatures and genres, including translated and non-translated works, compete for dominance. The polysystemists worked with a Belgium-based group including José Lambert and the late André Lefevere (who subsequently moved to the University of Austin, Texas), and with the UK-based scholars Susan Bassnett and Theo Hermans. A key volume was the collection of essays edited by Hermans, *The Manipulation of Literature: Studies in Literary Translation*, which gave rise to the name of the ‘Manipulation School’. Bassnett and Lefevere’s volume *Translation, History and Culture* (1990) then introduced the term ‘cultural turn’. This dynamic, culturally oriented approach held sway for much of the following decade.

In the USA, during the 1990s the cultural studies-oriented analysis of Lawrence Venuti called for greater visibility and recognition of the translator. Developments continued at a fast pace in the new millennium, with special interest devoted to translation, globalization and resistance, the sociology and historiography of translation, translator training (e.g. Kearns 2008) and process oriented research. Research activity, as well as the practice of translation, has also been revolutionized by new technologies. These new areas include audiovisual translation, localization and corpus-based translation studies. Furthermore, the international reach of the discipline has expanded with research in or on China (e.g. Chan 2004, Cheung 2006, 2009) and the Arab world.

According to Intan Praditahe, p: 53, the 1980⁶⁰ was a decade of consolidation for the fledging discipline known as Translation Studies. It was the momentum of defining translation as a theory. Translation has been defined variously by different writers who concern in linguistics. It depends on how they view language and translation. This paragraph tries to explain three views of language and translation, which influence the development of translation studies. Since the dissemination of bibles, translation has played a very important role for information exchange; however, the study of translation as academic purposes began in the past fifty years.

Betlem Soler Pardo, 2013⁶¹, thinks from the beginning of the 20th century onwards, to learn a foreign language in some countries consisted in doing it through what was called the grammar-translation method, whose origins can be found in the way Latin and Greek used to be approached. This way of studying a language was later applied to modern languages, which concentrated on learning the grammatical rules of the target language and then carrying out a literal translation.

Betlem, *ibid.*, 2013, goes on saying that translation exercises were considered to be a way of learning a foreign language or of reading a foreign language text. Later, the grammar-translation method lost its popularity with the appearance of the communicative approach in the late 1960s and early 1970s. This method focused on the natural ability of students to learn a new language and attempted to represent the daily routine in classrooms focusing on spoken language instead of using

60 Praditahe, Intan, *An Introduction to Translation Studies, an overview*, Islamic University of Indonesia, 1980.

61 Betlem Soler Pardo, *Translation Studies: An Introduction to the History and Development of (Audiovisual) Translation*, Universidad Alfonso X El sabio, Facultad de Estudios Sociales y Lenguas Aplicadas, 2013.

sentences that were out of context. As a consequence, this new approach entailed the abandoning of the translation method in its classic form.

A new conceptual tool was developed by Van Doorslaer 2007, p: 223⁶², in "Translation Studies Bibliography, set a new map, he differentiated between translation, and translation studies, reflecting the divergent centres of interest of research. 'Translation' looks at the act of translating and, in the new map subdivided Translation into:

- 1- *lingual mode (interlingual, intralingual);*
- 2- *Media (printed, audiovisual, electronic);*
- 3- *mode (covert/overt translation, direct/indirect translation, mother tongue/ other tongue translation, pseudo-translation, retranslation, self-translation, sight translation, etc.);*
- 4- *Field (political, journalistic, technical, literary, religious, scientific, commercial).*

Doorslaer, *ibid.*, 2007, p: 228, subdivided Translation Studies into:

- 1- *approaches (e.g., cultural approach, linguistic approach);*
- 2- *theories (e.g., general translation theory, polysystem theory);*
- 3- *research methods (e.g., descriptive, empirical);*
- 4- *applied translation studies (criticism, didactics, institutional environment).*

2.5: Methods, Strategies and Types of Translation

2.5.1: Overview:

Cristina Cela Gutiérrez, 2018, p: 26⁶³ stated that Newmark distinguishes between two concepts: translation methods, to refer to those strategies applied to the whole text, while those applied to specific elements within the text are called translation procedures. Besides, Newmark states that while translation methods relate to whole texts, translation procedures used for sentences and the smaller units of language.

62 Doorslae, Luc Van. *The Metalanguage of Translation* | Lessius University College, 2007.

63 Gutiérrez, Cristina, Cela. *An analysis of the translation strategies of evidential adverbs in a corpus-based study*, 2018.

2.5.2: Translation Methods:

Newmark, *ibid.* 1988, p:81, mentions the difference between translation methods and translation procedures. He writes that, "While translation methods relate to whole texts, translation procedures are used for sentences and the smaller units of language". He goes on to refer to the following methods of translation:

2.5.2.1: Word-for-word translation

This is often demonstrated as interlinear translation, with the TL immediately below the SL words. The SL word order is preserved and the words translated.

2.5.2.2: Literal translation

The SL grammatical constructions converted to their nearest TL equivalents but the lexical words are again translated singly, out of context. As a pre-translation process, this indicates the problems to be solved. Literal translation or form-based translation attempts to follow the form of the source language.

2.5.2.3: Faithful translation

A faithful translation attempts to reproduce the precise contextual meaning of the original text within the constraints of the TL grammatical structures. It transfers cultural words and preserves the degree of grammatical and lexical 'abnormality' (deviation from SL norms) in the translation. It attempts to be completely faithful to the intentions and the text-realization of the SL writer.

2.5.2.4: Semantic translation

Semantic translation differs from faithful translation only in as far as it must take more account of the aesthetic value, that is, the beautiful and natural sounds of the SL text, compromising on meaning where appropriate so that no assonance, word-play or repetition jars in the finished version.

2.5.2.5: Adaptation

This is the freest form of translation. It is used mainly for plays, comedies and poetry; the themes characters, plots are usually preserved; the SL culture is converted to the TL culture and the text rewritten. The deplorable practice of having a play or poem literally translated and then rewritten by an established **dramatist or poet has produced many poor adaptations.**

2.5.2.6: Free translation

Free translation reproduces the matter without the manner, or the content without the form of the original. Usually, it is a paraphrase much longer than the original, a so-called 'intra-lingual' translation, often prolix and pretentious.

2.5.2.7 Idiomatic translations

Idiomatic translation reproduces the message of the original text but tends to distort nuances of meaning by preferring colloquialisms and idioms where these do not exist in the original.

2.5.2.8: Communicative translation

Communicative translation attempts to render the exact contextual meaning of the original in such a way that both content and language are readily acceptable and comprehensible to the readership.

2.5.3: Translation Strategies:

2.5.3.1: Foreword

Translation strategies are procedures for solving translation problems. They range from the realization of a translation problem to its solution or the realization of its insolubility by a subject at a given moment. When translation is held between a pair of texts of nature languages, there are typically many possible translations. Selecting one of these translations is not an easy task because natural languages translation is particularly noisy. It is difficult for the translator to choose the suitable method for carrying

out his translating task. For the reason that, the existence of synonyms frequently allows for multiple correct translations of the same kind.

Vinay and Darbelnet 1995, p: 30-42)⁶⁴ divide translation strategies in two categories: direct (or literal) translation, which are (borrowing, calque, and literal translation) and oblique (indirect) translation (transposition, modulation, equivalence, and adaptation), which are as following:

2.5.3.2: Direct Translation Procedures

The following section of my study deals with the definition of the translation strategies and their illustration through examples. The direct translation procedures are:

2.5.3.2.1: Borrowing:

A word from the ST is directly transferred to the TT, that is, a word is taken directly from another language and employed with its same form in the TT without translation ((*ibid*, p: 31). This technique used in English and other languages in order to fill a semantic gap in the TT. The following words are some common and frequently used examples of borrowing adopted in Spanish from the English language: light, software, hardware, marketing, merchandising, fitness.

2.5.3.2.2: Calque

This is “a special kind of borrowing”, according to Vinay and Darbelnet, (*ibid*. p: 32- 3), where the SL phrase or expression is literally translated word-for-word. Besides, they add that borrowings and calques often become fully integrated into the TL, although they suffer sometimes some semantic changes, which can turn them into false friends: “libraire” (French) and “librería” (Spanish) vs. “library” (English), which means the place where you read and borrow books and not the place where you buy books as in Spanish or French. Calques contribute to the richness of the

⁶⁴Vinay, J. and Darbelnet, J. Comparative stylistics of French and English. Amsterdam: Benjamins, 1995.

translation in the TL by avoiding the direct use of foreign words. It is noteworthy that some authors use the concept of “loan translation” as a synonym for calque. However, a calque is a construction, where a word or phrase borrowed from another language while translating its components in order to create a new lexeme in the TL, respecting the syntactical structures of the SL, while a loan may be a phonetic and morphological adaptation.

2.5.3.2.3: Literal translation

This occurs when ST translated ‘word-for-word’ into TT (ibid, p: 33,). According to Vinay and Darbelnet, literal translation most commonly used between languages of the same family and culture. Vinay and Darbelnet consider literal translation as a guarantee of good translation and for them another translation method would be regarded, only if the use of word-for-word translation in the TT alters the meaning of the original: “literalness should only be sacrificed because of structural and metalinguistic requirements and only after checking that the meaning is fully preserved” (ibid., p:288,). However, ((ibid., p:34-5) make clear that a literal translation is not acceptable, if it:

- 1- Has a different meaning as the original or has no meaning
- 2- Is not possible because it changes the structure of the ST
- 3- Is not equivalent to the same level of the language.
- 4- Does not have a corresponding expression within the metalinguistic experience of the TL.

2.5.3.3: Oblique (Indirect) Translation Procedures:

2.5.3.3.1: Transposition

It is the first technique towards oblique translation (ibid. p: 95,) Transposition operates at grammatical level and it involves the replacement of a word class of one part of the speech for another without changing the original message. Translators (often without being aware of it) change the word type, for instance verbs for nouns or nouns for prepositions. In

stylistic terms, the transposed phrase loses its original value; however, the meaning is the same. In short, transposition is a translation procedure, where a part or some parts of the original speech change their sequence in the translation process. This method requires the proficiency in both the source and the target language and mastery of the translator to know whether the replacement of the word category is conceivable in the TT without changing the meaning of the original message.

2.5.3.3.2: Modulation

This translation technique consists in the variation of the form of the original message by modifying the point of view without changing the meaning. It basically means a change of perspective: the translator uses a phrase that is different in the source and the target languages in order to transfer the same idea. This strategy involves a shift in both the semantics and the point of view of the source language.

Translation sounds awkward and unfamiliar, while the modulated translation generates a more natural feeling in the reader of the target text and it is easier to understand. Modulation is accepted in those contexts where either a literal or a transposed translation still sounds unsuitable, unidiomatic or awkward in the target language, although the result is grammatically correct ((ibid, p:36).

2.5.3.3.3: Equivalence

This term is used by Vinay and Darbelnet (ibid, p:38-9) to refer to cases where languages describe the same situation by different stylistic or structural means. An utterance of the ST is replaced in the TT with one that fulfills the same pragmatic function, although it differs in form and meaning. (Cruz 2013: 354). This strategy is commonly used for the translation of idioms, proverbs and the onomatopoeia of animal sounds.

2.5.3.3.4: Adaptation

Vinay and Darbelnet ((ibid, p:39-40) introduces this term to refer to the translation strategy that implies changing the cultural reference when the cultural-specific peculiarities of the source text do not exist in the target culture and they must be eliminated or replaced by other cultural- specific peculiarities appropriate in the TT.

2.5.3.3.5: Different translation procedures proposed by Newmark, mentioned by Ordudari M, in (Translation Journal), in a thesis entitled "Translation procedures, strategies and methods"⁶⁵:

- *Transference: it is the process of transferring an SL word to a TL text. It includes transliteration and is the same as what Harvey named "transcription."*
- *Naturalization: it adapts the SL word first to the normal pronunciation, then to the normal morphology of the TL.*
- *Cultural equivalent: it means replacing a cultural word in the SL with a TL one. However, "they are not accurate".*
- *Functional equivalent: it requires the use of a culture-neutral word.*
- *Descriptive equivalent: In this procedure, the meaning of the CBT explained in several words.*
- *Componential analysis: it means "comparing an SL word with a TL word which has a similar meaning but is not an obvious one-to-one equivalent, by demonstrating first their common and then their differing sense components*
- *Through-translation: it is the literal translation of common collocations, names of organizations and components of compounds. It can also be called: calque or loan translation.*

65. Ordudar, Mahmoud Translation procedures, strategies and methods, Volume 11, 3, July 2007.

- *Shifts or transpositions: it involves a change in the grammar from SL to TL, for instance, (i) change from singular to plural, (ii) the change required when a specific SL structure does not exist in the TL, (iii) change of an SL verb to a TL word, change of an SL noun group to a TL noun and so forth.*
- *Modulation: it occurs Modulation: it occurs when the translator reproduces the message of the original text in the TL text in conformity with the current norms of the TL, since the SL and the TL may appear dissimilar in terms of perspective.*
- *Recognized translation: it occurs when the translator "normally uses the official or the generally accepted translation of any institutional term.*
- *Compensation: it occurs when loss of meaning in one part of a sentence compensated in another part.*
- *Paraphrase: In this procedure, the meaning of the CBT explained. Here the explanation is much more detailed than that of descriptive equivalent.*
- *Couplets: it occurs when the translator combines two different procedures.*
- *Notes: notes are additional information in a translation.*

2.5.4: Types of Translation:

Cited from the site (Translate Day)⁶⁶, Translation is a field that is seeing a lot of activity nowadays, thanks to the increasing globalization of businesses. International travel has also increased significantly, for both business and leisure. This means there is, at any given time, a large number of people in a country that don't necessarily speak the local language well. There are many different types of translation that may be required, and each one is unique, with its own process and specific requirements. Here are the most common types of translation, classified according to translation services or the multi-use of translation the varied fields, such as following:

2.5.4.1: Literary Translation

The name is self-explanatory, literary translation refers to the translation of literary works like stories, novels, poems, and plays. It is often considered the highest form of translation because a literary translation is so much more than the mere conveying of the meaning and context of the document in the source language into the target language. It involves incorporating the appropriate cultural nuances, translating humor, feelings, emotions, and other subtle elements of a particular work. Many litterateurs believe that it is extremely difficult, if not impossible, to translate works of literature – especially poetry. Some examples of situations that could be very difficult are – rhyming words, puns, idioms, anagrams, and so on. Often, there are no appropriate translations in the target language, and the nuance is lost. Have you ever tried translating a joke into another language? If you have, you would understand this. Haven't you felt, that it did not seem as funny when translated? Often, many subtle connotations the writer has hinted at are lost in translation. Then there is the matter of the individualistic writing

66. www.translateday.com

style of the author, the translator has a tough job in attempting to convey that uniqueness.

2.5.4.2: Localization

E-learning localization is also often utilized for company trainings. The goal is to provide consistent information to all employees regardless of their physical location and trying to have the content adapted to their understanding.

Last but not least we need to pay special attention to localization services, which quite often coincide or occur simultaneously with the translation services. Localization is a very important part of the overall service provided by LPS (Local Provisioning System), which means (a windows component that resides in the operating system and enforces pay-as-you-go and subscription metering rules) as it guarantees that the content is not simply rendered from one language into another but properly localized taking into account the peculiarities of the local customers and their culture. Localization is often used by companies who want to expand globally and look for the best way to present their website, product or service in the new market.

2.5.4.3: Financial Document Translation

Financial documents like bank records, statements, account statements and more, sometimes need to be translated to make it easier for the target audience to comprehend. Here the actual content that you need to translate may be lesser, but it has to be done precisely; you may also be required to change the currencies – in which case, you would need to also convert the figures.

2.5.4.4: Commercial Translation

This type of translation necessitates a translator to possess specialized skills, like knowledge of the business jargon, and the industry to which the business belongs. The types of texts in the translation of commercial

documents could include business correspondence, reports, tender documents, company accounts, memos, and so on. Sometimes, this could overlap with legal translation if the company handles legal paperwork.

2.5.4.5: Administrative Translation

In the realm of translation, administrative refers to the translation of management texts we often see being used in organizations, whether huge corporations or regional businesses. Though similar to commercial translations, it is not exactly the same. While administrative translation can be called a subset of commercial translation, no commercial translation is necessarily administrative.

2.5.4.6: Legal Translation

This is one of the most complex translations, and involves birth certificate translations and marriage certificate translations, translating contracts, agreements, treaties, memorandums, wills, and so on. A good translator needs to understand the various underlying contexts of the documents and that of the two regions or countries for which the documents are intended – the socio-cultural aspects, and the politico-legal aspects as well. They would then need to translate it in a manner that the target audience easily grasps the text. Even if you are familiar with the cultures and other aspects and are highly skilled at translation, you may need to consult legal professionals to ensure that your translation is completely error-free.

2.5.4.7: Judicial Translation

This type of translation is different from legal translation; the latter is about translating legal documents, which could be very old too. However, when we talk about judicial translation, we refer to the activity of translating court documents like depositions, minutes of meetings, expert testimonies, witness testimonies, judgments, letters rotatory, interviews and more, basically, activities related to cases.

2.5.4.8: Technical Translation

Any technical content that needs to be translated – user guides, manuals, online help text, instruction booklets, training materials and videos, marketing materials for technical fields like manufacturing, science or engineering – all of this comes in the ambit of technical translation. Formatting is an important aspect where the translation of technical content is concerned, as desktop publishing or DTP (adapts graphics and other visual documents for multiple languages) is required for it. Often the screenshots and even graphics have to be edited to make it suitable for the target language/s, using a content management system CMS will help you keep cost down. When choosing a translator, it is essential to check how well versed they are with the terminology and jargon used in your specific industry, if they are not as familiar with that stuff as you'd like but they are proficient in the translation as such, it would make sense to provide training for them to familiarize them with your industry in general, and your business in particular. As a translation service provider, it would be worth investing in an efficient translation management system TMS; it can automate your project tasks and bring down your admin costs. By nature, technical content translation is complicated, and even a tiny error may result in a huge mistake at a later point; therefore, it is a good practice to check how stringent the quality control measures taken by the translation service provider are.

2.5.4.9: Medical Translation

Any medical content that is patient related, like labels, packaging, instructions, or software, and content that is product related, like research papers, clinical trial paperwork, quality management certificates and the like, usually needs translation. It is imperative that the translation service providers are experienced, have the requisite knowledge, and are in-country professionals. Translation of medical documents can also be very tricky as

the requirements of translation can differ from country to country; a translator or company specialized in medical documents would be your best bet, as they would be familiar with the intricacies of all the different requirements. If you want the best translation service provider, who follows a high level of quality control, like a company with an ISO 13485:2016 certification. The general certifications that signify quality, like ISO 9001:2015 and ISO 17100:2015 are, of course, a must-have.

2.5.4.10: Website Translations

We are of course talking about website copy, subtitles for videos on your web pages, and any documents you have there. Here you will also need to change things like currencies, address formats and layouts, to appeal to the different local audiences. You need to think about the languages you want your website to be translated into and localize only those pages, which will apply to the target audience. Using a website translation management system to automate and ease the process if you have frequent updates to your website copy.

2.5.4.11: Script Translation

Many popular movies and TV shows that come out of Hollywood are dubbed into several languages and released worldwide; sometimes the films are from foreign languages and dubbed into English and other European languages. The Harry Potter series was also released into dozens of languages. But for these releases to happen, the scripts have to be translated first. You can say this is a type of literary translation, but it is not exactly the same. It can be very dicey, as translating punchlines, jokes or catchy phrases into another language to make the same impact is very difficult. With more movies being released in multiple languages nowadays, this type of translation is very much in demand today.

2.5.4.12: Multimedia Localization

Videos, graphics, animations, GIFs, infographics, all this can be grouped under multimedia; and this is very important today, as more and more companies are creating multimedia content to widen their audience reach and keep them engaged. Localizing this content can get quite tricky though it may look simple from the outside, as it has to be appropriate for the local culture, and appeal to the customers in that region. If you don't do it correctly, you could end up offending your audience, and drive them away.

2.6: Machine Translation

2.6.1: Overview

In this part the study reviews many concepts and issues related to machine translation MT, mainly the technical aspects such like MT and modern technologies, the online MT, the online MT services, and MT apps, besides MT quality assessment, the research has covered the historical part of MT in section 6.

2.6.2: significant points of MT

Machine translation is an automatic translation system makes use of an advanced computational linguistic analysis to process source documents and automatically create target texts with human aided machine translation (HAMT) or without fully aided machine translation (FAMT) user intervention.

The term 'machine translation' (MT) refers to computerized systems responsible for the production of translations with or without human assistance. It excludes computer-based translation tools which support translators by providing access to on-line dictionaries, remote terminology databanks, transmission and reception of texts, etc. The boundaries between machine-aided human translation (MAHT) and human-aided machine translation (HAMT) are often uncertain and the term computer-

aided translation (CAT) can cover both, but the central core of MT itself is the automation of the full translation process, (W. John Hutchins, 1995)⁶⁷.

2.6.3: Some MT Concepts

According to Martin Kay, 1982, from Xerox Corporation, there are some term related to MT, as follows:

- 1- *Fully Automatic Machine Translation (FAMT) refers to translation wherein the programs run in "batch" mode (off-line) and produce translations without human intervention; afterwards, human revision (post-editing) may be performed with a text editing program or via other means, if desired.*
- 2- *Machine-Assisted Human Translation (MAHT) refers to translation wherein the program is a fancy editing and dictionary concordance tool which the human translator uses to increase his efficiency by automating his access to word definitions and terminology correspondences. All initiative resides with the human, unlike FAMT and HAMT.*
- 3- *Information Acquisition (IA) refers to a situation in which translation is being performed for "current awareness" or "screening" purposes where a quick and- dirty approach may be sufficient, at least to determine if a more careful translation is justified. No human revision (post-editing) is assumed.*
- 4- *Denotative Translation (DT) refers to an information dissemination situation in which the everyday and technical definitions of the words are meant, and where subtle nuances of a word choice are unjustified or even undesirable. This is typical of technical texts.*

⁶⁷ Hutchins, W. John. *MACHINE TRANSLATION: A BRIEF HISTORY*. From: *Concise history of the language sciences: from the Sumerians to the cognitivists*. Edited by E.F.K. Koerner and R. E. Asher. Oxford: Pergamon Press, P: 431-445, 1995.

5- *Connotative Translation (CT) refers to an information dissemination situation in which subtle nuances of word choice are very important, if not critical, in conveying the intended meaning of the text. This is typical of, for example, religious, and literary texts.*

W. John Hutchins, 1995⁶⁸, explained that computer programs are producing translations, not perfect translations, for that is an ideal to which no human translator can aspire; nor translations of literary texts, for the subtleties and nuances of poetry are beyond computational analysis; but translations of technical manuals, scientific documents, commercial prospectuses, administrative memoranda, medical reports.

2.6.4: MT on the Internet

Many MT companies (service providers) have been providing network-based translation services for on-demand translation, sometimes with human revision as optional extra. In some cases, these are client-server arrangements for regular users; such services are provided, for example, by the following companies: Systran, Logos, Globalink, Fujitsu, JICST and NEC. Some companies have now been set up primarily for this purpose: LANT in Belgium is a major example, based on its rights to develop the METAL system and the Eurolang Optimizer workstation. Its specialty is the customization of controlled languages for use with its MT and translation memory systems, W. John Hutchins, 2001⁶⁹.

2.6.5: Machine Translation, a step forward:

With the rise of technology and an increasing demand for quick, cheaper translation, technological advancements have increased the overall usability of machine translation. For that reason, many companies are turning to machine translation and away from traditional translation,

68 W. John Hutchins, *Machine Translation: A brief History*, From: *Concise history of the language sciences*, Oxford: Pergamon Press, 2005.

69 W. John Hutchins, University of East Anglia, Norwich, UK, 2001.

leaving many to question what might become of this industry and the language professionals who have built it.

2.6.5.1: MT system types: According to <https://gengo.com/>, (online translation services) technically, there are three types of MT systems:

2.6.5.1.1: Speech recognition systems

In recent years, speech recognition has made remarkable advances, especially in regard to machine translation. Using speech recognition, software learns from a body of recordings and the transcriptions created by humans. Conversational spoken phrases are instantly translated and repeated back in the target language, such as in the case of Skype Translator.

2.6.5.1.2: Statistical Machine Translation SMT:

It is a machine translation paradigm where translations are generated on the basis of statistical models whose parameters are derived from the analysis of bilingual text corpora. The statistical approach contrasts with the rule-based approaches (*a method of machine translation often characterized by its use of a bilingual corpus with parallel texts as its main knowledge base at run-time. It is essentially a translation by analogy and can be viewed as an implementation of a case-based reasoning approach to machine learning*). to machine translation as well as with example-based machine translation, which means "*a method of machine translation often characterized by its use of a bilingual corpus with parallel texts as its main knowledge base at run-time. It is essentially a translation by analogy and can be viewed as an implementation of a case-based reasoning approach to machine learning*".

The first ideas of statistical machine translation were introduced by Warren Weaver in 1949, statistical machine translation was re-introduced in the late 1980s and early 1990s by researchers at IBM's Thomas J. Watson Research Center and has contributed to the significant resurgence in

interest in machine translation in recent years. Before the introduction of neural machine translation, it was by far the most widely studied machine translation method, (Wikipedia, Free Encyclopedia).

2.6.5.1.3: Neural Machine Translation (NMT)

Neural Machine Translation describes an approach in which a large neural network is trained using machine learning techniques. For example, Google developed its own artificial intelligence programs and applied them to its own multilingual neural machine translation system. It has been argued that these systems can, in some cases, produce output that's "nearly indistinguishable" from humans. However, while the quality of machine translation has improved drastically over the years, humans can still add a lot of value.

2.6.5.1.4: Difference between SMT and NMT:

The key difference between SMT and NMT is that the former requires regular human manipulation and manual re-training of the engines in order to update, while the latter is able to use algorithms to learn linguistic rules on its own based on newly added data. That means that unlike SMT engines, NMT ones do not need to undergo lengthy re-trainings when there are new translations to learn from.

2.6.6: Mobile translation

Translation through mobile apps must also be situated within the wider paradigm of (Mobile Crowdsourcing - *term is attributed to Howe Jeff. (2006), who created this compound term by joining the words "crowd" and "outsourcing", Crowdsourcing represents a practice firmly grounded in the participatory nature of the Web 2.0, and it has been used by businesses, organizations, institutions and collectives to harness the wisdom of the crowd, consisting of a large group of amateurs, experts, volunteers, professionals, fans or citizens, to accomplish any given task.*).

This notion involves leveraging the wide distribution and use of mobile phones in order to Crowdfund small micro tasks, such as translation, transcription, surveys, news reporting, emergency reporting, etc. In this context, language industry experts have introduced the notion of “mobile translation.”

Miguel A. Jimenez⁷⁰, says “According to Armstro), the blog from the translation crowdsourcing app Steps states that “mobile translation” in its current context is often understood to be comprised of three distinct and interrelated phenomena: (1) the localization of apps; (2) the use of MT apps; and (3) the use of apps inspired by crowdsourcing workflows to carry out human translation either through post editing MT or through direct human translation. This paper is focused on the latter, which will be referred to hereinafter as (crowdsourced mobile human translation)

2.6.7: Translation Quality Assessment:

Malcolm Williams in (Translation Quality Assessment, 2004) explained the concept of translation quality assessment TQA in a broader academic and research context and determine what TQA is about. In fact, people with an interest in translation studies are always evaluating, evaluating sources (their usefulness and authenticity), evaluating authors and their translators (their aesthetic, their influences and how this informs their work), evaluating source texts and evaluating target texts. TQA is a type of evaluation, but what is evaluation? Michael Scriven, a leading evaluation researcher, defines it as "evaluation is taken to mean the determination of merit, worth, or significance", this definition itself presents a difficulty: How do we define value or worth, be it moral, aesthetic or utilitarian? by

70 Miguel A, Jimenez. Mobile apps and translation crowdsourcing: The next frontier in the evolution of translation, PhD Rutgers University, The State University of New Jersey USA, Número 14, TraduccióidispositiusmòbilsRevistaTradumàtica: tecnologies de la traducció . desembre. ISSN: 1578-7559. 2016.

extension, evaluation involves asking a question that has challenged thinkers from time immemorial: Is a particular thing good? Just like evaluation in the broad sense, TQA can be quantitative or qualitative: it can be based on mathematical/statistical measurement (as in the case of most academic instruments) or on reader response interviews and questionnaires. TQA can be diagnostic (determining areas for improvement at the outset of a course of study), formative (measuring progress and giving feedback during a course of study) or summative (measuring the results of learning).

2.6.7.1: House's TQA Model:

According to House, J. 2015, p: 21⁷¹, the model of translation quality assessment is based on theories of language use. It was designed to provide an analysis of the linguistic-discoursal as well as the situational-cultural particularities of originals and translated texts, a principled comparison of the two texts and an evaluation of their relative match. The model is an eclectic one and is based on pragmatic theory, Hallidayan systemic-functional linguistics, notions developed in the framework of the Prague school of language and linguistics, register theory, stylistics and discourse analysis.

2.6.8: Top MT Engines:

2.6.8.1: Google Translate

Probably it is the most used and well-known machine translation engine today, Google Translate has come a long way from its beginnings and it keeps improving every day. It covers more languages, and language combinations compared to other machine translation engines.

The tool started as a statistical machine translation system, most commonly known as word-by-word translation. These translations often didn't make much sense and were out of context.

⁷¹ House J. Translation Quality Assessment, Routledge, New York, 2015.

However, Google Translate has undergone major improvements since its early days. It keeps getting smarter and more accurate and, in fact, translations for some widely used language combinations such as English to German, or English to Spanish, are quite reliable nowadays.

Google Operating Systems, reports that Google is no longer using Systran technology, Google now uses their own home brewed version of translation technology to translate between the 25 languages available.

2.6.8.2: Microsoft Translator

Just as Google Translate, Microsoft Translator started as a statistical machine translation engine, but it has evolved to something considerably more advanced.

Nowadays, Microsoft Translator uses neural machine translation. This means that the translations will become even more accurate and closer to the natural language in the future. Microsoft Translator is well-known thanks to being integrated into products such as Bing and Skype.

2.6.8.3: DeepL

While DeepL has only 7 languages available to choose from, it's far more advanced than the products of Google and Microsoft. DeepL uses the artificial intelligence AI technology and it's focused on fast learning and improving its capabilities.

Google Translate and Microsoft Translator often go for a very literal translation that misses some nuances and idioms (or gets the translation of these idioms totally wrong), DeepL often provides a more natural translation that comes close to that of a professional translator. The developers behind DeepL are focusing on a small number of language combinations for the time being, but you can generally expect higher quality translations.

2.7: The Related Previous Studies

Different studies have been carried out by many researchers, in different times, in the field of Machine Translation, here, a review of some related preview studies:

2.7.1: A study entitled (*The Problems of Application of Machine Translation with Reference to Lexical Semantic Outputs in Legal and Medical Terms*), by Shadia Ahmed Sharfi Al Tyeb, January 2012, Omdurman Islamic University, Institute for Family and Social Studies.

The study gives detailed information about translation as part of language studies, and activity, describing the methods adopted, and theories emerged, throughout long time, especially the last century, by many prominent scholars, who achieved great progress in this field.

The study investigates the capability of Machine Translation as modern tool using various programs, applications through computers, smartphones, and websites, to help researchers, and all users, of these tools find what they are looking for, easily.

The study adopted the descriptive method, which enables describe, analyze, and compare data collected. The study referred to the progress made in Arabic Machine Translation systems.

The results of the study shows that there are some problems concerning the lexical semantic outputs in the two texts when using Google Translate in translating from English to Arabic, the study also finds that these problems vary; the problems in the medical text are less than in those found in the legal text.

The recommendations of the study stressed on exerting more efforts in the field of Machine Translation, from, and into Arabic language, indicating that these efforts should be in specific and specialized areas for better results.

2.7.2: Another study entitled (*An Evaluation of Online Machine Translation of Arabic into English News Headlines: Implications on Student's Learning Purposes*) performed by: Kais A. Kadhim, Luwaytha S Habeeb, Ahmad ArifinSapar, (English Department, Faculty of Language and Linguistics, University of Malaya), ZaharahHussin (Department of Educational Foundation and Humanities, Faculty of Education, University of Malaya), and Muhammad Muhammad Ridhuan Tony Lim Abdullah (Management & Humanities Department, University of Malaya), published in the "Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology", April 2013, volume 12 Issue 2). This study aims to test the translation quality of Google and Babylon machine systems/services in translating Arabic news headlines into English. 40 Arabic news headlines were selected from three online sources, namely "Aljazeera," "daralhayat," and "Aawsat," where their English manually-translated versions were available. The selected data was evaluated by conducting criteria of Hutchins and Somers (1992) to find the assessment of each system outputs. Besides that, the selected data was also examined to find the types of translation techniques that are available in both machine outputs. A questionnaire was assigned to experienced professionals to evaluate the outputs to examine and determine which system was better to use in translating the collected data. The evaluation was based on criteria proposed by Hutchins and Somers. The findings indicated that both Google and Babylon had 80% of clarity, and Google scored a higher value of accuracy, i.e. 77.5%, compared to 75% of accuracy for Babylon. However, Babylon scored a higher value for style, i.e. 72.5%, compared to a score of 70% by Google. Nevertheless, the results revealed that online MT is undergoing improvement, and it has the potential to be one of the elements of globalization. As implication, the students could use online MT for learning purposes easily and quickly.

2.7.3: Steven Doherty from the University of New South Wales, Australia, conducted a study entitled (*The Impact of Translation Technologies on the*

Process and Product of Translation), and published in the "International Journal of Communication" Nov. 2014.

The study overviewed the development of translation as a human activity, and its "crucial" role in the intellectual communication, by allowing sharing knowledge and culture between different languages.

Doherty gives a background of online translation, or translation and technology, and MT, referring to the importance of Automated Translation according to the growing numbers of the Internet users throughout the world, which the statistics show that the internet users has doubled many times in few years, he also showed numbers of the income of the "Translation Industry", and language services which get to US\$ 20 billion in 2013.

The study explained the spread of computer assisted translation CAT which depends on translation memory TM (a software program that stores a translator's translated text alongside its original source text).

The study detailed the rapid development of MT according to the great progress in information technologies in the last few years of the 21th century, which produced multiple content, such as websites, computer software, technical documentation, video games, and subtitles.

Despite this progress, most machine-translated content still requires some form of human intervention to edit the MT output to the desired level of quality and/or to verify its quality before publication, dissemination, product release, and legal compliance.

The study noted that one of the most substantial technological developments of the past decade has been the shift from desktop computing DC, to distributed and ubiquitous computing, that has enabled the flourishing of Web 2.0 technologies, also known as the "user-generated web", on which, social media is based.

The study concluded that, the impact of translation technologies on international communication from an "interactionist" perspective, the effects on the translation process, its products, and its place in society are all

remarkably tangible. Besides this, TMs paved the way for state-of-the-art MT systems that use human translations to emulate the results of the translation process and deliver output in speeds and volumes that will never be achieved by human translators alone. Also with informed and effective use of TMs and MT, many of the known issues and shortcomings of these technologies can be overcome, especially in terms of translation quality, to somewhat mitigate the downward trend in pricing for translation services in line with tighter budgets and deadlines.

As translation technologies intersect and sometimes subsume the translation process entirely, an important factor in moving toward, the effective use of these technologies and in preparing for future changes is a critical and informed approach in understanding what such tools can and cannot do and how users should use them to achieve the desired result.

2.7.4: A study entitled (*A Comparative Study of Google Translate Translations: An Error Analysis of English-to-Persian and Persian-to-English Translations*), by Hadis Ghasemi and Mahmood Hashemian, Department of Foreign Languages, Isfahan (Khorasgan) Branch, Islamic Azad University, Isfahan, Iran, Jan. 2016.

The study gives a short history review of machine translation studies and methods in the statistical machine translation, and the study referred to the efforts of Keshavarz M. H. in his work (Contrastive analysis and error analysis) on which the researcher mainly depends in his study.

During the last decades, Google Translate, as a Statistical Machine Translation (SMT), was in the center of attention for supporting 90 languages. Although there are many studies on Google Translate, few researchers have considered Persian-English translation pairs. This study used the descriptive-comparative human analysis of translations by means of Keshavarz's model of error analysis to carry out a comparison study between the raw English-Persian translations and Persian-English translations from Google Translate.

Based on the criteria presented in the model, 100 systematically selected sentences (50 sentences in English and 50 in Persian) from an interpreter app called "Motarjem Hamrah", were translated by Google Translate and then evaluated and brought in different tables.

Results of analyzing and tabulating the frequencies of the errors together with conducting a chi-square test showed no significant differences between the qualities of Google Translate from English to Persian and Persian to English. In addition, lexico-semantic and active/passive voice errors were the most and least frequent errors, respectively. Directions for future research are recognized in the paper for the improvements of the system.

2.7.5: A study entitled (*Machine Translation for Human Translators*), by Michael Denkowski, Language Technologies Institute, School of Computer Science, Carnegie Mellon University Pittsburgh.US, 2015.

While machine translation is sometimes sufficient for conveying information across language barriers, many scenarios still require precise human-quality translation that MT is currently unable to deliver. Governments and international organizations such as the United Nations require accurate translations of content dealing with complex geopolitical issues. Community-driven projects such as Wikipedia rely on volunteer translators to bring accurate information to diverse language communities.

As the amount of data requiring translation has continued to increase, the idea of using machine translation to improve the speed of human translation has gained significant traction. In the frequently employed practice of post-editing, a MT system outputs an initial translation and a human translator edits it for correctness, ideally saving time over translating from scratch. While general improvements in MT quality have led to productivity gains with this technique, the idea of designing translation systems specifically for post-editing has only recently caught on in research and commercial communities.

In this work, we present extensions to key components of statistical machine translation systems aimed directly at reducing the amount of work required

from human translators. We cast MT for post-editing as an online learning task where new training instances are created as humans edit system output and introduce an adaptive MT system that immediately learns from this human feedback. New translation rules are learned from the data and both feature scores and weights are updated after each sentence is post-edited. An extended feature set allows making fine-grained distinctions between background and post-editing data on a per translation basis.

The study describes a simulated post-editing paradigm wherein existing reference translations are used as a stand-in for human editing during system tuning, allowing our adaptive systems to be built and deployed without any seed post-editing data.

The study presents a highly tunable automatic evaluation metric that scores hypothesis-reference pairs according to several statistics that are directly interpretable as measures of post-editing effort. Once an adaptive system is deployed and sufficient post-editing data is collected, our metric can be tuned to fit editing effort for a specific translation task.

This version of the metric can then be plugged back into the translation system for further optimization. To both evaluate the impact of our techniques and collect post-editing data to refine our systems, we present a web-based post-editing interface that connects human translators to our adaptive systems and automatically collects several types of highly accurate data while they work. In a series of simulated and live post-editing experiments, we show that while many of our presented techniques yield significant improvement on their own, the true potential of adaptive MT is realized when all techniques are combined. Translation systems that update both the translation grammar and weight vector after each sentence is post-edited yield super-additive gains over baseline systems across languages and domains, including low resource scenarios.

Optimizing systems toward custom, task-specific metrics further boosts performance. Compared to static baselines, our adaptive MT systems produce

translations that require less mechanical effort to correct and are preferred by human translators. Every software component developed as part of this work is made publicly available under an open-source license.

2.7.6: A study entitled (*Building a Large-Scale Knowledge Base for Machine Translation*), by Kevin Knight and Steve K. Luk, Information Sciences Institute, University of California, 1994.

Knowledge-based machine translation (KBMT) systems have achieved excellent results in constrained domains, but have not yet scaled up to newspaper text. The reason is that knowledge resources (lexicons, grammar rules, world models) must be painstakingly handcrafted from scratch. One of the hypotheses being tested in the PANGLOSS machine translation project is whether these resources can be semi-automatically acquired on a very large scale. This paper focuses on the construction of a large ontology (or knowledge base, or world model) for supporting KBMT. It contains representations for some 70,000 commonly encountered objects, processes, qualities, and relations. The ontology was constructed by merging various online dictionaries, semantic networks, and bilingual resources, through semi-automatic methods. Some of these methods (e.g., conceptual matching of semantic taxonomies) are broadly applicable to problems of importing / exporting knowledge from one KB to another. Other methods (e.g., bilingual matching) allow a knowledge engineer to build up an index to a KB in a second language, such as Spanish or Japanese.

Chapter Three

The Precttical Methodology

Chapter Three

The Practical Methodology

3.1: Introduction:

This chapter describes the methodology of the study, it includes the method adopted and tools used to collect and categorize data, besides the discussion and analyzing of this data.

3.2: Adopted Method:

The research methodology, as indicated in chapter one, is descriptive, analytical, and empirical, it investigates changes and errors occurred in the targeted texts translated by the use of machine translation. This method provides statistical tools that help analytics, and translating the processed collected data.

3.3: Research Tools and Materials:

The following tools and materials used in the study:

The main tools used by the researcher are Google Translate services, first, Google Translate apk for android, (offline), besides Google Translate free online service (the official site).

The materials of the study are (6) Arabic texts, and (6) English are sourced from different fields (political, economic, scientific, art/culture, sports, and legal).

Smartphone and computer, "PC".

The texts from Arabic into English are translated by using the official site of Google Translate; From English into Arabic android apk is used.

3.3.1: Research chosen program:

Google Translate is a multilingual neural machine translation service developed by Google, to translate text, documents and websites from one language into another.

It offers a website interface, a mobile app for Android and iOS, and an application programming interface that helps developers build browser extensions and software applications.

Google launched this service in April 2006 as a statistical machine translation service.

It used United Nations and European Parliament documents and transcripts to gather linguistic data. Rather than translating languages directly, it first translates text to English and then pivots to the target language in most of the language combinations it posits in Wikipedia.

Google Translate apk is compatible to most of android versions, and the app operated by smartphones is easy to use, and users are capable to download more languages in addition to English to provide them offline Google Translate service.

According to Wikipedia,” As of July 2021, Google Translate supports 109 languages at various levels and as of April 2016, claimed over 500 million total users, with more than 100 billion words translated daily”.

Google Translate can also be used in computers: desktop and laptop, as an app, (exe), or from the official site, and both must be used online.

3.3.2: Research selected data:

The study analyzes six tests of news articles from Arabic to English, and other six from English to Arabic, of the different fields mentioned before.

3.3.2.1: Arabic texts:

This part of the study investigates Arabic texts including political, economic, scientific, art/culture, sports, and legal ones. These news articles are short.

Political texts are common in media, its main characteristics are the simplicity of its language and expressions, also contain terms and abbrev. News followers know this type.

The first text provided is political, about Tunisia political status enforced by President Kais Saied's decisions to dismiss Prime Minister Hicham Al-Mashishi and suspend the parliament in response to a wave of popular protests against the country's ruling political class, it consists of (5) sentences, 83 words, including the title.

The second text is an economic, which distinguished by its objectivity, i.e., using figures and diagrams, it is quite similar to the political type. The text titled “Amazon: Huge fine of hundreds of millions of dollars to the e-commerce giant”, about the fine imposed on “Amazon” by European Union National Information Protection Authority in Luxembourg. for using the personal data of its customers, in violation to the laws of the EU. The text consists of 6 sentences, and about 138 words, including the title

The third text is scientific title is “Corona Virus: A deaf woman wins a lawsuit against the British government for the absence of sign language from media briefs”. Scientific texts have specific points, such as accuracy, specifying of information, and depend on investigation. This text is on Katie Rowley, a deaf woman wins a lawsuit against the British government for the absence of sign language from media briefs of COVID-19. The text consists of 5 sentences, and 112 words, including the title.

The fourth topic is about culture and art, “Harry Potter: Rare copy sold for £80,000 at auction” by the author “Joanne Rowling”, her first copy of “Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone" has sold in, exceptional condition" for £80,000 at auction. The text consists of 4 sentences, 80 words including the title.

The fifth text is sports text “Tokyo Olympics: Two Syrian friends separated by war and brought together by sport”, about two Syrian friends “Sanda

Aldas and Mona Duhok”, who trained together since childhood, but separated because of war, and settled in Netherlands, the text consists of 6 sentences, and 47 words, including the title.

The sixth text is a legal text titled “A legal battle between the British government and the BBC over a spy report”, about legal dispute between UK government and BBC over a news report the television network plans to broadcast that is said to have exposed the identity of a government spy, the text consists of 129 words including the title.

The total words of this part are 589 words (6 texts).

3.3.2.2: English Texts:

The first text is a political text is about the nuclear submarine deal between US, UK & Australia, consists of 68 words.

The second text is an economic text about Suzuki Motor Gujarat production reduction in Aug due to chip shortage, and consists of 58 words.

The third text about the meeting of Maasai women in Kenya to discuss practice of Female Genital Mutilation FGM, which consists of 82 words.

The fourth text on Japanese Princess to give up royal title, for 150 million yen to marry commoner, this text consists of 64 word.

Text five is about the performance of the ex-Arsenal forward, Pierre-Emerick Aubameyang scores who joined Barca on a free transfer on February in La Liga after Barca win at Real Sociedad, this text consists of 117 words.

The sixth text is legal, about the Turkish businesswoman Nehebat Isbilenn claim at the High Court in London that her business adviser Selman Turk dishonestly misappropriated" £38m of her assets, it consists of 76 words.

The total words of English texts are 465 words. So, the total words of the Arabic and English texts are 1054 words.

3.3.2.3: Text procedures:

The Arabic texts sample taken from BBC News, and English texts picked out from BBC News and the Indian news website “InShort.com”.

The study focused on the changes occurs on the structure of the sentence.

These texts are itemized into sentences, words, and the frequencies of the words.

The study follows a syntactic qualitative analysis, by adopting typological (the study of the language symbols “words”) equivalence or (alignment) method (the correspondence between particular words in the translated sentence pair). Some words have no counterpart in the TT, and considered as “omitted” words, and some words in TT have no equivalent in ST considered “additional” words, and called in MT “spurious” words.

The analysis discussing the following aspects:

- 1\ Enumerating the ST sentence words, and TT, and their syntactical form (verbs nouns, adverbs, adjectives, prepositions, and articles)
- 2\ Investigating the typological alignment of each sentence of the ST and TT, by identifying the omitted and additional words in the TT.
- 3\ Checking punctuation of the ST and TT.
- 4\ Studying the machine lexical selection.
- 5\ Identifying the word transposition: (MT), (word position).
- 6\ Studying grammatical accuracy of the TT.
- 7\ Checking the correctness of the TT meaning.

Chapter Four

Discussion and Analysis

Chapter Four

Discussion and Analysis

4.1. Arabic into English Sample Texts:

4.1.1: Sample Text (1): (political), from Arabic into English.

a\ Sentence (1):

1\ ST sentence: أزمة تونس: كيف أدى الصراع السياسي في تونس إلى أزمة مصيرية؟

2\ TT sentence: Tunisia Crisis: How did the political conflict in Tunisia lead to a fateful crisis?

Table (1)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	كيف how	تونس Tunisia	أزمة crisis	0	0
	السياسي political	الصراع The conflict	أدى Did lead	0	0
	إلى to	تونس Tunisia	في in	0	0
		مصيرية fateful	أزمة A crisis	0	0
Total	11			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (1):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (11) words, while the TT contains (14) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (6) (أزمة/أزمة/تونس/الصراع/السياسي/تونس).
- **Verbs:** there is (1) verb (أدى).
- **Adjectives:** (1) (مصيرية).
- **Adverbs:** (1) (كيف)
- **Prepositions:** (2) (في/إلى).
- **Additional words** there is no additional words
- **Omitted words** there is no omitted words

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

The machine word selection (in the TT) is **correct**, in the main words (crisis, conflict, lead and fateful).

- The machine has just **one equivalent** of the word (أزمة) which is (**crisis**).
- However, the word (الصراع) has (**10**) **choices**, the machine did not pick the first **equivalent** word, which is (**struggle**), and made the correct selection (**conflict**).
- For the verb (أدى), the machine picked the first equivalent (**lead**) among (4) other verbs, (**lead, result, perform** and **fulfill**).

c\ **Word position:**

- The nouns order of the nominal clause (أزمة تونس) is different in the TT, (**Tunisia Crisis**).
- The verb (أدى) comes in the beginning of the ST sentence, followed by the noun (الصراع), while the equivalent verb (**lead**) comes in the end of the TT sentence, followed by the preposition (**to**).
- There is no change of the position of the nouns (الصراع السياسي) in the two sentences.

d\ **Punctuation:** The TT sentence **contains the same punctuation elements** exist in the ST, which are colon, question mark and comma.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The sentence, grammatically correct, that the machine has modified words such as (**political**) and (**fateful**) to meet the grammar rules by adding the definite article (**the**), and the indefinite article (a) to the adjective (**fateful**).

Summary:

Semantically the meaning seems to be **clear** and demonstrating the original meaning.

Besides, the output is syntactically **accurate**, grammatically, and in the word equivalent.

The additional words represent imperfection of the machine performance, despite this the TT satisfying the meaning.

(b) Sentence (2):

1\ ST sentence: انقسم التونسيون بين مؤيد ومعارض لقرارات الرئيس قيس سعيد إقالة رئيس الوزراء هشام المشيشي وتعليق عمل البرلمان ردا على موجة احتجاجات شعبية مناهضة للطبقة السياسية الحاكمة في البلاد،

2\ TT sentence: Tunisians were divided between supporters and opponents of President Kais Saied's decisions to dismiss Prime Minister Hicham Al-Mashishi and suspend parliament in response to a wave of popular protests against the country's ruling political class,

Table (2)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	بين between	التونسيون Tunisian	انقسم Were divided	of (popular)	عمل (البرلمان)
	معارضون opponents	و and	مؤيدون supporters	0	لـ (الطبقة)
	الرئيس president	قرارات decisions	لـ of	0	في (البلاد)
	رئيس الوزراء Prime Minister	إقالة To dismiss	قيس سعيد Kais Saied	0	0
	تعليق To suspend	و and	هشام المشيشي Hicham AL-Mashishi	0	0
	ردا على Inresponseto	البرلمان parliament	عمل -	0	0
	شعبية popular	احتجاجات protests	موجة A wave	0	0
	الطبقة class	لـ -	مناهضة against	0	0
	في -	الحاكمة ruling	السياسية political	0	0
			البلاد country	0	0
Total	28			1	3

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (2):

a\ **Words equivalent** the ST sentence contains (28) words, while the TT contains (30) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns** The ST contains (16) (إقالة /قيس سعيد /الرئيس /قرارات) (لتونسيون)
- هشام المشيشي /تعليق/عمل/البرلمان/موجة/احتجاجات/الطبقة/السياسية/الحاكمة/البلاد/رئيس الوزراء
- **Verbs:** (1), (انقسم)
- **Adjective:** (4), (مؤيد/معارض/شعبية/مناهضة)
- **Adverb** (1), (رداً على).
- **Preposition:** (4), (بين/ل/ل/في).
- **Conjunctions:** (2), (و/و).
- **Additional words** The TT contains (1), which are: (of),
- **Omitted Words:** The ST omitted words are (3), which are: (عمل/ل/في).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine provided (6) equivalents of the word (انقسم), and picked the second one
- There are (6) equivalents of the word (مؤيدون) and picked the first.
- The word (معارضون) has not the same equivalent, (**opponents**) when the word entered as a single word, the machine provided (11) adjective, such as (opposed/dissenting/reluctant/opposite/unfavorable), so, the word (opponents) comes only in the context.
- The machine did not introduce an equivalent to the word (عمل), and the conjunction (ل) which precedes (الطبقة).
- The phrase (رداً على) has the same equivalent (**in response to**)
- But the adjective (شعبية) the machine picked the first equivalent (**popular**), which is not the accurate equivalent.
- The word (مناهضة) has no similar equivalent, when the machine processed it as a single word, that it gives one equivalent (anti).

- There are (4) additional words in the TT (to/a/of/the), see table (2)

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST sentence starts with a verb (انقسم), while the TT sentence starts with the noun (Tunisians), that Arabic language **usually** starts with a verb, and English language starts with a noun.

d\ **Punctuation:** There is just a comma in the end of the ST and TT sentences.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The **context determines the machine output**, this can be noticed in the equivalent words of (معارضون/مناهضة), this can be justified by the fact that one of the **disadvantages of Neural Machine Translation (NMT) output, is unjustifiable.**

Summary:

Semantically the meaning seems to be **clear** and demonstrating the original meaning.

Besides, the output is syntactically **correct**, grammatically, and in the word equivalent.

The additional and omitted words do not represent **imperfection** of the machine performance, that the output satisfying the meaning.

(c) **Sentence (3):**

1\ ST sentence: واعتبر كثيرون قرارات الرئيس ضرورية "لتصحيح مسار الثورة التونسية"،

2\ TT sentence: Many considered the president's decisions necessary to "correct the course of the Tunisian revolution"

Table (3)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	كثيرون many	اعتبر considered	و -	0	و (اعتبر)
	ضرورية necessary	الرئيس The president's	قرارات decisions	0	0
	مسار The course	تصحیح correct	ل to	0	0
	-	التونسية Tunisian	الثورة Of the revolution	0	0
Total	11			0	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (3):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (11) words, while the TT contains (14) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (6) (قرارات/الرئيس/تصحیح/مسار/الثورة/التونسية).
- **Verbs:** there is (1) verb (اعتبر).
- **Adjectives:** (2) (كثيرون/ضرورية).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverbs.
- **Conjunction:** (1), (و).
- **Prepositions:** (1) (ل).
- **Additional words** there is no additional word.
- **Omitted words:** (1), (و).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- Most of the TT equivalent words selected by the machine are **correct**, except the noun (تصحیح), that the accurate meaning is (**rectify**).
- The conjunction (و) considered by the machine as useless, neglected it.

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST sentence started with the verb (اعتبر), while the TT started with the adjective (**many**)
- The noun (قرارات) is the third word in the ST sentence, but its equivalent (**decisions**) comes in the middle of the TT sentence.

d\ **Punctuation:** both, the ST and TT contain a (**comma**) in the end of the sentence.

e/ **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct,

Summary:

The machine dealt with the text in a proper way, grammatically, and words' meaning is correct.

(d) Sentence (4):

1\ ST sentence: بينما وصفها آخرون "بالانقلاب" على الدستور،

2\ TT sentence: while others described it as a "coup" against the constitution,

Table (4)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	ها	وصف	بينما	0	0
	it	Described	while		
	الانقلاب	ب	آخرون	0	0
	A coup	as	others		
		الدستور	على	0	0
		constitution	against		
Total	8			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (4):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (8) words, while the TT contains (10) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (3) (الانقلاب/ الدستور/ها).
- **Verbs:** (1) verb (وصف).
- **Adjectives:** (1) (آخرون).
- **Adverbs:** (1) which is (بينما)
- **Prepositions:** (2) (على/ب).
- **Additional words** there is no additional words
- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted words.

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine selection is correct, except the preposition (ب), transferred it to an adverb: (as), but this can be justified that (ب) proceeded by (وصفها... ب-). (وصفها)
- The word (آخرون) can be translated as either noun, or adjective.

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST sentence started with the verb (اعتبر), while the TT started with the adjective (**many**)
- The noun (قرارات) is the third word in the ST sentence, but its equivalent (**decisions**) comes in the middle of the TT sentence.

d\ **Punctuation:** both sentences, ST and TT contain comma in the end.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct, because the TT meaning gives the same ST meaning.

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**, that grammar and words' meaning and text structure are correct.

(e) Sentence (5):

1\ ST sentence: وتشهد تونس أكبر أزمة اقتصادية وسياسية منذ ثورة 2011 التي أطاحت بالرئيس السابق زين العابدين بنعلي. فكيف وصلت الأمور إلى هذه المرحلة؟،

2\ TT sentence: Tunisia is experiencing the biggest economic and political crisis since the 2011 revolution that toppled former President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali. How did things get to this point?

Table (5)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	أكبر The biggest	تونس Tunisia	و/ تشهد Is experiencing	0	و(تشهد)
	و and	اقتصادية economic	أزمة crisis	0	ب(الرئيس)
	ثورة 2011 The 2011 revolution	منذ since	سياسية political	0	ف(كيف)
	ت -	أطاح toppled	التي that	0	أطاح (ت)
	السابق former	الرئيس president	ب -	0	وصل (ت)
	كيف how	ف -	زين العابدين بن علي Zine El Abidine Ben Ali	0	0
	الأمر things	ت -	وصل did Get	0	0
	المرحلة point	هذه this	إلى to	0	0
Total				0	5

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (5):

a\ **Words equivalent:** the ST sentence contains (25) words, while the TT contains (24).

- **Nouns/ pronouns:**(11) (تونس/أزمة/ثورة 2011/الرئيس/زين العابدين بن (علي/الأمر/المرحلة/ت/ت/هذه/التي
- **Verbs:** (3), (تشهد/أطاح/ وصل)

- **Adjective:** (4), (أكبر/سياسية/اقتصادية/السابق)
- **Adverb:** (2) adverbs (كيف/منذ).
- **Preposition:** (2), (ب/إلى).
- **Conjunctions:** (2), (و/و/ف).
- **Additional words** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted Words:** The ST omitted words are (5), which are: (و/ب/ف/ت/ت).

b\ Lexical word selection:

- The verb (تشهد) - as a single word - has (6) equivalents, (**witness/testify /attend/ assist/certificate/becalm**), so, the machine does not introduce the verb (experiencing) only in the context.
- There are (7) equivalents of the verb (أطاح) and the machine picked the first (**toppled**). In addition, the adjective (السابق) has one equivalent (**previous**) as a single word, and a different meaning in the context (**former**).
- The machine translated the phrase (فكيف وصلت الأمور إلى هذه المرحلة؟) in a very good way, this can be noticed in two words (الأمور=**things**) and (المرحلة=**point**), which reflects the original meaning.

c\ Word position:

The word order of the ST sentence corresponds the TT.

d\ **Punctuation:** both sentences contain the punctuation elements, which are a full stop after (زين العابدين بن علي), and in the end, besides a question mark another full stop in the end.

e / Grammatical Accuracy:

The TT sentence is grammatically correct.

Summary:

The machine shows a remarkable capacity in dealing with words with “wide range” meaning such as (الأمور). This apply on the noun (المرحلة) which expected to be transformed as (**stage**), but the machine picked the most suitable equivalent meaning (**point**).

4.1.2. Summary of words translation accuracy of the political text:

Table (6)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	11	11	100	0	0
2	28	27	96.5	1	3.5
3	11	10	91.9	1	9.1
4	8	8	100	0	0
5	25	25	100	0	0
Total	83	81	97.6	2	2.4

Source: Researcher

Table (6) and chart (1) show the **accurate** and **inaccurate** words in text (1): there is just (1) inaccurate equivalent In Sentence (2,) the machine picked inaccurate equivalent (popular) of the adjective (شعبية), that the right selection is (**public**), and the sentence accuracy rate is (**96.5%**).

And in sentence (3), to the verb (تصحیح), where the machine made the wrong choice, (**correct**), while the correct meaning is (**rectify**), is this sentence the accuracy represents (**91.9%**).

In other word, in this **text** the machine accuracy rate represents (**97.6%**).

Graph (1)

Source: Researcher

4.1.3: Sample Text (2): (Economic), from Arabic into English.

a\ Sentence (1):

1\ ST sentence: أمازون: غرامة ضخمة بمئات الملايين من الدولارات على عملاق التجارة الإلكترونية

2\ TT sentence: Amazon: Huge fine of hundreds of millions of dollars to the e-commerce giant.

Table (7)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	مالية	غرامة	أمازون	Of	مالية
	-	fine	Amazon	(millions)	
	مئات	ب	ضخمة	0	0
	hundreds	Of	huge		
	الدولارات	من	الملايين	0	0
	Dollars	Of	millions		
	التجارة الإلكترونية	عملاق	على	0	0
	e-commerce	giant	to		
Total	12			1	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (7):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (12) words, while the TT contains (13) words.

Words type:

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (6) (أمازون/غرامة/مئات/الملايين/الدولارات/التجارة).
- **Verbs:** there is no verb.
- **Adjectives:** (3) (مالية/ضخمة/عملاق).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (3) (من/على/ب).

- **Conjunctions:** there is no conjunctions.
- **Additional words** there are (1), (of).
- **Omitted words** there is (1) omitted word in the ST, which are: (مالية).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine dropped the word (مالية) from the TT phrase (غرامة مالية), and substitute with one word (**fine**).
- The term (التجارة الالكترونية) is the equivalent of the short (**e-commerce**), which refers to the electronic commerce.

c\ **Word position:**

- Both the ST and TT started with the noun (أمازون), (Amazon).
- The ST starts with the noun (غرامة), while the TT starts with the adjective (**huge**).

d\ **Punctuation:** The ST and the TT sentences contains a **colon**, after the first word (**Amazon**), and ended with a full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The machine output is correct in the grammar structure.

Summary:

This sentence is short, this made the machine task easy, because the accuracy of neural machine translation NMT depends on the length of the sentence. So meaning is quite clear and the structure is correct.

(b) Sentence (2):

1\ ST sentence: منيت شركة أمازون بغرامة قدرها 886.6 مليون دولار بسبب استخدامها البيانات الشخصية لزبائنها بشكل فيه انتهاك لقوانين الاتحاد الأوروبي.

2\ TT sentence: Amazon has been fined \$886.6 million for using the personal data of its customers in violation of European Union laws.

Table (8)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	أمازون Amazon	شركة -	مني/ت -	0	مني/ت
	886.6 مليون دولار \$886.6 million	قدرها -	ب/غرامة Has been fined	0	شركة
	البيانات data	استخدام/ها using	بسبب for	0	بـ (غرامة)
	بشكل -	ل/زبائن/ها of its customers	الشخصية personal	0	قدرها
	انتهاك violation	هـ -	في in	0	استخدام (ها)
	الاتحاد الأوروبي European Union	قوانين laws	ل Of	0	بشكل في/هـ
Total	23			0	8

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (8):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (23) words, while the TT contains (19).

Words type:

- **Nouns and pronouns:** The ST contain (15) (شركة/ أمازون /غرامة /قدرها /قوانين /الاتحاد الأوروبي /ت/هـ/هـ/ /886.6 مليون دولار / استخدام / البيانات / زبائن / انتهاك / قوانين /الاتحاد الأوروبي /ت/هـ/هـ/ (هـ)
- **Verbs:** (2), (مني/فرض)
- **Adjective:** (1), (الشخصية)
- **Adverbs:** (1), (بشكل)
- **Preposition:** (4), (بـ/ل/في/ل).
- **Conjunctions:** There is **no conjunction** in the sentence.
- **Additional words:** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted Words:** The ST omitted words are (9), which are: (مني/ت/شركة/ب/قدرها/ها/بشكل/في/هـ).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The verb (مني) has no equivalent in the TT, but it may refer to (**inflicted**) or (**suffered**). So, the equivalent of the phrase (منيت بغرامة), (**has been fined**).
- Also, the machine selection in the rest of the sentence is correct.

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST started with passive voice (**a verb + pronoun**) (منيت), while the TT started with a noun (**Amazon**) followed by passive verb (has been fined).
- The word (قوانين) preceded the compound noun (**European Union**) in ST, but came in the end of the TT.

d\ **Punctuation:** Both sentences - ST and TT - ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

This sentence indicates what the researcher referred to before, that NMT output quality is best if compared with other MT software technology; this gives correct and very cohesive grammatical structure.

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is clear. The two sentences meaning is symmetrical, although their structure is different.

(c) Sentence (3):

1\ ST sentence: وفرضت الهيئة الوطنية لحماية المعلومات في لوكسمبورغ الغرامة على شركة أمازون بقرار اتخذته في 16 يوليو/تموز، حسب بيان صدر عن الشركة.

2\ TT sentence: The National Information Protection Authority in Luxembourg imposed the fine on Amazon in a decision taken on July 16, according to a statement issued by the company.

Table (9)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	الهيئة الوطنية لحماية المعلومات The National Information Protection Authority	فرض/ت imposed	و -	0	و
	الغرامة the fine	لوكسمبورغ Luxembourg	في in	0	فرض(ت)
	أمازون Amazon	شركة -	على on	0	لـ (حماية)
	في on	اتخذ/ت/ه taken	ب/قرار In/ a /decision	0	اتخذ (ت/ه)
	بيان a statement	حسب according to	16 يوليو/تموز July 16	0	شركة
	الشركة the company	عن by	صدر issued	0	0
	Total	22			0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (9):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (22) words, while the TT contains (22) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (12) (لوكسمبورغ / الغرامة / شركة / أمازون / قرار /) (. الهيئة الوطنية لحماية المعلومات/ت/ت/ه/يوليو/بيان/الشركة
- **Verbs:** there is (3) verb (فرض/اتخذ/صدر).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverbs.
- **Prepositions:** (6) (ل/في/على/ب/في/حسب/عن).
- **Conjunctions:** (1) (و).
- **Additional words** there are no additional words.
- **Omitted words:** (6) word, (و/ت/ل/ت/ه/شركة).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

All of the TT equivalent words selected by the machine are **correct**.

The conjunction (و) considered by the machine as useless, and neglected it.

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST sentence started with the verb (وفرضت), while the TT started with the adjective (**The National Information Protection Authority in Luxembourg**), while the verb (**imposed**) places in the middle of the TT sentence.

d\ **Punctuation:** both, the ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The output syntactically **accurate**, in the grammar, and the word equivalent.

The TT sentence is grammatically correct,

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear, that the meaning of ST embodied** in TT.

(d) Sentence (4):

1\ ST sentence: وسوف تطعن أمازون على القرار، وفقا لمتحدث باسم الشركة، التي اعتبرت أن العقوبة المفروضة بحقها "ظالمة".

2\ TT sentence: Amazon will appeal the decision, according to a spokesperson for the company, which considered the punishment imposed on it "unfair".

Table (10)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	تطعن	سوف	و	0	و
	appeal	will	-		
	القرار	على	أمازون	0	على
	the decision	-	Amazon		
	باسم	متحدث	وقال	0	أن
	for	a/ spokesman	According to		
	اعتبرت	التي	الشركة	0	اعتبرت
	considered	which	the company		
	المفروضة	العقوبة	أن	0	حق
	imposed	the punishment	-		
		ظالمة	ب/حق/ها	0	0
		unfair	on it		
Total	20			0	5

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (10):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (20) words, while the TT contains (19) words.

Words type:

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (8) (أمازون/القرار/متحدث/الشركة/العقوبة/ت/حق/ها)
- **Verbs:** (3) verb (سوف/تطعن/اعتبر).

- **Adjectives:** (2) (المفروضة/ظالمة).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (5) (على/وفقاً لـ/باسم/ب).
- **Conjunctions:** (2) (و/أن).
- **Additional words** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words:** the omitted words (5) which are (و/على/أن/حق/ت).

b\ Lexical word selection:

- The verb (تطعن) as a single word has (12) equivalent their meanings centered on (**cut** or **stab**), but the machine selected the correct meaning when used in the context of the sentence.
- The adjective (ظالمة) has (8) meanings (**unjust/unfair/oppressive/wrongful/iniquitous/unequal/unequitable/tyronous**)
 - The rest of the TT is also correct.

c\ Word position:

- The ST sentence started with the verb (وسوف), while the TT started with the noun (**Amazon**)

d\ Punctuation: both sentences, ST and TT contain **full stop**.

e / Grammatical Accuracy:

The TT sentence is grammatically correct.

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**. The output is **accurate**, in the grammar, and the word equivalent.

(e) Sentence (5):

1\ ST sentence: وتتطلب قوانين حماية البيانات في الاتحاد الأوروبي من الشركات أن تحصل على موافقة المستهلكين قبل استخدام بياناتهم الشخصية، وإلا أصبحت تحت طائلة غرامات كبيرة.

2\ TT sentence: European Union data protection laws require companies to obtain consumer consent before using their personal data, or else face heavy fines.

Table (11)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	قوانين laws	تتطلب requires	و -	0	و(تتطلب)
	في -	البيانات data	حماية protection	0	في (الاتحاد...)
	الشركات companies	من -	الاتحاد الأوروبي European Union	0	من (الشركات)
	موافقة consent	تحصل على obtain	أن to	0	أصبح/ت
	استخدام using	قبل before	المستهلكين consumer	0	تحت
	وإلا or else	الشخصية personal	بيانات/هم Their ...data	0	0
	كبيرة heavy	غرامات fines	أصبحت تحت طائلة face	0	0
Total	26			0	6

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (11):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (26) words, while the TT contains (20).

- **Nouns/pronouns** The ST contains (13) (قوانين/حماية/البيانات/الاتحاد (الأوروبي/الشركات /موافقة/المستهلكين/استخدام/بيانات/هم/طائفة/غرامات/ت
- **Verbs:** (3), (تتطلب/تحصل/أصبح)
- **Adjective:** (2), (كبيرة/الشخصية)
- **Adverb:** (1), (وإلا).
- **Preposition:** (5), (في/من/على/قبل/تحت).
- **Conjunctions:** (2), (و/أن).
- **Additional words:** There is no additional words.
- **Omitted Words:** The ST omitted words are (6), which are (و/في/من/أصبح/ت/تحت).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The equivalent of the word (**obtain**) is a phrase, not a single word, (يحصل على), this shows what I referred to before about the NMT.
- The same is about the word (**face**) the machine translated it as (أصبحت (تحت طائفة), single word transferred into a phrase.
- The equivalent of the noun (موافقة = **consent**) is not accurate, the suitable word is (**approval**)

c\ **Word position:**

The word order of the ST sentence corresponds the TT.

d\ **Punctuation:** The two sentences have the same punctuation, there is a coma after (الشخصية), (the personal), and full stop in the end.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is correct.

Summary:

The machine shows a remarkable capacity in dealing with words, with “wide range” meaning, such as (الأمور). This apply on the noun (المرحلة) which expected to be transformed as (stage), but the machine picked the most suitable equivalent meaning (point).

(f) Sentence (6):

1\ ST sentence: وقد زادت الرقابة على عمالقة التجارة في العالم عقب سلسلة من الفضائح المتعلقة بالخصوصية وسوء استخدام بيانات المستهلكين، إضافة إلى شكاوى من بعض الشركات متهمة شركات كبرى باستخدام قوتها في السوق.

2\ TT sentence: Oversight of the world's trading giants has increased following a series of privacy scandals and misuse of consumer data, in addition to complaints from some companies accusing major companies of using their market power.

Table (12)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	زادت/	قد	و	0	و(قد)
	Has increased	-	-		
	عمالقة	على	الرقابة	0	قد (زادت)
	giants	of	oversight		
	العالم	في	التجارة	0	زادت/
	The world	-	trading		
	من	سلسلة	عقب	0	في (العالم)
	of	A series	following		
	ب/الخصوصية	المتعلقة	الفضائح	0	المتعلقة
	privacy	-	scandals		
	بيانات	سوء استخدام	و	0	ب(الخصوصية)
	data	misuse	and		
	شكاوى	إضافة إلى	المستهلكين	0	في (السوق)
	complaints	In addition to	Of consumers		
	الشركات	بعض	من	0	0
	companies	some	from		
	كبرى	شركات	متهمة	0	0
	major	companies	accusing		
	في	قوت/ها	ب/استخدام	0	0
	-	Their power	Of using		
			السوق	0	0
			market		
Total				0	7

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (12):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (35) words, while the TT contains (33) words, classified below:

- **Nouns and pronouns:** The ST contain (19) (الرقابة /التجارة / العالم /سلسلة /الفضائح)
/الخصوصية /استخدام /بيانات /المستهلكين /شكاوى/بعض/الشركات /متهمه /شركات /اسوء
(استخدام/قوت/ها/السوق/ت)
- **Verbs:** (1), (زاد)
- **Adjective:** (3), (عمالة/كبرى/المتعلقة).
- **Adverb:** (2) (قد/إضافة إلى).
- **Preposition:** (8), (على/في/عقب/من/ب/من/ب/في).
- **Conjunctions:** (2), (و/و).
- **Additional words:** there are no additional words.
- **Omitted Words:** The ST omitted words are (7), which are: (و/قد/ت/في /المتعلقة /ب /في).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The TT sentence started with two additional words, (وقد) dropped by the machine in the TT.
- The additional words show that when the machine deals with context drops some words, because the Neural MT performance sometimes unjustified linguistically.

c\ **Word position:**

The verb (زاد) comes in the beginning of the ST sentence, while it comes as the 7th, in the TT sentence, following the grammatical rule in the two languages (verbs usually come in the beginning of the sentence in Arabic, but in English sentence starts with noun).

d\ **Punctuation** Both ST and TT sentences follow the same punctuation; there is a full stop in the end.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence seems to be correct.

Summary:

By reviewing the machine output, the meaning is clear, and the structure is coherent and correct, but it is imperfect.

4.1.4: Summary of words translation accuracy of the economic text:

Table (13)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	12	12	100	0	0
2	23	23	100	0	0
3	22	22	100	0	0
4	20	19	95	1	5
5	26	25	96.2	1	3.8
6	35	35	100	-	
Total	138	136	98.6	2	1.4

Source: Researcher

Table (13) and chart (2) show the accurate and inaccurate words in text (2), there are (2) wrong selection, in sentence (4), to the preposition (**for**), the phrase (the spokesperson **for** the company), the correct preposition is (**of**), the sentence rate accuracy **95%**.

In sentence (5), the noun (**consent**) is not accurate equivalent to (موافقة), according to the context of the phrase (**require companies to obtain consumer consent**), the accurate meaning is (**approval**), the sentence rate accuracy is **96.2%**.

The machine accuracy rate represents in this **text** is (**98.6%**).

Graph (2)

Source: Researcher

4.1.5: Sample Text (3): (Scientific), from Arabic into English.

a\ Sentence (1):

1\ ST sentence: فيروس كورونا: ما سر إصابة أعداد كبيرة بكوفيد للمرة الثانية؟

2\ TT sentence: Corona Virus: What is the secret of infection of large numbers of “Covid” for the second time?

Table (14)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	سر	ما هو	فيروس كورونا	the	0
	The secret	What is	Corona Virus		
	بكوفيد	أعداد كبيرة	إصابة	0	0
	Of Covid	Of large numbers	Of infection		
			للمرة الثانية	0	0
			For the second time		
Total	10			1	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (14):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (10) words, while the TT contains (14) words, classified below:

- **Nouns pronouns:** (6) (فيروس كورونا/سر/إصابة/أعداد/كوفيد/المرة الثانية).
- **Verbs:** there is no verb.
- **Adjectives:** (1), (كبيرة).
- **Adverbs:** (1), (ما هو).
- **Prepositions:** (2) (ل/ب).
- **Additional words** (1), (the).
- **Omitted words:** There is no omitted words.

b\ Lexical word selection:

- The noun (فيروس كورونا) translated correctly into (**Corona Virus**).
- In addition, the name/term (كوفيد) translated into (**Covid**).

c\ Word position:

- Both sentences, ST and TT started with noun (كورونا فيروس), (**Corona Virus**).
- There is no significant change in the word's place in this sentence.

d\ Punctuation: After the first noun, in both sentences there is colon, and question mark in the end.

e / Grammatical Accuracy:

Regardless to the additional words, the structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear, that the machine gave a correct grammatical structure and the correct words' meaning.

b\ Sentence (2):

1\ ST sentence: في الأيام الأولى لانتشار وباء كورونا، كانت إصابة شخص واحد بكوفيد مرتين خبراً نادراً للغاية.

2\ TT sentence: In the early days of the coronavirus epidemic, one person being infected with Covid twice was very rare news.

Table (15)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	الأولى The early	الأيام days	في in	0	ل/انتشار
	كورونا coronavirus	وباء epidemic	لانتشار -	0	0
	شخص واحد One person	إصابة Being infected	كانت was	0	0
	خبراً news	مرتين twice	بكوفيد With Covid	0	0
	-	للعناية very	نادراً rare	0	0
Total	18			0	2

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (15):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (18) words, while the TT contains (17) words, classified below:

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (10) (الأولى/انتشار /وباء/كورونا إصابة /شخص /كوفيد/) (الأيام /ت/ خبراً).
- **Verbs:** (1), (كان).
- **Adjectives:** (3) (واحد/مرتين/نادراً).
- **Adverbs:** (1), (للمغاية).
- **Conjunctions:** there is no conjunction.
- **Prepositions:** (3) (في/ل/ب).
- **Additional words** there are no additional words.
 - **Omitted words:** (2), (ت/انتشار).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine has (2) meanings of the noun (الأولى), (**first/early**), and picked the second equivalent.
- The machine translated (وباء كورونا) into (**coronavirus epidemic**), which is incorrect, first; (**Corona**) must start with capital (**C**), and no need to the noun (**virus**).
- The machine translated the adverb (للمغاية), to (**very**).

c\ **Word position:**

- The verb + noun (كانت) placed in the middle of the ST sentence, but in the TT in the end (**was**).
- The place of the noun (خبراً) inside the ST sentence is the (16th), but placed in the end of the TT.

d\ **Punctuation:** Both ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT structure is correct, that there is no mistake can be noticed.

Summary:

The machine output is correct, i.e., the words' meaning, the grammatical structure

c\ Sentence (3):

1\ ST sentence: لكن اليوم لم تعد هذه الحال قائمة، وخصوصاً بعد ظهور متحور أوميكرون في نوفمبر/ تشرين الثاني 2021.

2\ TT sentence: Today, however, this is no longer the case, especially after the appearance of the Omicron mutant in November 2021.

Table (16)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	لم تعد قائمة Is no longer	اليوم today	لكن however	0	و
	وخصوصاً especially	الحال the case	هذه This	0	0
	متحور mutant	ظهور The appearance	بعد after	0	0
	نوفمبر/تشرين الثاني 2021 November 2021	في in	أوميكرون Omicron	0	0
Total	15			0	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (16):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (15) words, while the TT contains (16) words, classified below:

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (6) (هذه/الحال/ظهور/متحور/أوميكرون/نوفمبر تشرين (لثاني 2021).
- **Verbs:** there is no verb.
- **Conjunctions:** (2), (لكن/و).
- **Adjectives:** (2) (تعد/قائمة).
- **Adverbs:** (3) (اليوم/لم/خصوصاً).
- **Prepositions:** (2) (بعد/في).
- **Additional words:** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words:** (1), (و).

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine has (3) meanings of the conjunction (لكن), which are (but/however/only), and picked the second.
- The equivalent of the phrase (لم تعد قائمة) is (is no longer).
- The noun (متحور) has only one equivalent (mutant).

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST starts with the conjunction (لكن), while the TT starts with the adverb (today).
- The rest of the words are in the same order in both ST and TT.

b\ **Punctuation:** Both ST and TT contain comma, and full stop in the end.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

d\ **Sentence (4):**

1\ ST sentence: لماذا يتزايد أعداد الأشخاص الذين يصابون بكوفيد للمرة الثانية؟

2\ TT sentence: Why is the number of people infected with Covid increasing for the second time?

Table (17)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	أعداد The number	يتزايد increasing	لماذا why	0	الذين
	يصابون infected	الذين -	الأشخاص Of people	0	0
	-	للمرة الثانية For the second time	بكوفيد With Covid	0	0
Total				0	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (17):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (11) words, while the TT contains (12) classified below:

- **Words type:**
- **Nouns and pronoun:** (6) (أعداد/الأشخاص / الذين/ون/ كوفيد/المرّة الثانية) (6).
- **Verbs:** (2) verb (يتزايد/يصاب).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** (1), (لماذا).
- **Prepositions:** (2) (ب/ل).
- **Conjunctions:** there is no conjunction.
- **Additional words:** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words:** (1), (الذين).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- All of the machine word selection in this sentence is correct.

c\ **Word position:**

- The word place in the TT is incorrect, the machine output is (**Why is the number of people infected with Covid increasing for the second time?**), and the phrase (**for the second time**) must follow the verb (**infected**), so, this make both the meaning and structure of the sentence is clear and accurate.
- Both sentences are interrogative, starts with the adverb (لماذا), (why).

d\ **Punctuation:** The ST and TT sentences ended with question mark and full stop..

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT structure is partially incorrect.

Summary:

The meaning is not very clear, but understandable.

e\ Sentence (5):

1\ ST sentence: يعود جزء من السبب في ذلك إلى أوميكرون نفسه، فهو متحور يجيد خداع الدفاعات التي دشنتها إصابات سابقة بالفيروس، فيما يعود جزء من السبب إلى الصدفة.

2\ TT sentence: Part of the reason for this is Omicron itself, a mutant that is good at cheating defenses launched by previous HIV infections, and part of the reason is due to chance.

Table (18)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	من	جزء	يعود	0	يعود
	of	part	-		
	إلى	في ذلك	السبب	0	التي
	is	for this	The reason		
	فهو	نفسه	أوميكرون	0	0
	that	itself	Omicron		
	خداع	يجيد	متحور	0	0
	cheating	Is good at	A mutant		
	دشنتها	التي	الدفاعات	0	0
	Launched by	-	defenses		
	بالفيروس	سابقة	إصابات	0	0
	HIV	previous	infections		
	جزء	يعود إلى	فيما	0	0
	part	Due to	and		
		للصدفة	من السبب	0	0
		To chance	Of the reason		
Total	30			0	2

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (18):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (30) words, while the TT contains (31) words, classified below:

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (16):

السبب / أو ميكرون / هو /ها/ نفسه /متحور /خداع/ الدفاعات /التي /إصابات / /الفيروس /جزء /السبب الصدفة /جزء)

- **Verbs:** (4) verb (يعود/يجيد/دشن/يعود).

- **Adjectives:** (1) (سابق).

- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.

- **Prepositions:** (7) (من/في/إلى/ب/إلى/من/ل).

- **Conjunctions:** (2), (ف/فيما).

- **Additional words** there is no additional word.

- **Omitted words:** (2), (يعود/التي).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The verb (يعود) has no equivalent in the TT, because the ST structure is poor, it can be (جزء من السبب في ذلك هو أو ميكرون نفسه), the verb is a **spurious**.

- The verb (دشن) has (3) meanings (**inaugurated/launched/instituted**), the machine picked the second.

- The noun (الصدفة) has (6) equivalents, (**coincident/chance/accident/haphazard/happening/contingency**), the machine picked the second, but it is inaccurate, it can be (**coincident**).

- The noun (الفيروس) has been misinterpreted by the machine, which gave the equivalent (**HIV**), the virus causing (**AIDS**).

c\ **Word position:**

- Irrespective the **additional** word (يعود), both sentences have the same beginning.

- The rest of the words of both sentences are in the same order.

d\ **Punctuation:**

- The ST and TT contain comma after the noun (الفيروس), (**HIV**), and full stop in the end.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

f) Sentence (6):

1\ ST sentence: وعليه، فقد أصيب كثير منا في وقت ما، والآن، ثمة موجة مرتفعة من الإصابات، هي في معظمها إصابات ثانية لنفس الأشخاص.

2\ TT sentence: So, many of us have been injured at some point, and now, there is a high wave of injuries, mostly second injuries of the same people.

Table (19)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	أصيب Have been injured	فقد -	وعليه so	0	فقد
	في وقت ما At some point	منا Of us	كثير many	0	هي
	موجة wave	ثمة There is	والآن And now	0	0
	هي -	من الإصابات Of injuries	مرتفعة high	0	0
	ثانية second	إصابات injuries	في معظمها mostly	0	0
	-	-	لنفس الأشخاص Of the same people	0	0
Total	28			0	2

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (19):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (28) words, while the TT contains (22) words, classified below:

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (12): (وقت/ موجة/ ة / الإصابات /هي/معظم /ها /إصابات)
(//ثانية/ نفس الأشخاص)
- **Verbs:** (1) verb (أصيب).

- **Adjectives:** (3) (كثير/ما/مرتفع).
- **Adverbs:** (4) (و عليه/قد/الآن/ثمّة).
- **Prepositions:** (5) (من/في/من/في/ل).
- **Conjunctions:** (3), (و/ف/و).
- **Additional words** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words:** (4), (فقد/هي).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine has no direct equivalent of the adverb (عليه), it has the same meaning of (هكذا), or (so).
- The machine misinterpreted the verb (أصيب), by: (injured), while the correct equivalent meaning is (**infected**). The same is said about the noun (إصابات), which means (**infections**).
- The machine translated the noun (معظمها), into adverb (**mostly**), but correct.
- The machine translated the noun (وقت) into (**point**).

c\ **Word position:**

- Both sentences start with adverb (عليه), (so).
- The adjective (كثير) is the fourth word of the ST, but the second (**many**) in the TT.

d\ **Punctuation:**

- There is comma in the beginning of the ST and TT sentences (وعليه,) and (so,). Besides another comma after (وقت ما), and (some point,), a third comma after (الإصابات), (**injuries**). Both sentences ended with **full stop**.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

4.1.6: Summary of Words Translation Accuracy of the Scientific Text:

Table (20)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	10	10	100	0	0
2	18	17	94.5	1	5.5
3	15	15	100	0	0
4	11	7	63.7	4	36.3
5	30	28	93.4	2	6.6
6	28	26	92.9	2	7.1
Total	112	103	92	9	8

Source: Researcher

Table (20) shows the accurate and inaccurate words in text (3), in sentence (2), the machine translated (وباء كورونا) into (**coronavirus epidemic**) as one word, and the **initial** of (**corona**) is small not capital, so, the accuracy rate is (**94.5%**).

The machine translated sentence (4) into (**Why is the number of people infected with Covid increasing for the second time?**), the phrase (**for the second time**) must be after the verb (**infected**), and the accuracy rate is (**63.7%**)

In sentence (5) there are two mistakes, the equivalent of (الصدفة) is (coincidence) not (**chance**). Besides the equivalent of the noun (الفيروس) is the (**virus**), not (**HIV**), so, the sentence accuracy rate is (**93.4%**).

In sentence (6), the machine translated (أصيب) into (**injured**), the correct is (**infected**), also the noun (إصابات) transferred to (**injuries**), it must be (**infections**), the accuracy rate is (**92.9%**).

The machine selection accuracy rate represents in this text is (**92%**).

Graph (3)

Source: Researcher

4.1.7: Sample Text (4): (Culture and Art), from Arabic into English.

a) Sentence (1):

1\ ST sentence: هاري بوتر: بيع نسخة نادرة مقابل 80-ألف جنيه إسترليني في مزاد

2\ TT sentence: Harry Potter: Rare copy sold for £80,000 at auction

Table (21)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	نسخة	بيع	هاري بوتر	0	0
	copy	sold	Harry Potter		
	80 ألف جنيه إسترليني £80,000	مقابل for	نادرة rare	0	0
	-	مزاد auction	في at	0	0
Total	8			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (21):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (10) words, while the TT contains (8) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (6) (هاري بوتر/بيع/نسخة/80 ألف جنيه استرليني/مزاد).
- **Verbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Adjectives:** (1) (نادرة).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (2) (مقابل/في).
- **Additional words** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words** there is no additional words.

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The noun (بيع) must be translated to the equivalent (**selling** or **sale**), but the machine picked (**sold**) and considering it as **past participle or passive voice**, which is the **right selection**.
- The word (مقابل) has no suitable equivalent as a single word, except when followed by a noun, but the machine give the correct meaning of (مقابل), which is (**for**) in the context.
- The rest of the sentence is selected correctly.

c\ **Word position:**

- The phrase (نسخة نادرة) translated to (**rare copy**), that the adjective (**rare**) preceded the noun (**copy**) as the TT grammar rules.
- The machine dealt with the noun (بيع) as **past part. (sold)**, so moved it to the middle of the sentence.

d\ **Punctuation:** Both, ST and TT sentences contain colon after the first noun and full stop in the end.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The machine modified the “core” of the ST sentence (بيع) to fit TT context. This gives an accurate structure.

Summary:

The meaning is very clear and simple.

b\ Sentence (2):

1\ ST sentence: بيعت النسخة الأولى من كتاب "هاري بوتر وحجر الفيلسوف" للكاتبة جي كي رولينغ في "حالة استثنائية" مقابل 80 ألف جنيه إسترليني في مزاد.

2\ TT sentence: A first copy of J.K. Rowling's "Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone" has sold in "exceptional condition" for £80,000 at auction.

Table (22)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	النسخة copy	ت -	بيع Has sold	0	بيع(ت)
	كتاب 's	من of	الأولى A first	0	كتاب
	الكاتبة -	ل -	هاري بوتر وحجر الفيلسوف Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone	0	ل(الكاتبة)
	حالة condition	في in	جي كي رولينغ J.K. Rowling	0	0
	80 ألف جنيه إسترليني £80,000	مقابل for	استثنائية exceptional	0	0
	-	مزاد auction	في at	0	0
Total	17			0	4

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (22):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (17) words, while the TT contains (16) words.

- **Nouns:** (9) (كتاب/ هاري بوتر وحجر الفيلسوف /الكاتبة/جي كي رولينغ/حالة/80 ألف جنيه) (النسخة/إسترليني/مزاد).

- **Verbs:** (1) verb (بيع).
- **Adjectives:** t(1) (الأولى / استثنائية).
- **Adverbs:** there is adjective.
- **Prepositions:** (5) (من/ل/في/مقابل/في).
- **Additional words** there are no additional words.
- **Omitted words** the ST contain (4) words: (ت/ل/كتاب/الكاتبة).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

The machine selection is correct; this can be noticed as following:

- The verb (بيع) translated correctly (sold).
- The machine omitted (3) words (the pronoun ت, the preposition ل, and the nouns (كتاب والكاتبة)).
- The machine selection in rest of the sentence is correct.
- The noun (حالة) translated to (**condition**), which is not the accurate selection, that (**case** or **event**) can be more suitable.
- The machine picked the wrong equivalent article (a), (**a first**), while the correct is (**the**).
- Also (**has sold**) is incorrect, it must be (**has been sold**).

c\ **Word position:**

- The order of the verb (بيع), noun (النسخة) and the adjective (الأولى) follow the TT grammar rules.
- The machine follows TT grammar rules in the rest of the sentence.

b\ **Punctuation:** The name of the book “Harry Potter and the Philosopher’s Stone” put between two quotation marks in the ST and TT sentences and both sentences ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The sentence is correct grammatically

Summary:

The machine output is very clear.

c\ Sentence (3):

1\ ST sentence: وكان الكتاب واحدًا من 500-نسخة مطبوعة في أول إصدار له عام 1997 وتم شراؤه من مكتبة في نوتنغهام.

2\ TT sentence: The book was one of 500 copies in print in its first edition in 1997 and was purchased from a bookshop in Nottingham.

Table (23)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	الكتاب	كان	و	0	و
	The book	was	-		
	500 نسخة	من	واحدًا	0	شراء(هـ)
	500 copies	of	one		
	أول	في	مطبوعة	0	0
	first	in	In print		
	عام 1997	ل/هـ	إصدار	0	0
	In 1997	its	edition		
	شراء	تم	و	0	0
	purchased	was	and		
	في	مكتبة	من	0	0
	in	A bookshop	from		
	-	-	نوتنغهام	0	0
			Nottingham		
Total	21			0	2

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (23):

a\ Words count: The ST sentence contains (20) words, while the TT contains (22) words.

- Nouns/pronouns :(10) (500

(لكتاب/ نسخة/ أول/ إصدار/ عام 1997// شراء/ مكتبة/ نوتنغهام/ هـ/ هـ).

- **Verbs:** there is (1) verb (كان/تم).
- **Adjectives:** (2) (واحدًا/مطبوعة).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Conjunctions:** (2), (و/و).
- **Prepositions:** (5) (من/من/في/في/ل).
- **Additional words** there are no additional words.
- **Omitted words** the ST contains (2), which are: (و/ه).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine selected the verb (**was**) as an equivalent to the verbs (كان/تم).
- The machine used the date (**1997**) as an equivalent to (عام 1997), dropping (عام) and replaced by the preposition (**in**).
- The phrase (تم شراؤه) replaced by (**purchased**).
- The equivalent of (نسخة مطبوعة) = **in print copy** is inaccurate, it can be (**printed** or **hard copy**).

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST started with a conjunction and a verb (وكتن), while the TT begins with definite article and a noun (the book).
- The machine substitutes the noun (شراء) with ate verb (purchased), but the meaning remains clear.

d\ **Punctuation:** both ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is correct, despite that the machine made some changes (replace a verb for a noun).

Summary:

The meaning is clear, but not perfect.

d\ Sentence (4):

1\ ST sentence: وعلى صفحة حقوق الطبع والنشر للكتاب، يُشار إلى المؤلفة الشهيرة عالمياً باسم "جوان رولينج".

2\ TT sentence: On the book's copyright page, the world-famous author is referred to as "Joanne Rowling".

Table (24)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	صفحة page	على on	و -	0	و،(على)
	يشار Is referred	للكتاب book	حقوق الطبع والنشر copyright	0	ل
	الشهيرة famous	المؤلفة author	إلى to	0	0
	جوان رولينج Joanne Rowling	باسم as	عالمياً The world	0	0
Total	17			0	2

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (24):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (16) words, while the TT contains (12) words.

- **Nouns:** (7) (صفحة/حقوق/الطبع/النشر/الكتاب/المؤلفة/اسم/جوان رولينج).
- **Verbs:** there is (1) verb (يشار).
- **Adjectives:** (2) (الشهيرة/عالمياً).
- **Adverbs:** no adverbs.
- **Conjunction:** (و)
- **Prepositions:** (1) (على/إلى/ب).
- **Additional words:** there is no additional words.

- **Omitted words** the ST contains (2), which are: (و/ل).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine dropped the conjunction (و) in the beginning of the ST sentence.
- The phrase (صفحة حقوق الطبع والنشر) translated in good way (**copyrightpage**).
- The verb (يشار) converted to the same passive (**referred**).

c\ **Word position:**

- The preposition (على) in the beginning of the ST also placed in the start of the TT.
- The position of the noun (الكتاب) in the ST is the eighth, but in the TT is the third.
- The verb (يشار) in the middle of the ST, but moved to the end of the TT sentence.

b\ **Punctuation:** in both ST and TT sentences the noun (**Joanne Rowling**) put between two quotation marks, then a comma after (للكتاب) (copyright page), and both ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence wording is grammatically correct.

Summary:

The meaning of the TT sentence show the implied meaning of the ST.

e\ Sentence (5):

1\ ST sentence: وقدر المسؤولون عن المزاد، الذي أُجري في شمال يوركشير، سعر الكتاب بحوالي 20.000 إلى 30.000 جنيه إسترليني.

2\ TT sentence: The auction house, which took place in North Yorkshire, estimated the price of the book at between 20,000 and 30,000 pounds.

Table (25)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words		Omitted Words
				Freq.	%	Freq.
	المسؤولون عن المزاد The auction house	قدر estimated	و -	0		و
	في in	أجري Took place	الذي which	0		0
	سعر The price	يوركشير Yorkshire	شمال North	0		0
	20.000 إلى 30.000 جنيه إسترليني 20,000 and 30,000 pounds	بحوالي At between	الكتاب Of the book	0		0
Total	17			0		1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (25):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (17) words, while the TT contains (20) words, classified below:

- **Nouns:** (6) (أزمة/ أزمة/ تونس/ الصراع/ السياسي/ تونس).
- **Verbs** (2) verb (قدر/ أجري).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjectives.

- **Adverbs:** there is no adverbs.
- **Conjunctions:** (1), (و).
- **Prepositions:** (4) (عن/في/ب/إلى).
- **Additional words:** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words:** (1), (و).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

The machine made some changes in the TT sentence, which are:

- Dropped the conjunction (و).
- The phrase (الذي أجري) substituted by (**which took place**), in other word, passive form for passive form.
- The machine did the same with (قدر), which translated to (**estimated**).
- The phrase (المسنولون عن المزاد) translated into (**the auction house**), which is accurate.
- The machine the preposition (إلى) in the end of the ST sentence to a conjunction (**and**), which is also correct.
- The phrase (بحوالي 20,000 إلى 30.000 جنيه استرليني) = **at between 20.000 and 30,000 pounds**) is incorrect, the TT output must be (**about 20.000 to 30.000 pounds**).

c\ **Word position:**

- The verb (قدر) in the **beginning** of the ST sentence, but placed in the **middle** of the TT sentence (**estimated**)
- Also the rest of the TT sentence placed in their correct position, as usual.

d\ **Punctuation:** The ST and TT sentence contain a **comma** after (المزاد) and the (**auction house**), in addition to full stop in the end.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is clear and simple.

4.1.8: Summary of Words Translation Accuracy of the Culture/Art Text:

Table (26)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	8	8	100	0	0
2	17	14	94.2	3	5.8
3	21	20	95.3	1	4.7
4	17	17	100	0	0
5	17	16	94.2	1	5.8
Total	80	75	93.8	5	6.2

Source: Researcher

Table (26) and chart (4) show the accurate and inaccurate words in text (4), there are (3) wrong selection: in sentence (2), the noun phrase (حادثة استثنائية), the machine made a wrong section (exceptional **condition**), while the correct meaning is (**event**), the sentence accuracy rate **94.2%**.

Also, in sentence (2), the indefinite (a) (**a first copy**) = (النسخة الأولى), is incorrect selection, that it can be (**the first copy**), and the passive voice (بيعت), translated into (**has sold**), while the correct equivalent is (p. pt.) (**has been sold**), the sentence accuracy rate is **95.3%**

In sentence (3), the machine selected the wrong equivalent meaning of adjective (مطبوعة), to (in print), it must be (**hard copy**) or (**printed**), the sentence accuracy rate is **94.2%**.

in sentence (5), the phrase (بحوالي 20 إلى 30 ألف جنيه) translated to (**at between 20and 30 thousand Pounds**), while the correct is (**about 20 to 30 thousand Pounds**)

The machine accuracy rate represents in this text is (**93.8%**).

Graph (4)

Source: Researcher

4.1.9: Sample Text (5), (Sports), from Arabic into English.

a\ Sentence (1):

1\ ST sentence: أولمبياد طوكيو: صديقتان سوريّتان فرقتهما الحرب وجمعتهما الرياضة

2\ TT sentence: Tokyo Olympics: Two Syrian friends separated by war and brought together by sport

Table (27)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	صديقة/ان Two friends	طوكيو Tokyo	أولمبياد Olympics	By (war)	فر /ق /ت (هما)
	الحرب war	فرق/ت/هما separated	سورية/ان Syrian	By (sport)	جمع /ت (هما)
	الرياضة sport	جمع/ت/هما Brought together	و and	0	0
Total	15			2	4

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (27):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (15) words, while the TT contains (11) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (11) طوكيو/صديق/تان/الحرب/الرياضة/هما/هما/ت/ت (أو لمبياد).
- **Verbs:** there is (2) verb (فرق/جمع).
- **Adjectives:** (2), (سوري/تان).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** .there is no preposition.
- **Conjunction:** (1), (و).
- **Additional words :**(2), (by/by).
- **Omitted words :**(4), (هما/هما/ت/ت).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The verb (فرق) has (5) equivalents (**Divide/part/ differentiate/ disperse separate**). The machine picked the last one.
- The phrase (سوريتان) consists of (2) adjectives and a noun, the machine translated it correctly (**two Syrian friends**) = (**2 adj. + n**).
- In (فرقتهما) and (جمعتهما), the **pronoun** (ت) refers to (الحرب) in the first phrase, and to (الرياضة) in the second, in both, the ST and TT.

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST started with nominal clause (أولمبياد طوكيو), but a change is made in TT, become (**Tokyo Olympics**) according to the grammar rule.
- Also, a transposition is occurred on the phrase (صديقتان سوريتان) = (n+adj), and translated to (two Syrian friends) = (adj. +adj. +n).

d\ **Punctuation:** Both, ST and TT sentences contain quotation mark and full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The sentence is grammatically correct.

Summary:

The meaning is **clear**.

b\ Sentence (2):

1\ ST sentence: تدريبت ساندا الداس ومنى دهورك معاً منذ الطفولة،

2\ TT sentence: SandaAldas and Mona Duhok have trained together since childhood,

Table (28)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	ساندا الداس SandaAldas	ت -	تدرب trained	0	تدرب(ت)
	معاً together	منى دهورك Mona Duhok	و and	0	0
	-	الطفولة childhood	منذ since	0	0
Total	8			0	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (28):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (8) words, while the TT contains (7) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (3) (ساندا الداس/ منى دهورك/ت).
- **Verbs:** there is (1) verb (تدرب).
- **Adjectives:** (1) there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** (1) (معاً)
- **Prepositions:** (2) (منذ).
- **Conjunctions:** there is no conjunction.
- **Additional words** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words** (1), (ت).

b\ Lexical words election:

- The verb (تدرب) has (6) equivalent meanings, (**train/practice/exercise/intern/drill/work out**), the machine picked the first one.
- In this short sentence, there is no significant change, made by the machine.

c\ Word position:

- The ST sentence starts with a verb (تدرب), while the TT begins a noun (SandaAldas).
- Both sentences, ST and TT, have the same ending (معًا منذ الطفولة) and (**together since childhood**).

d\ Punctuation: There a comma in the end of both, the ST and TT sentences.

e / Grammatical Accuracy:

The grammatical structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is very clear.

c\ Sentence (3):

1\ ST sentence: لكن الحرب في سوريا فرقتهما.

2\ TT sentence: but the war in Syria separated them

Table (29)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	في	الحرب	لكن	0	فرق(ت)
	in	The war	but		
	-	فرق/ت/هما	سوريا	0	0
		Separated them	Syria		
Total	7			0	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (29):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (7) words, while the TT contains (7) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (4) (الحرب/سوريا/ت/هما).
- **Verbs:** there is (1) verb (فرق).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverbs.
- **Prepositions:** (1) (في).
- **Conjunctions:** (1) (لكن).
- **Additional words** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words** (1), (ت).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

Among (17) equivalents of the verb (فرق), (divide/part/differentiate/disperse/separate /allow/be afraid/become afraid/defuse/be scared/disunite/scatter/strew about/distribute/apportion/give out/parcel out) the machine selected the fifth, (separate).

c\ **Word position:**

- Both sentences started with the conjunction (لكن) = (but).
- Because the sentence is short and simple words place did not change.

d\ **Punctuation:** The ST and TT sentences ended with a comma.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The structure of the TT sentence is accurate.

Summary:

The meaning is very clear.

d\ **Sentence (4):**

1\ ST sentence: وجدت الصديقتان الأمان في هولندا،

2\ TT sentence: The two friends found safety in the Netherlands,

Table (30)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	الأمان safety	الصديق/ت/ان The two friends	وجدت found	0	وجدت
	-	هولندا The Netherlands	في in	0	0
Total	8			0	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (30):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (7) words, while the TT contains (8) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (6) (الصديق/ت/ان/الأمان/هولندا/ت).
- **Verbs:** there is (1) verb (وجد).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (1) (في).
- **Conjunctions:** there is no conjunction.
- **Additional words** there are no additional word.

- **Omitted words (1) (ت)**

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

The machine introduced (7) meanings of the verb (وجد), (**find/locate/hit/get it/puzzle out/mange**), and picked the first one (find).

The noun (الأمان) has just one equivalent (**safety**).

The rest of the selection is correct, because the sentence is short and simple.

c\ **Word position:**

The ST begins with the verb (وجد), while the TT, starts with (**definite article + adjective + noun**) = (**the two friends**), following grammatical rule of the TT.

d\ **Punctuation:** Both sentences ended with a comma.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The structure is correct, the there is no mistake in the MT output

Summary:

The meaning is **clear, the ST meaning is similar to the TT.**

e\ **Sentence (5):**

1\ ST sentence: وأصبحتا جزءاً من فريق اللاجئين الأولمبي.

2\ TT sentence: and became part of the refugee Olympic team.

Table (31)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	جزءاً part	أصبح/ت/ا became	و and	0	أصبح(ت/ا)
	اللاجئين The refugee	فريق team	من of	0	0
	-	-	الأولمبي Olympic	0	0
Total	9			0	2

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (31):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (8) words, while the TT contains (8) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (5) (جزءاً/ فريق/ اللاجئين/ت/ا).
- **Verbs:** there is (1) verb (أصبح).
- **Adjectives:** (1) (الأولمبي).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (1) (من).
- **Conjunctions:** (1) (و).
- **Additional words** (2), (ت/ا).
- **Additional words** there are no additional word.

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- There are (8) equivalent meanings of the verb (أصبح), (**become/be/ turn into/ fall/turn out/turn off/wax/go**), the machine picked the first one (**become**).
- Also, the noun (جزء) has (10) meanings, (**part/portion/fraction/ section/piece/bit/ share/ parcel/partition/slice**), the machine selected the first equivalent (**part**).
- In the rest of the sentence, the machine also made the correct selections.

c\ **Word position:**

- Both, the St and TT started with a conjunction followed by a verb (واصبح) = (**and became**)
- The ST phrase (فريق اللاجئين الأولمبي) consists of (**noun +noun +adjective**), while in the TT, the order of these (3) words is changed (**noun +adjective +noun**), (**refugee Olympic team**).

b\ **Punctuation:** both ST and TT sentences ended with a comma.

d / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

f) Sentence (6):

1\ ST sentence اللاعبين السوريين ضمن الفريق المختلط للجودو والذي يلعب لأول مرة في أولمبياد طوكيو.

2\ TT sentence: The two Syrian players are part of the mixed judo team, which is playing for the first time in the Tokyo Olympics.

Table (32)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	الفريق team	ضمن part	اللاعبان السوريين The two Syrian players	Are (part)	و
	الذي which	و -	المختلط ل /لجودو Of the judo mixed	The	0
	أول first	ل for	يلعب Is playing	0	0
	أولمبياد Olympics	في in	مرة time	0	0
	-	-	طوكيو Tokyo	0	0
Total	20			2	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (32):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (20) words, while the TT contains (21) words.

- **Nouns:** (12) (اللاعب/ت/ان/السوري/ت/ان/الفريق/الجودو/مرة/أولمبياد/طوكيو/الذي).
- **Verbs:** there is (1) verb (يلعب).
- **Adjectives:** (1) (المختلط/أول).
- **Adverbs:** (1) (كيف).
- **Prepositions:** (4) (ضمن/ل/ل/في).

- **Conjunctions:** (1) (و).
- **Additional words** (2), (are/the).
- **Omitted words:** (1) (و).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine processed the noun (جزء) in the same way in the previous sentence.
- The adjective (مختلط) has (4) equivalent (**mixed/jumbled/ disordered/ unsettled**), and the machine picked the first one.
- The noun (مرة) has (3) equivalents (**time/once/whet**), the machine selected the first one.

c\ **Word position:**

- The noun clause (اللاعبان السوريان), processed as (**the two Syrian players**), that the TT started with (**definite article +adjective**) = (**the two**), which is correct transposition.
- The phrase (الفريق المختلط للجودو) translated to (**the mixed judo team**), or (noun +adjective +noun)=(**definite article +adjective +noun +noun**), that the adjective (مختلط) moved (**mixed**) to the beginning of the phrase.

d/ **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The sentence is correct grammatically.

e\ **Punctuation:** Both sentences ended with full stop.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

4.1.10: Summary of Words Translation Accuracy of the Sports Text:

Table (33)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	15	15	100	0	0
2	8	8	100	0	0
3	7	7	100	0	0
4	8	8	100	0	0
5	9	9	100	0	0
6	20	20	100	0	0
Total	67	67	100	0	0

Source: Researcher

Table (33) and chart (5) show the accurate and inaccurate words in text (5), it is noticeable that all the selections of the machine are correct, and accurate, so the **performance** is completely accurate, (100%).

Graph (5)

Source: Researcher

4.1.11: Sample Text (6): (Legal), from Arabic into English.

a\ Sentence (1):

1\ ST sentence: معركة قانونية بين الحكومة البريطانية و"بي بي سي" بسبب تقرير إخباري عن جاسوس

2\ TT sentence: A legal battle between the British government and the BBC over a spy report.

Table (34)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	بين	قانونية	معركة	0	عن (جاسوس)
	between	A legal	battle		
	و	البريطانية	الحكومة	0	0
	and	British	government		
	تقرير إخباري	بسبب	بي بي سي	0	0
	report	over	The BBC		
			عن جاسوس	0	0
			A spy		
Total	12			0	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (34):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (12) words, while the TT contains (13) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (6) (معركة/ الحكومة/ البريطانية/ بي بي سي/ تقرير/ جاسوس).
- **Verbs:** There is no verb.
- **Adjectives:** (2), (قانونية/ إخباري).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (3), (بين/ بسبب/ عن).
- **Conjunction:** (1), (و).
- **Additional words:** There is no additional word.

- **Omitted words:** (1), (عن).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The noun (معركة) has (9) equivalents (**battle/combat/fighting/ clash/ conflict/ action/ engament/encounter/fray**), and the machine picked the first one.
- The acronym "بي بي سي" translated at the same way (**BBC**), and dropped the double quotation marks.
- Both the ST nouns (تقرير إخباري/جاسوس), and TT (**a spy/a report**) are undefined.
- The compound noun (تقرير إخباري), translated into (**report**), also (تقرير) has the same machine equivalent.

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST starts with noun (معركة), while the TT starts with an adjective (**legal**) , that in English the adjective precedes the noun.
- The preposition (بين), (**between**), at the same place, in ST and TT.

d\ **Punctuation:** there is no punctuation in this sentence, because it is the headline (title) of the report, besides the double quotation mark dropped from the TT.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

the structure is correct, the words' use, and meaning suggested by the MT is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is **clear**, that the machine gives the same "source meaning".

b\ Sentence (2):

1\ ST sentence: تنهياً حكومة المملكة المتحدة وشبكة "بي بي سي" البريطانية لخوض معركة قضائية بسبب تقرير إخباري تنوي المؤسسة التلفزيونية بثه، قيل إن من شأنه أن يكشف هوية أحد جواسيس الحكومة.

2\ TT sentence: The UK government and the BBC are preparing for a court battle over a news report the television network plans to broadcast that is said to have exposed the identity of a government spy.

Table (35)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	المملكة المتحدة UK	حكومة government	تنهياً preparing	0	شبكة
	بي بي سي BBC	شبكة -	و and	0	البريطانية
	معركة battle	ل/خوض for	البريطانية -	0	خوض
	تقرير report	بسبب over	قضائية court	0	بث(ه)
	المؤسسة network	تنوي plan	إخباري news	0	من شأنه
	قيل إن That is said	بثه broadcast	التلفزيونية television	0	0
	هوية identity	أن يكشف to Have exposed	من شأنه -	0	0
	-	الحكومة government	أحد جواسيس A spy	0	0
Total	30			0	7

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (35):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (28) words, while the TT contains (25) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (16)

المملكة المتحدة/شبكة/بي بي سي/خوض/معركة/تقرير/المؤسسة/بث/ه/هوية/جواسيس
(حكومة/شأن/ه/الحكومة/ة).

- **Verbs:** (4), (تنهياً/تنوي/قيل/يكشف).

- **Adjectives:** (4), (قضائية/إخباري/التلفزيوني/أحد).

- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.

- **Prepositions:** (3), (ل/بسبب/من).

- **Conjunction:** (3), (و/أن/أن).

- **Additional words:** There is no additional word.

- **Omitted words:** (7), (شبكة/البريطانية/خوض/ه/من/شأن/ه).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The verb (تنهياً) has just one meaning as a single word, (**getting ready**), but in the context (complete sentence) the meaning is changed to (**preparing**).

- The noun (المملكة المتحدة), translated into (**the UK**), also, (بي بي سي) to (**theBBC**)

- In the TT the machine dropped the nouns (شبكة/البريطانية/خوض) and the pronouns (ه) referring to (**the report**), besides (من شأنه).

- The adjective (قضائية), has (3) meanings, (**judicial/judiciary/forensic**), and the machine made another selection out of this list, the meaning of (**court**) is referring to (**legal battle in court**).

- The verb (تنوي) has (8) meanings (**intend/meant/mean/purpose/plan/project/propose/have in mind**), the machine picked the fifth equivalent, (**plan**).

- The machine in the previous sentence translated (تقرير إخباري) into (report), but in this sentence translated it into (**news report**), both selections are correct.
- The phrase (أحد جواسيس) translated into (**a spy**), because of the adjective (أحد), plus its equivalent (the indefinite article) (**a**).

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST starts with the verb (تتهياً), while the TT starts with nominal phrase (**the UK government**).
- In the phrase (أحد جواسيس الحكومة), the machine interchanged the places of the two nouns in the TT (**a government spy**).

d\ **Punctuation:** the machine dropped the double quotation marks “بي بي سي” from the TT, and retained the full stop in both sentences.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The structure is correct

Summary:

The meaning is **clear**.

c\ Sentence (3):

1\ ST sentence: وأفادت صحيفة "تليغراف" بأن البرنامج الإخباري قد يفصح هوية أحد موظفي الاستخبارات البريطانية من الذين يعملون خارج البلاد، وعلم أن المسألة تعد حساسة للغاية.

2\ TT sentence: And the newspaper "Telegraph" reported that the news program may expose the identity of a British intelligence employee who is working outside the country, and learned that the issue is very sensitive.

Table (36)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	تليغراف Telegraph	أفادت/ت reported	و and	newspaper	أفادت(ت)
	الإخباري news	البرنامج The program	بأن that	0	يعمل/ون
	هوية identity	يفصح عن expose	قد may	0	موظف/ي
	الاستخبارات intelligence	موظفي employee	أحد -	0	تعد
	يعمل/ون working	من الذين who	البريطانية British	0	0
	و and	البلاد The country	خارج outside	0	0
	المسألة The issue	أن that	علم learned	0	0
	للاغاية Is very	حساسة sensitive	تعد -	0	0
Total				1	4

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (36):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (28) words, while the TT contains (26) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (10) تليغراف/ البرنامج/ هوية/ موظف/ الاستخبارات/ الذين (ت/ي/ون (/المسألة
- **Verbs:** (5), (أفاد/يفصح/يعمل/علم/تعد).
- **Adjectives:** (5), (قضائية/الإخباري/التلفزيوني/أحد/حساسة).
- **Adverbs:** (2), (قد/للغاية).
- **Prepositions:** (2), (من/عن).
- **Conjunction:** (4), (و/و/بأن/أن).
- **Additional words:** (1), (newspaper).
- **Omitted words:** (4), (ت/ون/ي/تعد).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The verb (أفاد) as a single word has (5) meanings, (**stated/ benefit/ avail/signify/subserve**), and the equivalent meaning (**reported**), is not in this list, so the nearest meaning is (**stated**).
- The verb (يفصح), has two meanings (**reveal/disclose**), and the machine selected another meaning (**expose**), which is also correct.
- The noun (مسألة) has (8) equivalent meaning (**issue/question/matter/ problem/case/affair/thing/proposition**) and the machine picked the first one.
- The word (للغاية) can be classified as an adverb if means (**very**), and adjective when means (**extremely** or **very much indeed**), in this sentence the machine dealt with it as an **adverb**.

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST starts with conjunction article and verb (وأفادت), while the TT begins with (**and the newspaper**) = (**conj. + definite Article + noun**).
- There is no important change in the position of the rest of words.

d\ **Punctuation:** the two sentences contain double quotation marks “Telegraph”+”تليغراف”, in addition to full stop in the end.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The structure is correct

Summary:

The meaning is **clear**.

d\ Sentence (4):

1\ ST sentence: ولم يأت أي من طرفي النزاع القانوني على ذكر محتوى البرنامج المراد بثه، لكن كلاهما أكدا أن الحكومة البريطانية كانت تسعى إلى الحصول على إنذار قضائي بعدم بثه.

2\ TT sentence: None of the two sides of the legal conflict did not mention the content of the program to broadcast, but both stressed that the British government was seeking to obtain a judicial alarm not to broadcast.

Table (37)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	ذكر mention	لم يأت على Did not	و -	0	و
	النزاع The conflict	طرفي two side	أي من None of	0	طرف (ي)
	البرنامج The program	محتوى content	القانوني legal	0	بث (هـ)
	كليهما both	لكن but	المراد بثه To broadcast	0	أكد (ا)
	الحكومة government	أن that	أكدا stressed	0	بث (هـ)
	تسعى seeking	كانت was	البريطانية The British	0	كلي/هما
	إنذار alarm	الحصول على obtain	إلى to	0	كان/ت
	بثه broadcast	بعدم Not to	قضائي judicial	0	ب/عدم
Total	34			0	8

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (37):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (34) words, while the TT contains (31) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (17) ذكر/أي/طرف/ي /هـ/النزاع /محتوى /البرنامج (17) (الحصول/إنذار/عدم/بث/ت/هـ/ا /بث/الحكومة).
- **Verbs:** (4), (يأت /أكد /كان/تسعى).
- **Adjectives:** (4), (القانوني/المراد /كلا /قضائي).
- **Adverbs:** (1), (لم).
- **Prepositions:** (5), (على/من/إلى/ب/على).
- **Conjunction:** (3), (و/لكن/أن).
- **Additional words:** there are no additional words.
- **Omitted words :** (8), (و/ي/هـ/ا/هـ/هما/ت/ب).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine translated the phrase (لم يأت على ذكر) to (**did not mention**).
- The phrase (أي من) translated into (**none of**)
- The noun (نزاع) has (13) meanings, (**conflict/dispute/row/strife/struggle/contention/quarrel/controversy/odds/disagreement/disputation/question/fray**), and the machine selected the second one, the accurate selection is (**dispute**), because it has more legal sense.
- The noun (إنذار) has (10) Meanings, (**warning/alert/notice/ultimatum/alarm/prognosis/callosity/intimation/signaling**), and the machine picked (**alarm**), which is correct, but there are many other correct nouns (**warning/alert/notice**).

c\ **Word position:**

- Both sentences started with negation (لم), (**did not**), preceding the past tense (لم يأت على ذكر or لم يذكر), (**did not mention**).
- The machine dropped the conjunction (و), from the ST sentence.

- In the phrase (النزاع القانوني), (إنذار قضائي), the noun precedes the adjective, while in the TT, the adjective comes first (**legal conflict**), (**judicial alarm**), following the grammatical rule in both languages.

d\ **Punctuation:** the two sentences contain comma and full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The structure is correct, the MT out shows above.

Summary:

The TT shows a clear meaning, that the machine selected the correct meaning, and the structure, grammatically is correct.

e\ **Sentence (5):**

1\ ST sentence: وأوضحت شبكة "بي بي سي" في بيان لها أن المدعي العام حرك إجراءات قانونية ضد المؤسسة بهدف الحصول على أمر قضائي يمنع نشر تقرير إخباري أعدته "بي بي سي".

2\ TT sentence: The BBC said in a statement that "the attorney general has initiated legal proceedings against the institution with the aim of obtaining a court order preventing the publication of a news report prepared by the BBC."

Table (38)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	شبكة -	أوضح/ت said	و -	With the aim of	و
	بيان لها A statement	في in	"بي بي سي" The BBC	Publication (of)	أوضح/ت
	حرك Has initiated	المدعي العام Attorney general	أن that	0	شبكة
	ضد against	قانونية legal	إجراءات proceedings	0	لها
	الحصول على obtaining	يهدف With the aim of	المؤسسة The institution	0	0
	نشر The publication of	يمنع Preventing	أمر قضائي Court order	0	0
	أعدته Prepared by	إخباري report	تقرير A news	0	0
	-	-	"بي بي سي" The BBC	0	0
Total	27			1	4

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (38):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (27) words, while the TT contains (32) words.

- **Nouns and pronouns:** (15), (شبكة/ت/"بي بي سي"/بيان/لها/المدعي (العام/إجراءات/المؤسسة/هدف/الحصول/أمر/نشر/تقرير/ت-ه
- **Verbs:** (4), (أوضح/حرك/يمنع/أعد).
- **Adjectives:** (3), (قانونية/قضائي/إخباري).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.

- **Prepositions:** (3), (في/ضد/على).
- **Conjunction:** (2), (و/أن/).
- **Additional words:** (3), (the/of/of).
- **Omitted words :**(4), (و/ت/شبكة/لها).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The verb (أوضح), has (14) equivalent meanings, (**clarify/explain/light/illustrate/state/spell/represent/define/illucidate/illuminate/lithten/puzzle out/ravel out/accentuate**), but the machine used another verb (**said**), which is accurate.
- The machine dropped the noun (شبكة), because the acronym (**BBC**) is widely known.
- The compound noun (المدعي العام) and (النائب العام) has more than one equivalent (**attorney general/public prosecutor/prosecutor/procurator/ solicitor general**), and the machine picked the first one.
- The phrase (**with the aim of**) is **inaccurate** equivalent of (بهدف); it can be replaced by (**to**).
- The equivalent of the verb (حرك), which means (**started**), the machine replaced it with (**initiated**).

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST started with the verb (أوضح), while the TT started with the noun (**the BBC**).
- There is no important changes in the position of the rest of words.

d\ **Punctuation:**

- In the ST, the double quotation marks mentioned two times, but dropped from the TT.
- Both sentences ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The structure is correct

Summary:

The meaning is **clear**.

4.1.12: Summary of Words Translation Accuracy of the Legal Text Arabic into English:

Table (39)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	12	12	100	0	0
2	30	30	100	0	0
3	28	26	100	0	0
4	34	32	94.1	2	5.9
5	27	26	96.2	1	3.8
Total	129	126	97.6	3	2.4

Source: Researcher

Table (39) and chart (6) show the accurate and inaccurate words in text (6). In sentence (4), the machine selected the equivalent noun (**conflict**) to the noun (نزاع), while the accurate selection is (**dispute**). Also, the machine picked the equivalent noun (alarm) to (إنذار), while the accurate selection is one of the three equivalents (**warning/alert/notice**). The accuracy rate is (**94.1%**).

In sentence (5), the phrase (بهدف) translated into (**with the aim of**), which is incorrect, the right selection must be (to), so the accuracy rate is (96.2%).

Graph (6)

Source: Researcher

4.1.13: Total statistics of Words Translation Accuracy English into Arabic

Table (40)

text	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	83	81	97.6	2	2.4
2	138	136	98.6	2	1.4
3	112	103	92	9	8
4	80	75	93.8	5	6.2
5	47	47	100	0	0
6	129	126	97.6	3	2.4
Total	589	568	96.5	21	3.5

Source: Researcher

Table (40) and chart (7) show total translation accuracy rates of part (1) (Arabic into English). In text (1) the accuracy is (97.6%), while text (2) the machine accuracy represents (98.6%), and text (3), (92%), in text (4) the accuracy rate is (93.8%), but the machine performance is perfect in text (5), e.t. (100%). While in text (6) the rate went down to (97.6%).

The total translation accuracy rate of this section (Arabic into English) is (96.5%).

Graph (7)

Source: Researcher

4.2. English into Arabic Sample Texts:

4.2.1: Sample Text (1) (political), English into Arabic

a\ Sentence (1):

1\ **ST sentence:** Why is France angry over nuclear submarines deal between US, UK & Australia?.

2\ **TT sentence:** لماذا فرنسا غاضبة من صفقة الغواصات النووية بين الولايات المتحدة والمملكة المتحدة وأستراليا؟

Table (1)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	why لماذا	France فرنسا	Is angry غاضبة	0	0
	over من	nuclear النووية	submarines الغواصات	0	0
	deal صفقة	between بين	US الولايات المتحدة	0	0
	UK المملكة المتحدة	& و	Australia أستراليا	0	0
Total	13			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (1):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (13) words, while the TT contains (12) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (6), (France/submarine/deal/US/UK/Australia)
- **Verbs:** (1), (is).
- **Adjectives:** (2) (angry/nuclear).
- **Adverbs:** (1) (why)
- **Prepositions:** (2) (over/ between).
- **Conjunction:** (1) (&).

- **Additional words:** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words** there is no omitted words.

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine selected the first equivalent of the adjective (**angry**), which has five meanings (غاضب/محتد/متوعد بغضب/مغيظ/محنق).
- The machine translated the acronyms (**US/UK**) accurately.
- The machine translated the ampersand (**&**) into (و).
- The machine introduced (8) equivalent meanings of the preposition (**over**), (خلال/فوق/حتى/عن طريق/بالقرب/على الجانب الآخر من/على طول كذا/إلى), which all did not give the correct meaning implied in the ST, which means (بسبب), and the equivalent (من) is inaccurate.

c\ **Word position:**

- Both sentences (ST/TT) started with an adverb (**why**)=(لماذا).
- The nouns (**France/deal/ US/ UK/Australia**) at the same position in the TT.

d\ **Punctuation:** The interrogative sentences in the (ST/TT) ended with question mark.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear, despite the incorrect equivalent of the preposition (over).

(b) Sentence (2):

1\ ST sentence: After US, UK and Australia announced a trilateral security pact that would enable Australia to get nuclear-powered submarines,

2\ TT sentence: بعد إعلان الولايات المتحدة والمملكة المتحدة وأستراليا اتفاقية أمنية ثلاثية من شأنها أن تمكن أستراليا من الحصول على غواصات تعمل بالطاقة النووية،

Table (2)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	after بعد	US الولايات المتحدة	UK المملكة المتحدة	تعمل (بالطاقة)	A (trilateral)
	and و	Australia أستراليا	announced إعلان	0	0
	A trilateral ثلاثية	Security أمنية	pact اتفاقية	0	0
	That أن	would من شأنه	enable تمكن	0	0
	Australia استراليا	to من	get الحصول على	0	0
	Nuclear- powered تعمل بالطاقة النووية	submarines غواصات	-	0	0
Total	19			1	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (2):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST Sentence contains (19) words, while the TT contains (21) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns:** The ST contains (7)
(US/UK/Australia/security/pact/Australia/submarine)

- **Verbs:** (4), (announced/would/enable/get)
- **Adjective:**(3), (trilateral/nuclear/powered)
- **Adverb:** there is no adverbs.
- **Preposition:** (2), (after/to).
- **Conjunctions:** (3), (that/and/a).
- **Additional words** (1), (تعمل).
- **Omitted Words** :(1), (a).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine translated the verb (**would**) into ablative case (من شأنه), and the adjective (**nuclear-powered**) into adjective (تعمل بالطاقة النووية).
- The noun (**announcement**) has (3) equivalents, (إعلان/تصريح/بلاغ), the machine picked the first one.
- The verb (**get**) has (14) equivalents, (يحصل (على/جلب/كسب/أصاب/أخرج/نال/فاز/حيز/صير في حالة/زار/هيا/انتقم من/فاز بـ/أثار), the machine selected the first one.
- The noun (**pact**) has (9) meanings, (ميثاق/اتفاق/اتفاقية/معاهدة/تحالف/عهد/عقد/ذمة/معاهدة دولية), and the machine picked the third equivalent.
- The verb (**announced**) converted to a noun in the TT (إعلان), it is an accurate translation, but also can be (أن أعلنت).
- The verb (**get**), converted into noun phrase (الحصول على).

c\ **Word position:**

- Both sentences begin with preposition (**after**), (بعد), but the second word of the ST sentence is a noun (**US**).
- The phrase (**trilateral security pact**), (**adj. +adj. +N**), while, in the TT (اتفاقية أمنية ثلاثية), (**N+ adj. +adj.**).

d\ **Punctuation:** both the ST and TT ended with comma.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The grammatical structure is correct. Poor style of the ST Sentence produces a poor

Summary:

Despite the weak structure of the ST, the meaning is clear.

(c) Sentence (3):

1\ ST sentence: France said it was "very angry and bitter".

2\ TT sentence: "قالت فرنسا إنها "غاضبة ومريرة للغاية".

Table (3)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	France فرنسا	said قال/ت	it إن/ها	إن	was
	was -	Very للغاية	angry غاضب/ة	قال(ت)	0
	and و	bitter مريرة	-	غاضب(ة)	0
Total	8			3	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (3):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (8) words, while the TT contains (11) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (2) (/France /it).
- **Verbs:** there is (2) verb (said/was).
- **Adjectives:** (2) (/angry/bitter).
- **Adverbs:** (1), (very).
- **Conjunction:** (1), (and).
- **Prepositions:** there is no preposition.
- **Additional words**(3), (إن/ت/ة).
- **Omitted words:** (1), (was).

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine gives (4) equivalents to adjective (**bitter**), (مرارة/ساخر/عنيف/لاذع), and selected the first one.
- The adverb (**very**) has (3) meanings, (جداً/تماماً/إلى حد بعيد), while the machine translated it into (للغاية), which didn't include in this list.

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST started with a noun (**France**), while the TT begins with verb (قال).
- The phrase (**very angry and bitter**), (adv. +adj.+ conj. +adj.), while the word order in the TL sentence (غاضبة ومريرة للغاية), (adj.+ conj. +adj. +adv.)

b\ **Punctuation:** both, the ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The structure of the TT sentence is very poor; it could be (وقالت فرنسا إنها شعرت)
(بالغضب والمرارة)

Summary:

The meaning is **clear**, but structure, as referred to, in the previous point, is very weak.

(d) Sentence (4):

1\ ST sentence: This is because France's partly state-owned Naval Group was chosen in 2016 to build 12 conventional diesel-electrical submarines for Australia.

وذلك لأن مجموعة نافال الفرنسية المملوكة جزئياً للدولة تم اختيارها في عام 2016 \ TT sentence 2
لبناء 12 غواصة تقليدية تعمل بالديزل والكهرباء لأستراليا.

Table (4)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	this is و/ذلك	because لأن	France's الفرنسية	و	0
	partly جزئياً	State-owned مملوكة للدولة	Naval Group مجموعة نافال	اختيار (ها)	0
	was تم	chosen اختيار/ها	In 2016 عام 2016	0	0
	To ل	Build بناء	12 conventional 12 تقليدية	0	0
	Diesel- electrical تعمل بالديزل والكهرباء	Submarine غواصة	For ل	0	0
	Australia أستراليا			0	0
Total	17			1	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (4):

a) **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (17) words, while the TT contains (19) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (7) (this/France/Naval Group/in 2016/build/12 conventional/submarine/Australia).
- **Verbs:** (3) verb (is/was/chosen).
- **Adjectives:** (2) (/state-owned/diesel-electrical).
- **Adverbs:** (1), (partly).
- **Prepositions:** (2), (to/for).

- **Conjunctions:** (1) (because).
- **Additional words:** (2), (و/ها).
- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted words.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The pronoun (**this**), translated into (ذلك), and the correct equivalent is (هذا).
- The adverb (**partly**) has (2) equivalents (جزئياً/إلى حد ما), the machine selected the first one.
- The (phrase) or adjective (**state-owned**), translated into (المملوكة للدولة), (adj. into adj.).
- The adjective (**conventional**) has (9) equivalent meanings (تقليدي/عادي/مألوف/متمسك بالعرف/اصطلاحي/مبتذل/مؤتمر/مؤتمري/لطيف بطريقة (رسمية)), but classified as a noun because it is connected with a number (12).
- The adjective (**diesel-electrical**) translated into the adjective (تعمل بالديزل), the meaning is inaccurate, it must be (تعمل بالديزل), or (بالكهرباء (المنتجة من الديزل)).

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST begins with pronoun (this), while the TT begins with a conjunction (و).
- The noun (**Naval Group**), when translated into (مجموعة نافال), comes before the phrase (الفرنسية المملوكة جزئياً للدولة).

b\ **Punctuation:** both sentences, ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct,

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**.

(e) Sentence (5):

1\ ST sentence: The trilateral pact means that the French-Australian deal is effectively scrapped.

2\ TT sentence: يعني الاتفاق الثلاثي أن الصفقة الفرنسية الأسترالية تم إلغاؤها فعلياً.

Table (5)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	The trilateral الثلاثي	pact الاتفاق	means يعني	تم/ إلغاؤها	0
	that أن	the French- Australian الفرنسية الأسترالية	deal الصفقة	0	0
	is effectively فعلياً	scrapped تم إلغاؤها	-	0	0
Total	11			2	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (5):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST Sentence contains (11) words, while the TT contains (10).

- **Nouns/ pronouns:**(2) (pact/deal)
- **Verbs:** (3), (mean/is/scrapped)
- **Adjective:** (2), (trilateral/the French-Australian)
- **Adverb:** (1), (effectively).
- **Preposition:** there is no prepositions.
- **Conjunctions:** (3), (that/the/the).
- **Additional words** (2), (تم/ها).
- **Omitted Words:** there is no omitted words.

b\ Lexical word selection:

- The adverb (**effectively**) has (1) equivalent (على نحو فعال), and the machine adapted it with the context to be (فعلياً).
- The verb (**scrapped**), has (5) meanings (تخلص من/تشاجر/باع/نبذ/هجر), but the machine translated it to (ألغى), which is not included in this list.

c\ Word position:

- The ST started with definite article and noun (**the trilateral**), while TT started with a verb (يعني).
- The rest of the TT words aligned to each other.

d\ Punctuation: both sentences ended with full stop.

e / Grammatical Accuracy:

The TT sentence is grammatically correct.

Summary:

The TT structure is correct, but it can be clearer and more lucid if some changes done, such like (ويعني الاتفاق الثلاثي أن الصفقة الفرنسية الأسترالية أصبحت ملغية) (فعلياً), by adding conjunction (و), in the beginning of the sentence, replacing (تم إلغاؤها), by (أصبحت ملغية).

4.2.2: Summary of Words Translation Accuracy of the Political Text English into Arabic:

This text consists of five sentences

Table (6)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	13	12	92.4	1	7.6
2	19	19	100	0	0
3	8	6	75	2	25
4	17	15	88.3	2	11.7
5	11	9	81.9	2	18.1
Total	68	61	89.8	7	10.2

Source: Researcher

Table (6) chart (1) show the **accurate** and **inaccurate** words in text (1): In sentence (1) the equivalent meaning of (**over**) is (من) which is not accurate, it must be (بسبب), the sentence accuracy rate is **92.4%**.

In sentence (3) the equivalent of the adjective (**bitter**) is (مريرة), but it is not the accurate contextual meaning, it must be (وقالت فرنسا إنها شعرت بالغضب والمرارة) not (قالت فرنسا إنها "غاضبة ومريرة للغاية") so, the sentence accuracy rate is **75%**

In sentence (4) the pronoun (**this**), translated into (ذلك), and the correct equivalent is (هذا).

Also in sentence (4) the equivalent of the adjective (**diesel-electrical**) is (تعمل بالكهرباء المنتجة من الديزل), is inaccurate, it must be (تعمل بالديزل), or (بالكهرباء المنتجة من الديزل). The accuracy rate is **88.3%**.

In sentence (5) the output (يعني الاتفاق الثلاثي أن الصفقة الفرنسية الأسترالية تم إلغاؤها فعليًا.) is correct, but inaccurate, it must be (ويعني الاتفاق الثلاثي أن الصفقة الفرنسية الأسترالية (أصبحت ملغية فعليًا.), the accuracy rate is **81.9%**.

The total accuracy rate is tis text is **89.8%**.

Graph (1)

Source: Researcher

4.2.3: Sample Text (2): (Economic)

(a) Sentence (1):

1\ ST sentence: Suzuki Motor Gujarat to reduce production in Aug due to chip shortage

2\ TT sentence: سوزوكي موتور غوجارات ستخفض الإنتاج في أغسطس بسبب نقص الرقائق.

Table (7)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Suzuki Motors Gujarat سوزوكي موتور غوجارات	To reduce ستخفض	production الإنتاج	0	0
	in في	August أغسطس	due to بسبب	0	0
	Chip الرقائق	shortage نقص	-	0	0
Total	9			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (7):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (9) words, while the TT contains (9) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (5), (Suzuki Motors Gujarat/ production/ August/chip/ shortage)
- **Verbs:** (1), (reduce).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (2) (to/ in/due to).
- **Conjunction:** there is no conjunctions.
- **Additional words** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words** there is no omitted words.

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The sentence is short and represents a headline of the news article, so, most of its words are nouns and prepositions.
- The compound noun (**Suzuki Motors Gujarat**) translated correctly.
- All of the selections made by the machine are correct.

c\ **Word position:**

- There is no change in the position of the words of the TT.

d\ **Punctuation:** there is no punctuation marks because this is a headline.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

(b) Sentence (2):

1\ ST sentence: Suzuki Motor Gujarat will scale down production activity this month at its manufacturing plant in Ahmedabad, Gujarat due to semiconductor shortage, Maruti Suzuki India has said.

2\ TT sentence: قالت ماروتي سوزوكي الهند إن سوزوكي موتور جوجارات ستقلص نشاط الإنتاج هذا الشهر في مصنعها في أحمد أباد بولاية غوجارات بسبب نقص أشباه الموصلات.

Table (8)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Suzuki Motor Gujarat سوزوكي موتور غوجارات	will Scale down ستقلص	production الإنتاج	قال/ت	0
	activity نشاط	this هذا	month الشهر	0	0
	at في	its manufacturing plant مصنعها	in في	0	0
	Ahmedabad أحمد أباد	Gujarat غوجارات	Due to بسبب	0	0
	semiconductor أشباه الموصلات	shortage نقص	Maruti Suzuki India ماروتي سوزوكي الهند	0	0
	Has/said قال/ت	-	-	0	0
Total	19			1	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (8):

a\ **Words equivalent** the ST sentence contains (19) words, while the TT contains (19) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns** The ST contains (12) (Suzuki Motor Gujarat/ production/activity/this/month/its/manufacturing plant/ Ahmedabad/ Gujarat/semiconductor/shortage/Maruti Suzuki India)
- **Verbs:** (4), (will/scale down/has/said)
- **Adjective:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverb** there is no adverbs.
- **Preposition:** (3), (at/in/due to).
- **Conjunctions:** there is no conjunction.
- **Additional words** (1), (ت).
- **Omitted Words** there is no omitted words.

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine translated nouns (**Suzuki Motors Gujarat**) and (**Suzuki Maruti**), accurately.
- There are (4) equivalent meanings of the noun (**plant**), (مصنع/نبات/معمل/نبته), and the machine picked the first.
- The verb (**scale down**) has (3) meanings, (خفض/قلص/خفض السعر), the machine selected the first equivalent.
- The machine and gave (1) meaning to the noun (**semiconductor**), (أشباه موصلات) classified it as plural.

c\ **Word position:**

- There is transposition of the phrase (**Maruti Suzuki India has said**), from the end of the ST, to the beginning of TT, قالت ماروتي سوزوكي (الهند).

d\ **Punctuation:** both the ST and TT contain two commas and full stop in the end.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The structure of the TT is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

(c) Sentence (3):

1\ ST sentence: The firm has also decided to scale down production to single shift at some manufacturing lines in the plant.

2\ TT sentence: قررت الشركة أيضاً خفض الإنتاج إلى وردية واحدة في بعض خطوط التصنيع في المصنع.

Table (9)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	The firm الشركة	Has decided قررت	also أيضاً	0	0
	To scale down خفض	production الإنتاج	To إلى	0	0
	single واحدة	shift وردية	At في	0	0
	Some بعض	Manufacturing الإنتاج	Lines خطوط	0	0
	In في	The plant المصنع		0	0
Total	18			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (9):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (18) words, while the TT contains (15) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (5) (firm /production/shift/lines/plant).
- **Verbs:** there is (3) verb, (has/decided/scale down).
- **Adjectives:** (4) (also/single/some/manufacturing).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Conjunction:** (2), (the/the).
- **Prepositions:** (4), (to/at/in/to).
- **Additional words:** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted words.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The noun (**firm**) as (4) meanings, (شركة/مؤسسة/شركة تجارية/رأس), the machine picked the first equivalent (شركة), and the third meaning (شركة تجارية) is also correct.
- The rest of the machine selection are also correct.

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST sentence started with noun (**the firm**), while the TT sentence started with a verb (قررت).
- There is no significant change in the rest of the TT sentence.

b\ **Punctuation:** both, the ST and TT ended with full stop..

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT is grammatically correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

(d) Sentence (4):

1\ ST sentence: It will tentatively not carry out production on three Saturdays (August 7, 14 and 21).

2\ TT sentence: ولن تنفذ مبدئياً الإنتاج في ثلاثة أيام سبت (7 و14 و21 أغسطس).

Table (10)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	It	Will not	tentatively	0	it
	-	لن	مبدئياً		
	Carry out	production	on	0	0
	تنفذ	الإنتاج	في		
	three	Saturdays	August 7,14	0	0
	ثلاثة	أيام سبت	and 21 7 و14 و21 أغسطس		
Total	12			1	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (10):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (12) words, while the TT contains (12) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (7) (it/production/ Saturdays/three/August 7,14 and 21)).
- **Verbs:** (2) verb (will/carry out).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective
- **Adverbs:** (1), (tentatively/not).
- **Prepositions:** (1) , (on).
- **Conjunctions:** there is no conjunction.
- **Additional words:** there is no additional word.
- **Omitted words:** (1), (it).

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The adverb (**tentatively**) has (1) meaning (مؤقتاً), but in the context the machine gives another correct meaning, (مبدئياً).
- The machine translated the phrase (**on three Saturdays**) accurately, (في ثلاثة أيام سبت).

d\ **Word position:**

The ST sentence started with pronoun (**it**), followed by verb (**will**), then adverb (**tentatively**), while the TT sentence began with adverb (لن), followed by verb (تنفذ), then adverb (مبدئياً).

b\ **Punctuation:** The date (August 7,14 and 21) in both sentences between two brackets, and both sentences ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**.

4.1.2.4: Summary of Words Translation Accuracy of the Economic Text, Arabic into English:

This text consists of four sentences

Table (11)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	9	9	100	0	0
2	19	19	100	0	0
3	18	18	100	0	0
4	12	12	100	0	0
Total	58	58	100	0	0

Source: Researcher

Table (11) and chart (2) show the **accurate** and **inaccurate** words in text (2): the machine performance in this text is accurate, so the total accuracy rate is (100%).

Graph (2)

Source: Researcher

4.1.2.5: Sample Text (3): (Scientific), from English into Arabic

a\ Sentence (1):

1\ ST sentence: Maasai women in Kenya meet to discuss practice of FGM

2\ TT sentence: نساء الماساي في كينيا يجتمعن لمناقشة ممارسة تشويه الأعضاء التناسلية الأنثوية

Table (12)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
Maasai الماساي	women نساء	in في	0	Of	
Kenya كينيا	meet يجتمع/ن	To ل	0	0	
Discuss مناقشة	Practice ممارسة	Of -	0	0	
FGM تشويه الأعضاء التناسلية الأنثوية			0	0	
Total	10			0	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (12):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (9) words, while the TT contains (9) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (5), (Maasai/women/Kenya/practice/FGM)
- **Verbs:** (1), (meet/discuss).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (3) (to/ in/of).
- **Conjunction:** there is no conjunctions.
- **Additional words:** (1), (of).
- **Omitted words** there is no omitted words.

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine introduced one equivalent to the verb (**meet**), (**يجتمع**).
- The noun (**practice**) has (11) meanings, (**ممارسة/تدريب/عادة/مهنة/تمرين/خبرة/تقاليد**), (**مباشرة/من أن/التطبيق العملي**), and the machine selected (**ممارسة**), it is correct, but, (**عادة**) is the accurate selection.

- The acronym (FGM) translated correctly (تشويه الأعضاء التناسلية الأنثوية), and (ختان الإناث) in the next sentence.

c\ **Word position:**

The nominal clause (**Maasai women**), has different word order in the TT, (نساء الماساي).

d\ **Punctuation:** there is no punctuation marks because this is a headline.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

(b) **Sentence (2):**

1\ ST sentence: The practice of female genital mutilation (FGM), where women's genitals are altered or injured for non-medical reasons, is rife in parts of Africa.

2\ TT sentence: ممارسة تشويه الأعضاء التناسلية للإناث، حيث يتم تغيير أو إصابة الأعضاء التناسلية الأنثوية لأسباب غير طبية، منتشرة في أجزاء من إفريقيا.

Table (13)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	The practice ممارسة	of -	Female Genital Mutilation تشويه أعضاء التناسلية للإناث	0	Of
	where حيث	Women's الأنثوية	genitals الأعضاء التناسلية	0	0
	are altered يتم تغيير	or أو	injured إصابة	0	0
	For ل	Non-medical غير طبي	reasons أسباب	0	0
	Rife منتشر	In في	Parts of أجزاء من	0	0
	Africa أفريقيا			0	0
Total	19			0	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (13):

a\ **Words equivalent** The ST sentence contains (19) words, while the TT contains (19) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns** The ST contains (7), (practice/female genital mutilation/women/genitals/reasons/parts/Africa)
- **Verbs:** (3), (are/injured/alterd)
- **Adjective:** (2), (non-medical/rife).
- **Adverb** there is no adverbs.
- **Preposition:** (4), (of/for/in/of).
- **Conjunctions:** (3), (the/or/where).
- **Additional words** there is no additional words
- **Omitted Words.** (1), (of).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The acronym (**FGM**) translated to (تشويه الأعضاء التناسلية للإناث) and (ختان (الإناث)), but the machine drop the Arabic equivalent from the TT when the comma after the acronym is dropped.
- The contextual meaning of the noun (**mutilation**) is (تشويه), but as a single word the machine gives (3) meanings (بتر/إفساد/جدع).
- The verb (**alter**) has (7) meanings, (تغير/تبدل/عدل/قلب/حسن/عير أو زور/خصي), the first and the second verbs refer to the correct meaning.
- The verb (**injure**) has (6) meanings (جرح/ضرر/انجرح/آذى/أهان/نزل به ضرر) and translated to (أصاب), which is incorrect, it must be (جرح).

c\ **Word position:**

There is no change in the word order in the TT.

d\ **Punctuation:** both the ST and TT contain (2) commas and full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT structure is correct

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

(c) Sentence (3):

1\ ST sentence: Dangers include severe bleeding, problems urinating, infections, infertility and increased risk of newborn deaths in childbirth.

2\ TT sentence: تشمل المخاطر النزيف الحاد، ومشاكل التبول، والالتهابات، والعقم، وزيادة خطر وفيات الأطفال حديثي الولادة أثناء الولادة.

Table (14)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	dangers المخاطر	include تشمل	severe حاد	و (مشاكل)	of
	bleeding نزيف	problems مشاكل	urinating تبول	و(الالتهابات)	0
	infections التهابات	infertility العقم	and و	و(العقم)	0
	increased زيادة	risk خطر	of -	0	0
	newborn الأطفال حديثي الولادة	deaths وفيات	In childbirth أثناء الولادة	0	0
Total	16			3	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (14):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (16) words, while the TT contains (17) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (9)
(danger/bleeding/problems/urinating/infections/infertility/risk/deaths/chil
dbirth).
- **Verbs:** (1), (include).
- **Adjectives:** (3) (sever/increased/newborn).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Conjunction:** (1), (the).
- **Prepositions:** (2), (of/in).

- **Additional words:** (3), (و/و).
- **Omitted words:** (1), (of).

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine has different meaning to the noun (**infection**) and (**infections**) as plural, the first has (11) meanings (عدوى/إصابة/تلوث/تعفن) (عدوى/إصابة/تلوث/تعفن), but has only one meaning to the plural form (التهابات).
- The noun (**risk**) has (5) meanings (خطر/مخاطرة/مجازفة/مغامرة/عرضة للخطر), the machine selected the first meaning.
- The “**commas**” which separating the phrases (**severe bleeding, problems urinating, infections, infertility**), replaced by the conjunction (و).

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST sentence started with noun (**dangers**), while the TT sentence started with verb (تشمل).
- The word order in ST (**increased risk of newborn deaths in childbirth**) is different from the TT (زيادة خطر وفيات الأطفال حديثي الولادة أثناء الولادة), that adjective (**newborn**) precedes the noun (**deaths**) in the ST, but in the TT, the adjective comes next, (الأطفال حديثي الولادة).

b\ **Punctuation:** there are (3) commas in the ST used as conjunctions, but the TT sentence maintained the commas and used (و) as conjunctions. In addition, both sentences ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence structure is accurate, that the machine output shows no mistake.

Summary:

The meaning is clear, that the word selection of the MT, and structure is correct.

(d) Sentence (4):

1\ ST sentence: Despite these complications, cultural and religious beliefs mean millions of girls are still at risk of being mutilated.

2\ TT sentence على الرغم من هذه التعقيدات، فإن المعتقدات الثقافية والدينية تعني أن ملايين الفتيات ما زلن عرضة لخطر التشويه.

Table (15)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	despite على الرغم من	these هذه	complications التعقيدات	ما زلن (ن)	of
	cultural الثقافية	and و	religious الدينية	0	are
	beliefs المعتقدات	mean تعني	millions ملايين	0	Of being
	Of -	Girls الفتيات	Are -	0	0
	Still ما زلن	At risk عرضة للخطر	Of being -	0	0
	Mutilated التشويه			0	0
Total	16			1	3

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (15):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (12) words, while the TT contains (19) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (5) (these/complications/ belief/millions/ girls).
- **Verbs:** (2) verb (mean/are).
- **Adjectives:** (5) (cultural/religious/at risk/mutilated/of being).
- **Adverbs:** (1), (still).

- **Prepositions:** (2) , (despite/of).
- **Conjunctions:** (1),(and).
- **Additional words:** (1), (ن).
- **Omitted words:** (3), (of/are/of being).

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine has (4) meanings to the noun (**complications**), which are (مضاعفات/تعقيد/تعقد/المضاعفة), but in the context of this sentence it gives another equivalent (تعقيدات), and the accurate selection must be (مضاعفات).
- After the phrase (despite these complications), there is a comma, then followed by (**cultural and religious beliefs**), but in the TT the machine inserted the adverb (فإن) after the comma, this shows excellent performance of the machine in tis point.
- The machine translated the phrase (**being mutilated**), (**noun + adj.**) into the **infinitive** (التشويه), which reflect the core meaning of the ST.

d\ **Word position:**

- Both sentences begin with preposition (**despite**), and (على الرغم من).
- In the ST the adjectives (**cultural/religious**) precede the noun (**beliefs**), but in the TT, the noun follows the adjectives.

b\ **Punctuation:** both sentences contain a comma and full stop

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct,

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**.

(d) Sentence (5):

1\ ST sentence: Anne Soy reports from Kenya where there is a generational divide between proponents of FGM and those who want to abandon the tradition.

2\ TT sentence: تقرير أن صوي من كينيا حيث يوجد فجوة بين مؤيدي تشويه الأعضاء التناسلية الأنثوية وأولئك الذين يريدون التخلي عن هذا التقليد.

Table (16)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Anne Soy آن صوي	reports تقرير	from من	يريد(ون)	A
	Kenya كينيا	where حيث	There is يوجد	عن	Of
	A -	generational divide فجوة	Between بين	0	Want (to)
	Proponents مؤيدي	Of -	FGM تشويه الأعضاء التناسلية الأنثوية	0	0
	And و	Those أولئك	Who الذين	0	0
	Want to يريدون	Abandon التخلي عن	The tradition هذا التقليد	0	0
Total	21			2	3

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (16):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (21) words, while the TT contains (18) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (7) (Ann Soy/ Kenya/divide / FGM / those/who / tradition).
- **Verbs:** (3) verb (reports/want/abandon).
- **Adjectives:** (2) (generational/proponent).
- **Adverbs:** (1), (there is).
- **Prepositions:** (4), (between/of/to/from).
- **Conjunctions:** (4), (A/where/and/the).
- **Additional words:** (2), (و/عن).
- **Omitted words:** (3), (a/of/to).

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The word (**report**), classified by the machine as noun (تقرير), but it is a (**verb**), I.e. (**send a report**).
- The phrase (**generational divide**) translated into (فجوة), and accurate is (انقسام أجيال/قائم على الفوارق العمرية).
- The rest of the machine selection in this sentence is correct.

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST begins with noun (**Anne Soy**), while the TT begins with verb (**report**).

b\ **Punctuation:** both sentences, ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct,

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**.

4. 2.6: Summary of Words Translation Accuracy of the Scientific Text, English into Arabic:

This text consists of five sentences

Table (17)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	10	11	100	0	0
2	19	18	94.7	1	5.6
3	16	16	100	0	0
4	16	15	93.7	1	6.3
5	21	20	95.2	1	4.8
Total	82	79	96.4	3	3.6

Source: Researcher

Table (17) and chart (3) show the **accurate** and **inaccurate** words in text (3): In sentence (2) the equivalent of the verb (**injure**) is (جرح), but the machine selected incorrect meaning (أصاب), the accuracy rate is (94.7%).

In sentence (4) the noun (**complications**) translated into (تعقيدات) but the correct equivalent meaning is (مضاعفات), the accuracy rate is (93.7%).

In sentence (5) the pronoun (**this**), translated into (ذلك), but the correct equivalent is (هذا), the accuracy rate is (95.2%).

The total accuracy rate of this text is (96.4%).

Graph (3)

Source: Researcher

4.2.7: Sample Text (4): (culture and Art), English into Arabic.

a\ Sentence (1):

1\ ST sentence: Japanese Princess to give up royal title, 150 million yen to marry
commoner: Reports

2\ TT sentence: الأميرة اليابانية تتخلى عن اللقب الملكي، 150-مليون ين للزواج من عامة الشعب: تقارير

Table (18)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Japanese اليابانية	Princess الأميرة	To give up تتخلى عن	0	0
	royal الملكى	title اللقب	150 million yen 150 مليون ين	0	0
	to marry للزواج	Commoner من عامة الشعب	Reports تقارير	0	0
Total	11			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (18):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (11) words, while the TT contains (12) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (6), (Japanese/princess/title/150 million yen /commoner/ reports)
- **Verbs:** (2), (give up/ marry).
- **Adjectives:** (1), (royal).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (2), (to/to).
- **Conjunction:** there is no conjunctions.
- **Additional words** there is no additional words.

- **Omitted words** there is no omitted words.

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The noun (**commoner**) has (5) equivalents (عامة الناس/من عامة الشعب/شخص (عامي سوقي/طالب في جامعة/عضو في مجلس العموم), the machine selected the second meaning.
- The noun (**reports**) translated correctly, but its position inside the TT is not accurate, it must be (تقارير: الأميرة اليابانية تتخلى عن اللقب الملكي، 150 مليون ين للزواج) (من عامة الشعب تقول تقارير: الأميرة اليابانية تتخلى عن) (اللقب الملكي، 150 مليون ين للزواج من عامة الشعب).

c\ **Word position:** The position of the noun (تقارير) must be in beginning of the TT sentence.

d\ **Punctuation:** Both, ST and TT sentences contain colon and comma.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The machine output (TT) is correct, that there is no mistake in the structure, it is clear, simple and correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear, because the meaning of the TT, and structure (grammar) look clear.

(b) Sentence (2):

1\ ST sentence: Japan's Princess Mako is reportedly set to forego a one-off payment of 150 million yen (\$1.35 million) for giving up her royal status to marry a commoner whom she met during her college years.

2\ TT sentence: يقال إن الأميرة اليابانية ماكو ستتخلى عن دفعة لمرة واحدة قدرها 150-مليون ين (1.35 مليون دولار) لتخليها عن وضعها الملكي للزواج من شخص من عامة الشعب التقت به خلال سنوات دراستها الجامعية.

Table (19)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Japan's اليابانية	Princess الأميرة	Mako ماكو	تخلي/ها	A (one-off)
	Is reportedly يقال إن	Set to سوف	forego تتخلى عن	دراسة/ها	0
	A one-off لمرة واحدة	payment دفعة	of -	0	0
	150 million yen 150 مليون ين	(\$1.35 million) (1.35 مليون دولار)	for ل	0	0
	Giving up تخليها	her royal status لقبها الملكي	To marry للزواج	0	0
	A commoner من عامة الشعب	Whom she met التقت به	During خلال	0	0
	her college years سنوات دراستها الجامعية			0	0
Total	29			2	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (19):

a\ **Words equivalent** The ST sentence contains (29) words, while the TT contains (33) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns** The ST contains (14), (Japan's/princess/Mako/ payment/150 million yen/\$1.35 million/her/ status/commoner/ whom/ she/her/college/years)
- **Verbs:** (6), (is/set to/forego/giving up/marry/met)
- **Adjective :**(2), (royal/one-off).
- **Adverb** (1), (reportedly).
- **Preposition:** (4), (of/for/to/during).
- **Conjunctions:** (2), (a/a).
- **Additional words** (1), (ها/دراسة).
- **Omitted Words** (1), (a).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The verb (**set to**) has (5) meanings (ضبط ل/تشاجر/بدأ العمل بنشاط/بدأ بهمة/بدأ) (بنشاط أعدت (العدة للتخلي عن دفعة لمرة واحدة قدرها).
- The verb (**forego**) has (3) meanings (سبق/أضاع فرصة/امتنع عن), but these equivalents do not give the accurate meaning as single words, the accurate meaning introduced by machine in the context (تخلي عن).
- There is only one meaning of the adjective (**one-off**) , which is (لمرة واحدة).
- The noun (**status**) has (12) meanings, (حالة/وضع/مكانة/منزلة/مرتبة/) (مقام/وضع قانوني/اعتبار/هيبة/وضع حالة/تشريع/وضع شرعي), but the machine gave another correct equivalent meaning, (**title**), but some of this list is correct or accurate (حالة/وضع/مكانة/منزلة/مرتبة/مقام).

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST starts with a noun (**Japan's Princess**), while the TT starts with a verb (يقال).

d\ **Punctuation:** both the ST and TT ended with comma.

e / Grammatical Accuracy:

The grammatical structure is correct. Poor style of the St Sentence produces a poor

Summary:

The meaning is clear, but the accurate translation of (Japan's Princess Mako is reportedly set to forego a one-off payment of 150 million yen (\$1.35 million) for giving up her royal status to marry a commoner) is (يقال إن الأميرة اليابانية ماکو ستتخلى عن مبلغ قدره) 150 مليون ين (1.35 مليون دولار) ، في دفعة واحدة مقابل تخليها عن وضعها الملكي للزواج من شخص من عامة الشعب).

(c) Sentence (3):

1\ ST sentence: This comes amid public criticism over her former college classmate and fiance Kei Komuro.

2\ TT sentence: يأتي ذلك وسط انتقادات علنية لزميلتها وخطيبها السابق في الكلية كي كومورو.

Table (20)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	This ذلك	comes يأتي	amid وسط	0	0
	public علنية	criticism انتقادات	over ل	0	0
	Her classmate لزميلتها/ها	Former السابق	And و	0	0
	fiance خطيب/ها	Kei Komuro بعض		0	0
Total	12			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (20):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (12) words, while the TT contains (14) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (6) (this /criticism/her/ classmate/ fiance/ Kei Komuro).
- **Verbs:** there is (1) verb, (come).

- **Adjectives:** (2) (public/former).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Conjunction:** (1), (and).
- **Prepositions:** (2), (amid/over).
- **Additional words** there are no additional words.
- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted words.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The equivalents of the preposition (**this**) is (هذه/هذا/هؤلاء/هو/هن), and the machine introduced another meaning (ذلك), which is inaccurate, it must be (هذا).
- The adjective (**public**) has (7) equivalents (عام /عمومي/ علني/شعبي/شهير (/شائع/اجتماعي), the machine selected the third one.
- The preposition (**over**) has (8) meanings (خلال /فوق /حتى/عن ((طريق/بالقرب/على الجانب الآخر من/على طول كذا / إلى جانبه), and the machine introduced accurate meaning out of this list (**to**), or (ل), but there is another accurate meaning, which is (بشأن).
- The phrase (**her classmate and fiancé**), translated into (زميلتها وخطيبها), which incorrect, that her classmate is male (**Kei Komuro**), not female, the correct meaning is (زميلها وخطيبها).

d\ **Word position:** The ST begins with preposition (**this**) , while the TT begins with verb (يأتي).

b\ **Punctuation:** both, the ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The structure is correct

Summary:

The meaning of the final parts of the sentence is inaccurate (**her classmate and fiance**), (زميلتها وخطيبها).

(d) Sentence (4):

1\ ST sentence: The 29-year-old granddaughter of then-Emperor Akihito had announced her engagement in 2017.

2\ TT sentence: أعلنت حفيدة الإمبراطور أكيهيتو البالغة من العمر 29- عامًا خطوبتها في عام 2017.

Table (21)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	The 29- years-old البالغة من العمر	granddaughter حفيدة	of -	0	of
	then -	Emperor الإمبراطور	Akihito أكيهيتو	0	then
	had announced أعلنت	Her engagement خطوبتها	In 2017 في عام 2017	0	0
Total	12			0	2

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (21):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (12) words, while the TT contains (12) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (5) (granddaughter/Emperor/Akihito/her/engagement)).
- **Verbs:** (2) verb (had/announced).
- **Adjectives:** (2) (29-years-old/then).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (2), (of/in).
- **Conjunctions:** (1), (the).
- **Additional words:** there is no additional word.

- **Omitted words:** (2), (of/then).

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The equivalent of the adjective (**then**) is (قائم آنذاك), which is incorrect, the accurate equivalent is (**ex-**, or **former**), (السابق), but the machine dropped it from the TT.

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST started with the adjective (**the 29-years-old**), while the TT started with the verb (**announced**).

b\ **Punctuation:** both sentences, ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct,

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**.

4.2.8: Summary of Words Translation Accuracy of the Culture and Art Text, English into Arabic;

This text consists of four sentences

Table (22)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	11	10	90.9	1	9.1
2	29	28	96.5	1	3.5
3	12	10	83.3	2	16.7
4	12	12	100	0	0
Total	64	60	93.7	4	6.3

Source: Researcher

Table (17) and chart (4) show the **accurate** and **inaccurate** words in text (4):

In Sentence (1), the noun (**reports**) placed in the end of the sentence, it should be in the beginning, so the sentence accuracy rate is (**90.9%**).

In sentence (2), The machine translated the verb (**set to**) into (ستتخلى), but it would be accurate (أعدت/أعدت العدة), the sentence accuracy rate is(**96.5%**).

In sentence (3) the machine translated the preposition (**this**) into (ذلك), and the accurate equivalent is (هذا).

Also in sentence (3) the machine considered the princess fiancé (**Kei Komuro**) as female, according to the output (يأتي ذلك وسط انتقادات علنية لزميلتها وخطيبها السابق) (في الكلية كي كومورو), so, the sentence accuracy rate is (**83.3%**).

The text total accuracy is (**93.7%**).

Graph (4)

Source: Researcher

4.2.9: Sample Text (5): (sports), English into Arabic

a\ Sentence (1):

1\ ST sentence: Aubameyang scores as Barca win at Real Sociedad

2\ TT sentence: أوباميانج يسجل في فوز برشلونة على ريال سوسيداد

Table (23)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Aubameyang أوباميانج	scores يسجل	as في	0	0
	Barca برشلونة	win فوز	at على	0	0
	Real Sociedad ريال سوسيداد			0	0
Total	7			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (23):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (7) words, while the TT contains (7) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (3), (Aubameyang/Barca/Real Sociedad)
- **Verbs:** (2), (scores/win).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** (1), (as).
- **Prepositions:** (1) (at).
- **Conjunction:** there is no conjunction.
- **Additional words** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words** there is no omitted words.

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The word (**as**) here can be classified as (**pronoun, conjunction, adverb or preposition**), the machine considered it as preposition (**في**).
- The rest of the word's equivalent are correct.

c\ **Word position:**

- All words in the TT sentence in the same position.

d\ **Punctuation:** There punctuation mark in this sentence.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

(b) Sentence (2):

1\ ST sentence: Pierre-Emerick Aubameyang's ninth goal in 11 La Liga appearances helped earn Barcelona a win at Real Sociedad that lifted them to second in the table.

2\ TT sentence: ساعد الهدف التاسع لبيير إيمريك أوباميانج في 11-مباراة بالدوري الإسباني على فوز برشلونة على ريال سوسيداد الذي رفعه إلى المركز الثاني في جدول الترتيب.

Table (24)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Pierre-Emerick Aubameyang's بيير إيمريك أوباميانج	ninth التاسع	goal الهدف	0	earn
	In 11 La Liga appearances في 11 مباراة بالدوري الإسباني	helped ساعد على	earn -	0	that
	Barcelona برشلونة	A win فوز	At Real Sociedad على ريال سوسيداد	0	0
	that -	lifted رفع	them هـ	0	0
	To second للمركز الثاني	In the table في جدول الترتيب		0	0
Total	22			0	2

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (24):

a\ **Words equivalent:** the ST sentence contains (22) words, while the TT contains (23) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns** The ST contains (10) Pierre-Emerick Aubameyang/ goal/La Liga/11 appearance/Barcelona/win/Real Sociedad/ that/them/ table).
- **Verbs:** (3), (helped/earn/lifted)
- **Adjective :** (2), (ninth/second).
- **Adverb** (1), (what).
- **Preposition:** (4), (in/at/to/in).
- **Conjunctions:** (2), (a/the).
- **Additional words:** there is no additional word.
- **Omitted Words** (2), (earn/that).

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The noun (appearance) has (5) equivalent meanings, (مظهر/ظهور/ مظهر خارجي /مثول/هيئة), it can be (ظهور), but is not accurate; the contextual meaning here is (مباراة).
- The phrase (**Pierre-Emerick Aubameyang's ninth goal in 11 La Liga appearances helped earn Barcelona a win**), translated into (ساعد الهدف (التاسع لبيير إيمريك أوباميانج في 11 مباراة بالدوري الإسباني على فوز برشلونة)), the verb (**earn**) is additional word, and can be dropped, the meaning (ساعد (الهدف).... برشلونة على كسب فوز), it is correct but weak.
- The noun (**table**), translated into (جدول الترتيب), which is accurate meaning.

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST started with the noun (**Pierre-Emerick Aubameyang**), while the TT started with verb (ساعد).
- The rest of TT words position is not different from the ST.

d\ **Punctuation:** both the ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The grammatical structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

(c) Sentence (3):

1\ ST sentence: The ex-Arsenal forward scored with a close-range header after a cross by ex-Manchester City player Ferran Torres.

2\ TT sentence: سجل مهاجم أرسنال السابق بضربة رأس من مدى قريب بعد عرضية من لاعب مانشستر سيتي السابق فيران توريس.

Table (25)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	The ex-Arsenal forward مهاجم أرسنال السابق	scored سجل	With a close-range header بضربة رأس من مدى قريب	0	0
	after بعد	A cross عرضية	by من	0	0
	Ex-Manchester City player لاعب مانشستر سيتي السابق	Ferran Torres فيران توريس		0	0
Total	17			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (25):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (17) words, while the TT contains (16) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (6) (Arsenal/header/cross/Manchester City/ferran Torres).

- **Verbs** :(1) verb, (scored).
- **Adjectives:** (4) (forward/close-range/ex/ex).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Conjunction:** (3), (a/a/the).
- **Prepositions:** (3), (with/after/by).
- **An additional word there is** no additional words.
- **Omitted words:** there are no omitted words.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The equivalent of the phrase (**The ex-Arsenal forward**), is (مهاجم أرسنال السابق) is accurate.
- The machine translated the adjective (**a close-range header**) into (ضربة رأس) (من مدى قريب) is accurately.

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST started with noun (the ex-Arsenal), while the TT begins with verb (سجل).
- The rest of the TT words have the same ST words position.

b\ **Punctuation:** both, the ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is **clear**.

(d) Sentence (4):

1\ ST sentence: Shortly before Aubameyang's goal, Ousmane Dembele's shot came back off the post.

2\ TT sentence: قبل وقت قصير من هدف أوباميانغ ، ارتدت تسديدة عثمان ديمبيلي من القائم.

Table (26)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	shortly وقت قصير	before قبل	Aubameyang أوباميانغ	من	0
	goal هدف	Ousmane Dembele عثمان ديمبيلي	shot تسديدة	0	0
	Came back Off ارتد من	the post القائم		0	0
Total	10			1	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (26):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (10) words, while the TT contains (11) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (5) (Aubameyang/goal/Ousmane Dembele/shot/post)
- **Verbs:** (2), (came/ back off).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** (1), (shortly).
- **Prepositions:** (1),(before).
- **Conjunctions:** (1), (the).
- **Additional words:** (1), (من).
- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted word.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine has (5) equivalents to the adverb (**shortly**), which are (قريباً/باختصار/حالة/بخشونة/بفضاعة), the machine selected the first one.
- The equivalent of the verb (**back off**) is (تراجع), which is correct.
- The machine selections seem to be correct in the entire target sentence.

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST began with adverb (**shortly**), while the TT, started with preposition (قبل).
- The noun phrases (**Aubameyang's goal**), and (**Ousmane Dembele's shot**), the proper noun (**Aubameyang** and **Ousmane Dembele**) precedes the noun goal and shots, in ST, but in the TT, they came after it.

b\ **Punctuation:** both sentences, ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct,

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**.

(d) Sentence (5):

1\ ST sentence: Aubameyang, 32, joined Barca on a free transfer in February after not playing for Arsenal following a disciplinary breach in December. Only Memphis Depay has scored more goals in La Liga for Barca this season.

2\ TT sentence: وانضم أوباميانج ، 32 عامًا ، إلى برشلونة في صفقة انتقال مجانية في فبراير بعد عدم اللعب مع أرسنال بعد مخالفة تأديبية في ديسمبر. فقط ممفيس ديباي سجل المزيد من الأهداف في الدوري الإسباني لبرشلونة هذا الموسم.

Table (27)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Aubameyang أوباميانج	32 32 عاماً	joined انضم لـ	0	0
	Barca برشلونة	On a free transfer في صفقة انتقال مجانية	In February في فبراير	0	0
	after بعد	Not playing عدم اللعب	For Arsenal مع أرسنال	0	0
	following بعد	A disciplinary breach مخالفة تأديبية	In December في ديسمبر	0	0
	only فقط	Memphis Depay ممفيس ديباي	Has scored سجل	0	0
	More goals المزيد من الأهداف	In La Liga في الدوري الإسباني	For Barca this season لبرشلونة هذا الموسم	0	0
Total		32		0	1

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (27):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (32) words, while the TT contains (33) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (15)
- (Aubameyang/32/Barca/transfer/February/playing/Arsenal/breach/December/Memphis Debay/goals/La Lega/Barca/this/season).
- **Verbs:** (3), (joined/has/scored).
- **Adjectives:** (4) (free/following/disciplinary/more).
- **Adverbs:** (2), (not/only).
- **Prepositions:** (7), (on/in/in/in/for/for/after).
- **Conjunctions:** (1), (a).
- **Additional words:** there is no additional word.
- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted word.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The equivalent of the phrase (**free transfer**) is (صفقة انتقال مجانية), it can mean also (صفقة انتقال حر), this expression widely used in the sports language.
- The meanings of adjective (**following**) are (6), (التالي /بعد/وراء/ الآتي/تابع) , (/لاحق) but can be accurate if translated into (بسبب).
- The noun (breach) has (8) equivalents (خرق/مخالفة/فتحة/ثغرة في) (القانون/صداقة/فجوة/انقطاع في العلاقات الودية/وثبة الحوت في الماء). The machine picked the second.
- The preposition in the phrase (not playing **for**), use to mean (**with**), (مع).

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST starts with the noun (**Aubameyang**), while the TT starts with verb (انضم).
- There is no change in the word position of the rest of the TT.

b\ **Punctuation:** both sentences contain comma after (**32**) and full stop after (**December**), besides full stop in the end.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct,

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**.

(e) Sentence (6):

1\ ST sentence: Barca's win lifts them into second spot on 63 points - 15 behind runaway leaders Real Madrid.

2\ TT sentence: ورفع فوز برشلونة للمركز الثاني برصيد 63 نقطة - بفارق 15-نقطة عن ريال مدريد المتصدر.

Table (28)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Barca برشلونة	win فوز	lift رفع	و	0
	them هـ	Into second spot للمركز الثاني	On 63 points برصيد 63 نقطة	نقطة	0
	15 behind بفارق 15 نقطة	runaway leaders المتصدر	Real Madrid ريال مدريد	رصيد	0
Total	13			3	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (28):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (13) words, while the TT contains (14) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (7) (Barca/win/ them/spot /63 points/15/Real Madrid).
- **Verbs:** (1), (lift).
- **Adjectives :**(2),(runaway leaders/second).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (3) , (on/into/behind).
- **Conjunctions:** there is no conjunction.
- **Additional words:** (3), (و/نقطة/رصيد).

- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted word.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The pronoun (**them**) refers to the team members.
- The word (**win**) rarely used as a noun, the alternative meaning is (**victory**), but not commonly used in sports language.
- The noun (**spot**) has (12) meanings (بقعة/نقطة/مكان/موقع/موضع/مركز/محل) (/إعلان/ضوء كشاف/مقدار قليل/ارتباك), the machine picked the sixth one.
- The machine translated the phrase (**on 63 points**) into (برصيد 63 نقطة).
- The phrase (**15 behind**) means (**15 points behind**), and here means (بفارق 15 نقطة).
- The literal meaning of (**runaway leaders**), out of the context, is (قيادة هاربين), but the machine selected the accurate meaning (المتصدر).

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST begins with noun (**Barca**), and the TT begins with verb (رفع).
- The adjective (runaway leaders) in the ST comes before the noun (Real Madrid), while in the TT comes after.

b\ **Punctuation:** both sentences, ST and TT contains hyphen, and ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct.

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**, but there may be more lucidity if the TT begins as following (ورفع هذا الفوز برشلونة للمركز).

(e) Sentence (7):

1\ ST sentence: Real Sociedad remain sixth in the table - six points off a Champions League spot with five games left.

2\ TT sentence: حافظ ريال سوسيداد على المركز السادس في الترتيب بفارق ست نقاط عن مكانه في دوري أبطال أوروبا قبل خمس مباريات على النهاية.

Table (29)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Real Sociedad ريال سوسيداد	remain حافظ	Sixth In the table السادس في المركز الترتيب	المركز	0
	Six points off بفارق ست نقاط عن	A Champions League spot مكانه في دوري أبطال أوروبا	with قبل	0	0
	Five games خمس مباريات	left قبل	-	0	0
Total	16			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (29):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (16) words, while the TT contains (17) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (8) (Real Sociedad /table/six/points/Champions League/spot/five/games).
- **Verbs:** (2) (remain/left).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** (1), (sixth).

- **Prepositions:** (3), (in/off/with).
- **Conjunctions:** (2), (a/the).
- **Additional words:** there is no additional word.
- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted word.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The verb (**remain**) has (3) equivalents (بقي/ظل/مكث), and the machine selected the correct word (حافظ على), but it can be accurate by selecting (بقي في أو ظل في).
- In the phrase (**six points off a Champions League spot**), the machine equivalent meaning (المركز السادس في الترتيب بفارق ست نقاط عن مكانه في دوري (أبطال أوروبا) is correct, but it would be accurate to say (المركز السادس في (الترتيب بفارق ست نقاط عن الترتيب الذي يؤهله لدوري أبطال أوروبا).
- The adverb (**off**) has (2) equivalents (بعيداً/جانباً) and the machine selected another accurate alternative (بفارق).

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST begins with noun (**Real Sociedad**), while the TT begins with verb (بقي).

b\ **Punctuation:** both sentences, ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence is grammatically correct,

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**.

4.2.10: Summary of Words Translation Accuracy of sports Text, (English into Arabic):

This text consists of seven sentences

Table (30)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	7	7	100	0	0
2	22	21	95.4	1	5.6
3	17	17	100	0	0
4	10	10	100	0	0
5	32	31	96.8	1	3.2
6	13	13	100	0	0
7	16	15	93.7	1	6.3
Total	117	114	97.4	3	2.6

Source: Researcher

Table (30) and chart (5) show the **accurate** and **inaccurate** words in text (5):

In sentence (1) the verb (earn) is a spurious, or no need to it in this phrase (helped **earn** Barcelona a win), the output could be accurate as following (ساعد برشلونة على الفوز), the sentence accuracy rate is (95.4%).

In sentence (5) the accurate equivalent of the adjective (**following**) if translated into (بسبب), not (بعد), the sentence accuracy rate is (96.8%).

In sentence (7), the equivalent of the phrase (**six points off a Champions League spot**) would be accurate if translated to (المركز السادس في الترتيب بفارق ست نقاط عن الترتيب الذي يؤهل دوري أبطال أوروبا), the sentence accuracy rate is (93.7%).

The total accuracy of the text is (97.4%).

Graph (5)

Source: Researcher

4.2.11: Sample Text (6): (legal), (English into Arabic)

a\ Sentence (1):

1\ ST sentence: Princess Beatrice 'wedding gift' claim in court case

2\ TT sentence: مطالبة الأميرة بياتريس بـ "هدية زفاف" في قضية قضائية:

Table (31)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Princess الأميرة	Beatrice بياتريس	Wedding زفاف	0	0
	gift هدية	claim مطالبة	in في	0	0
	court قضائية	case قضية		0	0
Total	8			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (31):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (8) words, while the TT contains (8) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (7), (Princess/Beatrice/wedding/gift/claim/court/case)
- **Verbs:** there is no verb.
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (1) (in).
- **Conjunction:** there is no conjunctions.
- **Additional words** there is no additional words.
- **Omitted words** there is no omitted words.

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The machine has (6) equivalents to the noun (**gift**), (هدية/هبة/عطية/موهبة/عطاء), (منحة/إنعام), the machine selected the first one.
- The noun (**court**) has (11) equivalent meanings (محكمة/ملعب/بلاط/جلسة/فناء/محكمة (الاستئناف/تملق/بلاط الملك/اجتماع رسمي/استقبال بقيمة الملك/مبنى كبير introduced another meaning (قضائي), which is correct.

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST started with the proper noun (**Princess Beatrice**), while the TT started with the noun (مطالبة)

d\ **Punctuation:** in both sentences the phrase (**wedding gift**), (هدية زفاف) between quotation mark (in the ST) and double quotation mark (in the TT).

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT sentence structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

(b) Sentence (2):

1\ ST sentence: Nehebat Isbilenn is claiming at the High Court in London that her business adviser Selman Turk "dishonestly misappropriated" £38m of her assets.

2\ TT sentence: تدعي نيهابات إسبيلين أمام المحكمة العليا في لندن أن مستشارها التجاري سلمان ترك "اختلف بطريقة غير شريفة" 38 مليون جنيه إسترليني من أصولها.

Table (32)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Nehebat Isbilienn نيهابات إسبيلين	is claiming تدعي	at أمام	0	0
	The High Court المحكمة العليا	in في	London لندن	0	0
	that أن	her business adviser مستشارها التجاري	Selman Turk سلمان ترك	0	0
	dishonestly بطريقة غير شريفة	misappropriate اختلف	£38m 38 مليون جنيه استرليني	0	0
	of من	her assets أصولها		0	0
Total	19			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (32):

a\ **Words equivalent** The ST sentence contains (19) words, while the TT contains (21) words, classified below:

- **Nouns/pronouns** The ST contains (11) Nehabat Isbilienn/high Court/activity/London/business/adviser/her/Selman Turk/£38m/her/ Assets)
- **Verbs:** (2), (is/claiming/misappropriate)
- **Adjective:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverb** (1), (dishonestly).
- **Preposition:** (3), (at/in/ of).

- **Conjunctions:** (2), (that/the).
- **Additional words:** there is no additional word.
- **Omitted Words** there is no omitted words.

b\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The preposition in the phrase (claiming **at** court) out of the context (يدعي في), while it is meaning in the context is (يدعي أمام المحكمة).
- The adverb (**dishonestly**) translated into (غير شريف), while the machine equivalent meaning is (بطريقة غير شريفة), which represents the contextual meaning.
- The rest of the machine performance is also correct in the rest of the sentence.

c\ **Word position:**

- The ST sentences begins with the noun (**Nehebat Isbilenn**), while the TT starts with the verb (تدعي).
- The rest of the word's position is correct.

d\ **Punctuation:** the ST and TT contain the phrases "dishonestly misappropriated" and its equivalent "اختلس بطريقة غير شريفة", between double quotation mark. Also, both ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

the TT sentence structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

(c) Sentence (3):

1\ ST sentence: Mrs. Isbilen paid £750,000 to Prince Andrew and claims Mr. Turk had wrongly told her bank it was a wedding gift.

2\ TT sentence: دفعت السيدة إسبيلين 750 ألف جنيه إسترليني للأمير أندرو وتزعم أن السيد ترك أخبر بنكها بالخطأ أنها هدية زفاف.

Table (33)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Mrs. Isbilen السيدة إسبيلين	paid دفعت	£750,000 750 ألف جنيه إسترليني	دفع(ت)	0
	to ل	Prince الأمير	Andrew اندرو	0	0
	and و	claims تزعّم	Mr. Turk السيد ترك	0	0
	had أن	wrongly بالخطأ	Told أخبر	0	0
	her bank بنكها	It was أنها	A wedding زفاف	0	0
	Gift هدية			0	0
Total	19			1	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (33):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (19) words, while the TT contains (19) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (10) (Mrs. Isiblen /£750,000/Prince/Andrew/Mr Turk/her/bank/it/wedding/gift).
- **Verbs:** there is (5) verb, (paid/claim/had/told/was).

- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective
- **Adverbs:** (1), (wrongly).
- **Conjunction:** (2), (and/a).
- **Prepositions:** (1), (to).
- **Additional words**(1), (ت).
- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted words.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The verb (**claim**) has (4) meaning (تطلب/دعا/طاقي/استحق), the machine introduced another correct meaning (تزعّم), but the accurate meaning is (ادعى).
- The machine selections in the rest of the sentence are correct.

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST started with the noun (**Mrs. Isbilen**), while the TT started with the verb (دفعت).
- The rest of the word's places in the TT similar to the ST.

b\ **Punctuation:** both, the ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The grammatical structure is correct.

Summary:

The meaning is clear.

(d) Sentence (4):

1\ ST sentence: There is no suggestion of wrongdoing by Princess Beatrice or Prince Andrew.

2\ TT sentence: ليس هناك ما يشير إلى ارتكاب مخالفات من قبل الأميرة بياتريس أو الأمير أندرو.

Table (34)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	There is هناك	no ليس	suggestion ما يشير	0	0
	of على	wrongdoing ارتكاب مخالفة	by من قبل	0	0
	Princess الأميرة	Beatrice بياتريس	or أو	0	0
	Prince الأمير	Andrew أندرو		0	0
Total	11			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (34):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (11) words, while the TT contains (14) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (6)
(suggestion/wrongdoing/Princess/Beatrice/Prince/Andrew).
- **Verbs:** there is no verb.
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** (2), (there is/no).
- **Prepositions:** (2), (by/of).
- **Conjunctions:** (1), (or).
- **Additional words:** there is no additional word.

- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted word.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- The noun (**suggestion**) has (5) meanings (اقتراح/مقترح/إيحاء/تلميح/مسحة), but the machine introduced the phrase (ما يشير), which is accurate.

- The noun (wrongdoing) had only one meaning (آثام), while the contextual meaning here by the machine (مخالفات) is correct.

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST begins with the adverb (**there is**), while the TT starts with the adverb (ليس).

b\ **Punctuation:** both sentences, ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:**

The TT structure is correct,

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**.

(e) Sentence (5):

1\ ST sentence: The Duke of York has now returned the £750,000 to Mrs. Isbilen.

2\ TT sentence: أعدد دوق يورك الآن 750.000 جنيه إسترليني للسيدة إسبيلين.

Table (35)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	The Duke of York دوق يورك	has now returned أعاد الآن	The £750,000 750.000 جنيه إسترليني	0	0
	To ل	Mrs. Isbilen السيدة إسبيلين		0	0
Total	11			0	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (35):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (11) words, while the TT contains (7) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (4) (Duke/York/ £750,000/Mrs. Isbilen).
- **Verbs:** (2) verb (has/returned).
- **Adjectives:** there is no adjective.
- **Adverbs:** (1), (now).
- **Prepositions:** (2), (of/to).
- **Conjunctions:** (2), (the/the).
- **Additional words:** there is no additional word.
- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted word.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- All of the selections made by the machine in this sentence is accurate.

d\ **Word position:**

- The ST begins with the noun (**Duke of York**), and TT starts with the verb (أعاد).

b\ **Punctuation:** both sentences, ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:** The TT sentence is grammatically correct,

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**.

(f) Sentence (6):

1\ ST sentence: Mr. Turk has rejected the allegations made against him.

2\ TT sentence: وكان السيد ترك قد رفض المزاعم التي وجهت ضده.

Table (36)

Item	Word and its equivalent			Additional Words	Omitted Words
				Freq.	Freq.
	Mr. Turk السيد ترك	Has rejected كان قد رفض	The allegation المزاعم	و/ قد	0
	made التي وجهت	against him ضده		التي	0
Total	8			2	0

Source: Researcher

Structuring: from table (36):

a\ **Words equivalent:** The ST sentence contains (12) words, while the TT contains (10) words.

- **Nouns/pronouns:** (3) (Mr. Turk/allegation/him).
- **Verbs:** (2) verb (has/rejected/made).
- **Adjectives:** (1) (tentatively).
- **Adverbs:** there is no adverb.
- **Prepositions:** (1), (against).
- **Conjunctions:** (1), (the).
- **Additional words:** (3), (و/قد/التي).
- **Omitted words:** there is no omitted word.

c\ **Lexical word selection:**

- All of the selections made by the machine is correct in this sentence, but there is something unworthy along the sentence, that the machine

mistranslated the title (**Mrs. And Mr.**), and mentioned it as following (**Mrs and Mr**).

d\ **Word position:**

- The St begins with the noun (**Mr. Turk**), while the TT starts with the verb (كان).

b\ **Punctuation:** both sentences, ST and TT ended with full stop.

e / **Grammatical Accuracy:** The structure of the TT is correct,

Summary:

The meaning of the TT is **clear**.

4.1.2.12: Summary of Words Translation Accuracy of Legal Text, (English into Arabic):

This text consists of six sentences

Table (37)

sentence	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	8	8	100	0	0
2	19	19	100	0	0
3	19	18	94.7	1	5.3
4	11	11	100	0	0
5	11	11	100	0	0
6	8	8	100	0	0
Total	76	75	98.6	1	1.4

Source: Researcher

Table (37) and chart (6) show the **accurate** and **inaccurate** words in text (6):

In sentence (3), the machine translated the verb (**claim**) to (تزعّم), but the accurate meaning is (ادعى), which is in the legal language, the sentence accuracy rate is (**94.7%**).

The total accuracy rate of the text is (98.6%).

Graph (6)

Source: Researcher

4.2.13: Total statistics of Words Translation Accuracy English into Arabic:

Table (40)

text	Total words	accurate		Inaccurate	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	68	61	89.8	7	10.2
2	58	58	100	0	0
3	82	79	96.4	3	3.6
4	64	60	93.7	4	6.3
5	117	114	97.4	3	2.6
6	76	75	98.6	1	1.4
Total	465	447	96.1	18	3.9

Source: Researcher

Table (40) and chart (7) show total translation accuracy rates of part (2) (English into Arabic). In text (1)/ **Political**, the accuracy is (**89.8%**), while text (2) / **Economic**, the machine accuracy represents (**100%**), and text (3)/ **Culture and Art**, (**96.4%**), in text (4) the accuracy rate is (**93.8%**), but the machine performance is perfect in text (5)/ **Sports**, (**93.7%**). While in text (6/ **Legal**, the rate went down to (**98.6%**).

The total translation accuracy rate of this section (Arabic into English) is (**96.1%**).

Graph (7)

Source: Researcher

4.2.14: Statistical Comparison between the two parts (Arabic – English and English – Arabic):

Reviewing the machine performance in parts one and two (Arabic to English) and (English to Arabic), is an important comparison as far as the research needs:

- 1- The machine accuracy in the **political text** (Arabic to English) is **(97.6%)**, while (English to Arabic) is **(98.8%)**.
- 2- The machine accuracy in the **Economic text** (Arabic to English) is **(98.6%)**, while (English to Arabic) is **(100%)**.
- 3- The machine accuracy in the **Scientific text** (Arabic to English) is **(92%)**, while (English to Arabic) is **(96.4%)**.
- 4- The machine accuracy in the **Culture and Art text** (Arabic to English) is **(93.8%)**, while (English to Arabic) is **(98.8%)**.
- 5- The machine accuracy in the **Sports text** (Arabic to English) is **(100%)**, while (English to Arabic) is **(97.4%)**.
- 6- The machine accuracy in the **Legal text** (Arabic to English) is **(97.6%)**, while (English to Arabic) is **(98.6%)**.

From the above statistics:

- 1- The machine performance is better (**with a slight difference**), when translating from English into Arabic the **political, economic, scientific, and culture and art** fields.
- 2- Nevertheless, in the **sports and legal** fields machine performance is better, (**also with slight difference**) from Arabic into English.

4.2.15: Chapter Summary:

This chapter is devoted to analyze texts translated from Arabic into English, and from English into Arabic by use of Google Translate, to study the changes (mistranslation) occurs in these texts. There are twelve texts, six of them from Arabic into English, and six from English into Arabic, the analysis of these texts is syntactical, by dismounting the structure, into the lingual units (noun, verb, pronoun, adjective, adverb, preposition, and article) and identifying the additional and omitted words the came out of the translation process by the machine. The results in the above section show that the accuracy of the machine in dealing with different types of texts from Arabic into English (political, economic, scientific, etc..) is slight, and accuracy ranged between 96.5% and the inaccuracy 3.5%. but from English into Arabic the accuracy between 96.1%, and the inaccuracy 3.9%.

Chapter Five

Conclusion

Chapter Five

Conclusion

5.1: Introduction:

This chapter includes the findings result and recommendations.

These findings meet the objectives of the study, by identifying the problems of the MT, and examining the changes and problem occur in the TT, besides suggesting some solutions to these problems.

Furthermore, the results examined the hypotheses and answered the questions proposed by the study, proving that there are some syntactical errors occur in the MT performance from Arabic to English and vice versa, and confirmed that the MT output must be re-edited, but these findings discovered that there is no significant errors and miss-translation as far as MT type (political, economic, scientific, culture and art, sports, and legal).

This study proved the usefulness of “Google Translate”, depends on the results of this study, which affirmed that it is trusted and can be used safely in MT from Arabic to English, and vice versa.

In addition, the study, by this set of results, urging researchers to conduct more studies in MT new field of translation studies.

5.2: Findings:

The study concluded to the following findings and results:

- 1- the study found that the machine output (from Arabic to English) and vice versa, is not completely accurate;
- 2- But, the quality of the machine output is very high, that accuracy rate of the machine performance from Arabic to English is 95.6%, and from English to Arabic is 96.1%.
- 3- Despite this high-quality output, the MT output sometimes need minor editing.

- 4- There are no significant differences of the machine performance in the various text types of translation (political, economic, scientific, arts and culture, sports, and legal), these differences are shown in the following two points:
- The machine performance is better (with a slight difference), when translating from English to Arabic in the political, economic, scientific, and cultural and artistic fields.
 - However, in the sports and legal fields machine performance is better, (also with slight difference) from Arabic to English.
- 5- There is more increase in the omitted words rather than the added ones when translating from English to Arabic, while the added words are less from Arabic to English translation. But there is an increase of the words added to the TT when the machine translates from Arabic to English. while the omitted words are less.

5.3: Recommendations:

Based on the study findings the researcher recommends the following:

- 1- Implementing more studies helps developing MT field, and causes enrichment of linguistic researches.
- 2- It is important to help concentration on MT studies, between the European and Semitic languages, such as Arabic, Persian, and Hebrew.
- 3- Because of the wide use of cellular phones, computers, and the expansion of the Internet networks, it is necessary to adopt students of translation, languages, and media, communication, and information with the importance of machine translation, especially in this era.
- 4- MT applicants should deal carefully with omitted and additional words in the output (TT) of the MT process.
- 5- Encouragement of linguists and translators to focus attention on MT applications and development.
- 6- For researchers, institutions, and ordinary people, the researcher recommends that MT from Arabic into English and vice versa is trustworthy.
- 7- The researcher recommends of more similar studies, to help fix MT programs defects, and promotes the technologies of MT generally.
- 8- Google translate, according to these findings, is reliable, and the researcher recommends of using it in media.
- 9- MT meansof translation should be taught to translation students including all the skills and knowledge needed i.e. should be included in the syllabus.
- 10- Grop transltison can be adopted as a method in dealing with MT outputs.
- 11- MT output will not be accurate in long texts, so, the SL texts must be treated to avoid long sentences and apply short sentences.

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Appendixes

Appendixes

Appendix (1)

Sample Texts Part One: Arabic into English

1- Text (1): Poetical:

Source Text

1- أزمة تونس: كيف أدى الصراع السياسي في تونس إلى أزمة مصيرية؟

29 يوليو/ تموز 2021

2- انقسم التونسيون بين مؤيد ومعارض لقرارات الرئيس قيس سعيد إقالة رئيس الوزراء هشام

المشيشي وتعليق عمل البرلمان ردا على موجة احتجاجات شعبية مناهضة للطبقة السياسية الحاكمة في البلاد.

3- واعتبر كثيرون قرارات الرئيس ضرورية "لتصحيح مسار الثورة التونسية"، بينما وصفها آخرون "بالانقلاب" على الدستور.

4- وتشهد تونس أكبر أزمة اقتصادية وسياسية منذ ثورة 2011 التي أطاحت بالرئيس السابق زين العابدين بن علي. فكيف وصلت الأمور إلى هذه المرحلة؟.

Target Text

1- Tunisia Crisis: How did the political conflict in Tunisia lead to a fateful crisis?

29 July 2021

2- Tunisians were divided between supporters and opponents of President Kais Saied's decisions to dismiss Prime Minister Hicham Al-Mashishi and suspend parliament in response to a wave of popular protests against the country's ruling political class.

3- Many considered the president's decisions necessary to "correct the course of the Tunisian revolution", while others described it as a "coup" against the constitution.

4- Tunisia is experiencing the biggest economic and political crisis since the 2011 revolution that toppled former President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali. How did things get to this point?

2- Text (2): Economic:

Source Text

1- أمازون: غرامة ضخمة بمئات الملايين من الدولارات على عملاق التجارة

الإلكترونية

قبل 5 ساعة

2- منيت شركة أمازون بغرامة قدرها 886.6 مليون دولار بسبب استخدامها البيانات

الشخصية لزيائنها بشكل فيه انتهاك لقوانين الاتحاد الأوروبي.

3- وفرضت الهيئة الوطنية لحماية المعلومات في لوكسمبورغ الغرامة على شركة أمازون

بقرار اتخذته في 16 يوليو/تموز، حسب بيان صدر عن الشركة.

4- وسوف تطعن أمازون على القرار، وفقا لمتحدث باسم الشركة، التي اعتبرت أن

العقوبة المفروضة بحقها "ظالمة".

5- وتتطلب قوانين حماية البيانات في الاتحاد الأوروبي من الشركات أن تحصل على

موافقة المستهلكين قبل استخدام بياناتهم الشخصية، وإلا أصبحت تحت طائلة

غرامات كبيرة.

6- وقد زادت الرقابة على عمالقة التجارة في العالم عقب سلسلة من الفضائح المتعلقة

بالخصوصية وسوء استخدام بيانات المستهلكين، إضافة إلى شكاوى من بعض

الشركات متهمة شركات كبرى باستخدام قوتها في السوق.

Target Text

1- Amazon: Huge fine of hundreds of millions of dollars to the e-commerce giant.

5 hours ago

- 2- Amazon has been fined \$886.6 million for using the personal data of its customers in violation of European Union laws.
- 3- The National Information Protection Authority in Luxembourg imposed the fine on Amazon in a decision taken on July 16, according to a statement issued by the company.
- 4- Amazon will appeal the decision, according to a spokesperson for the company, which considered the punishment imposed on it "unfair".
- 5- European Union data protection laws require companies to obtain consumer consent before using their personal data, or else face heavy fines.
- 6- Oversight of the world's trading giants has increased following a series of privacy scandals and misuse of consumer data, in addition to complaints from some companies accusing major companies of using their market power.

3- Text (3): Scientific:

Source Text

1- فيروس كورونا: ما سر إصابة أعداد كبيرة بكوفيد للمرة الثانية؟

روبرت كاف- بي بي سي

31 مارس/ آذار 2022

2- في الأيام الأولى لانتشار وباء كورونا، كانت إصابة شخص واحد بكوفيد مرتين

خبرًا نادرًا للغاية.

3- لكن اليوم لم تعد هذه الحال قائمة، وخصوصًا بعد ظهور متحور أوميكرون في

نوفمبر/ تشرين الثاني 2021.

4- لماذا يتزايد أعداد الأشخاص الذين يصابون بكوفيد للمرة الثانية؟.

5- يعود جزء من السبب في ذلك إلى أوميكرون نفسه، فهو متحور يجيد خداع الدفاعات

التي دشنتها إصابات سابقة بالفيروس، فيما يعود جزء من السبب إلى الصدفة.

6- وعليه، فقد أصيب كثير منا في وقت ما، والآن، ثمة موجة مرتفعة من الإصابات،

هي في معظمها إصابات ثانية لنفس الأشخاص.

Target Text

1- Corona Virus: What is the secret of infection of large numbers of “Covid” for the second time?

Robert Kave

BBC

March 31, 2022

- 2- In the early days of the coronavirus epidemic, one person being infected with Covid twice was very rare news.
- 3- Today, however, this is no longer the case, especially after the appearance of the Omicron mutant in November 2021.
- 4- Why is the number of people infected with Covid increasing for the second time?
- 5- Part of the reason for this is Omicron itself, a mutant that is good at cheating defenses launched by previous HIV infections, and part of the reason is due to chance.
- 6- So, many of us have been injured at some point, and now, there is a high wave of injuries, mostly second injuries of the same people.

7- Text (4): Scientific:

Source Text

1- هاري بوتر: بيع نسخة نادرة مقابل 80 ألف جنيه إسترليني في مزاد

29 يوليو/ تموز 2021، GMT22:42

2- بيعت النسخة الأولى من كتاب "هاري بوتر وحجر الفيلسوف" للكاتبة جي كي رولينج

في "حالة استثنائية" مقابل 80 ألف جنيه إسترليني في مزاد.

3- وكان الكتاب واحدًا من 500 نسخة مطبوعة في أول إصدار له عام 1997 وتم

شراؤه من مكتبة في نوتنغهام.

4- وعلى صفحة حقوق الطبع والنشر للكتاب، يُشار إلى المؤلفة الشهيرة عالميًا باسم

"جوان رولينج".

5- وقدّر المسؤولون عن المزاد، الذي أُجري في شمال يوركشير، سعر الكتاب بحوالي

20.000 إلى 30.000 جنيه إسترليني.

Target Text

1- Harry Potter: Rare copy sold for £80,000 at auction

29 July 2021, 22:42 GMT

- 2- A first copy of J.K. Rowling's "Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone" has sold in "exceptional condition" for £80,000 at auction.
- 3- The book was one of 500 copies in print in its first edition in 1997 and was purchased from a bookshop in Nottingham.
- 4- On the book's copyright page, the world-famous author is referred to as "Joanne Rowling".
- 5- The auction house, which took place in North Yorkshire, estimated the price of the book at between 20,000 and 30,000 pounds.

6- Text (5): Sports:

Source Text

1- أولمبياد طوكيو: صديقتان سوريّتان فرقتهما الحرب وجمعتهما الرياضة

قبل 5 ساعة

2- تدرّبت ساندا الداس ومنى دهوك معاً منذ الطفولة.

3- لكن الحرب في سوريا فرقتهما.

4- وجدت الصديقتان الأمان في هولندا.

5- وأصبحتا جزءاً من فريق اللاجئيين الأولمبي.

6- اللاعبتان السوريتان ضمن الفريق المختلط للجودو والذي يلعب لأول مرة في أولمبياد

طوكيو.

Target Text

1- Tokyo Olympics: Two Syrian friends separated by war and brought together by sport

5 hours ago

2- Sanda Aldas and Mona Duhok have trained together since childhood. but the war in Syria separated them .

3- The two friends found safety in the Netherlands

4- and became part of the refugee Olympic team .

5- The two Syrian players are part of the mixed judo team, which is playing for the first time in the Tokyo Olympics .

7- Text (5): Legal:

Source Text

1- معركة قانونية بين الحكومة البريطانية و"بي بي سي" بسبب تقرير إخباري عن

جاسوس

إلي أويريزو

الاثنين 24 يناير 2022 16:25

2- تنتهياً حكومة المملكة المتحدة وشبكة "بي بي سي" البريطانية لخوض معركة قضائية

بسبب تقرير إخباري تنوي المؤسسة التلفزيونية بثه، قيل إن من شأنه أن يكشف هوية أحد جواسيس الحكومة.

3- وأفادت صحيفة "تليغراف" بأن البرنامج الإخباري قد يفضح هوية أحد موظفي

الاستخبارات البريطانية من الذين يعملون خارج البلاد، وعلم أن المسألة تعد حساسة للغاية.

4- ولم يأت أي من طرفي النزاع القانوني على ذكر محتوى البرنامج المراد بثه، لكن

كلاهما أكدا أن الحكومة البريطانية كانت تسعى إلى الحصول على إنذار قضائي بعدم بثه.

5- وأوضحت شبكة "بي بي سي" في بيان لها أن المدعي العام حرك إجراءات قانونية

ضد المؤسسة بهدف الحصول على أمر قضائي يمنع نشر تقرير إخباري أعدته "بي

بي سي".

Target Text

1- A legal battle between the British government and the BBC over a spy report

to Ayorizo

Monday January 24 2022 16:25

- 2- The UK **government** and the BBC are preparing for a court battle over a news report the television network plans to broadcast that is said to have exposed the identity of a government spy.
- 3- And the newspaper "Telegraph" reported that the news program may expose the identity of a British intelligence employee who is working outside the country, and learned that the issue is very sensitive.
- 4- None of the two sides of the legal conflict did not mention the content of the program to broadcast, but both stressed that the British government was seeking to obtain a judicial alarm not to broadcast..
- 5- The BBC said in a statement that the attorney general has initiated legal proceedings against the institution with the aim of obtaining a court order preventing the publication of a news report prepared by the BBC.

Appendix (2)

Sample Texts Part Two: Arabic into English

1- Text (1): Poetical:

Source Text

1- Why is France angry over nuclear submarine deal between US, UK & Australia?

short by SakshitaKhosla / 06:03 pm on 18 Sep 2021, Saturday

- 2- After US, UK and Australia announced a trilateral security pact that would enable Australia to get nuclear-powered submarines,
- 3- France said it was "very angry and bitter" .
- 4- This is because France's partly state-owned Naval Group was chosen in 2016 to build 12 conventional diesel-electrical submarines for Australia.
- 5- The trilateral pact means that the French-Australian deal is effectively scrapped.

Target Text

1- لماذا فرنسا غاضبة من صفقة الغواصات النووية بين الولايات المتحدة والمملكة المتحدة وأستراليا؟

حررها ساكشيتا خوسلا / 06:03 مساءً يوم 18 سبتمبر 2021، السبت

- 2- بعد إعلان الولايات المتحدة والمملكة المتحدة وأستراليا اتفاقية أمنية ثلاثية من شأنها أن تمكن أستراليا من الحصول على غواصات تعمل بالطاقة النووية ،
- 3- قالت فرنسا إنها "غاضبة ومريرة للغاية".
- 4- وذلك لأن مجموعة نافال الفرنسية المملوكة جزئيًا للدولة تم اختيارها في عام 2016 لبناء 12 غواصة تقليدية تعمل بالديزل والكهرباء لأستراليا.
- 5- يعني الاتفاق الثلاثي أن الصفقة الفرنسية الأسترالية تم إلغاؤها فعليًا.

2- Text (2): Economic:

Source Text

1- Suzuki Motor Gujarat to reduce production in Aug due to chip shortage

short by Krishna Raj / 11:15 pm on 04 Aug 2021, Wednesday

- 2- Suzuki Motor Gujarat will scale down production activity this month at its manufacturing plant in Ahmedabad, Gujarat due to semiconductor shortage, Maruti Suzuki India has said.
- 3- The firm has also decided to scale down production to single shift at some manufacturing lines in the plant.
- 4- It will tentatively not carry out production on three Saturdays (August 7, 14 and 21).

Target Text

1- سوزوكي موتور غوجارات ستخفض الإنتاج في أغسطس بسبب نقص الرقائق.

حررها كريشنا راج / 11:15 مساءً في 4 أغسطس 2021، الأربعاء

2- قالت ماروتي سوزوكي الهند إن سوزوكي موتور غوجارات ستقلص نشاط الإنتاج هذا الشهر في مصنعها في أحمد آباد بولاية غوجارات بسبب نقص أشباه الموصلات.

3- قررت الشركة أيضاً خفض الإنتاج إلى وردية واحدة في بعض خطوط التصنيع في المصنع.

4- ولن تنفذ مبدئياً الإنتاج في ثلاثة أيام سبت (7 و14 و21 أغسطس).

3- Text (3): Scientific:

Source Text

- 1- Maasai women in Kenya meet to discuss practice of FGM
- 2- The practice of female genital mutilation (FGM), where women's genitals are altered or injured for non-medical reasons, is rife in parts of Africa.
- 3- Dangers include severe bleeding, problems urinating, infections, infertility and increased risk of newborn deaths in childbirth.
- 4- Despite these complications, cultural and religious beliefs mean millions of girls are still at risk of being mutilated.
- 5- Anne Soy reports from Kenya where there is a generational divide between proponents of FGM and those who want to abandon the tradition.

Target Text

- 1- نساء الماساي في كينيا يجتمعن لمناقشة ممارسة تشويه الأعضاء التناسلية الأنثوية
- 2- ممارسة تشويه الأعضاء التناسلية للإناث، حيث يتم تغيير أو إصابة الأعضاء التناسلية الأنثوية لأسباب غير طبية ، منتشرة في أجزاء من إفريقيا.
- 3- تشمل المخاطر النزيف الحاد ، ومشاكل التبول ، والالتهابات ، والعقم ، وزيادة خطر وفيات الأطفال حديثي الولادة أثناء الولادة.
- 4- على الرغم من هذه التعقيدات ، فإن المعتقدات الثقافية والدينية تعني أن ملايين الفتيات ما زلن عرضة لخطر التشويه.
- 5- تقرير أن صوي من كينيا حيث يوجد فجوة بين مؤيدي تشويه الأعضاء التناسلية الأنثوية وأولئك الذين يريدون التخلي عن هذا التقليد.

4- Text (4): Culture and Art:

Source Text

- 1- **Japanese Princess to give up royal title, 150 million yen to marry commoner: Reports**

Short by SakshitaKhosla / 04:52 pm on 26 Sep 2021, Sunday

- 2- Japan's Princess Mako is reportedly set to forego a one-off payment of 150 million yen (\$1.35 million) for giving up her royal status to marry a commoner whom she met during her college years.
- 3- This comes amid public criticism over her former college classmate and fiance Kei Komuro.
- 4- The 29-year-old granddaughter of then-Emperor Akihito had announced her engagement in 2017.

Target Text

1- الأميرة اليابانية تتخلى عن اللقب الملكي، 150 مليون ين للزواج من عامة الشعب: تقارير

اختصار: ساكشيتا خوسلا / 04:52 مساءً في 26 سبتمبر 2021، الأحد

2- يقال إن الأميرة اليابانية ماکو ستتخلى عن دفعة لمرة واحدة قدرها 150 مليون ين (1.35 مليون دولار) لتخليها عن وضعها الملكي للزواج من شخص من عامة الشعب التقت به خلال سنوات دراستها الجامعية.

3- يأتي ذلك وسط انتقادات علنية لزميلتها وخطيبها السابق في الكلية كي كومورو.

4- أعلنت حفيدة الإمبراطور أكيهيتو البالغة من العمر 29 عامًا خطوبتها في عام 2017.

5- Text (5): Sports:

Source Text

- 1- **Aubameyang scores as Barca win at Real Sociedad**
- 2- Pierre-Emerick Aubameyang's ninth goal in 11 La Liga appearances helped earn Barcelona a win at Real Sociedad that lifted them to second in the table.
- 3- The ex-Arsenal forward scored with a close-range header after a cross by ex-Manchester City player Ferran Torres.
- 4- Shortly before Aubameyang's goal, Ousmane Dembele's shot came back off the post.
- 5- Aubameyang, 32, joined Barca on a free transfer in February after not playing for Arsenal following a disciplinary breach in December. Only Memphis Depay has scored more goals in La Liga for Barca this season.
- 6- Barca's win lifts them into second spot on 63 points - 15 behind runaway leaders Real Madrid.
- 7- Real Sociedad remain sixth in the table - six points off a Champions League spot with five games left.

Target Text

- 1- أوباميانج يسجل في فوز برشلونة على ريال سوسيداد
- 2- ساعد الهدف التاسع لبيير إيمريك أوباميانج في 11 مباراة بالدوري الإسباني على فوز برشلونة على ريال سوسيداد الذي رفعه إلى المركز الثاني في جدول الترتيب.
- 3- سجل مهاجم أرسنال السابق بضربة رأس من مدى قريب بعد عرضية من لاعب مانشستر سيتي السابق فيران توريس.
- 4- قبل وقت قصير من هدف أوباميانج ، ارتدت تسديدة عثمان ديمبيلي من القائم.
- 5- وانضم أوباميانج ، 32 عامًا ، إلى برشلونة في صفقة انتقال مجانية في فبراير بعد عدم اللعب مع أرسنال بعد مخالفة تأديبية في ديسمبر . فقط ممفيس دييبي سجل المزيد من الأهداف في الدوري الإسباني لبرشلونة هذا الموسم.
- 6- ورفع فوز برشلونة للمركز الثاني برصيد 63 نقطة - بفارق 15 نقطة عن ريال مدريد المتصدر .
- 7- حافظ ريال سوسيداد على المركز السادس في الترتيب بفارق ست نقاط عن مكانه في دوري أبطال أوروبا قبل خمس مباريات على النهاية.

6- Text (6): Sports:

Source Text

1- Princess Beatrice 'wedding gift' claim in court case

By Sean Coughlan

Royal correspondent

12 hours ago

- 2- Nehebat Isbilenn is claiming at the High Court in London that her business adviser Selman Turk "dishonestly misappropriated" £38m of her assets.
- 3- Mrs. Isbilen paid £750,000 to Prince Andrew and claims Mr Turk had wrongly told her bank it was a wedding gift.
- 4- There is no suggestion of wrongdoing by Princess Beatrice or Prince Andrew.
- 5- The Duke of York has now returned the £750,000 to Mrs. Isbilen.
- 6- Mr Turk has rejected the allegations made against him.

Target Text

1- مطالبة الأميرة بياتريس بـ "هدية زفاف" في قضية قضائية

بقلم شون كوغلان

مراسل ملكي

منذ 12 ساعة

- 2- تدعي نيهابايسبلين أمام المحكمة العليا في لندن أن مستشارها التجاري سلمان ترك "اختلس بطريقة غير شريفة" 38 مليون جنيه إسترليني من أصولها.
- 3- دفعت السيدة إسبلين 750 ألف جنيه إسترليني للأمير أندرو وتزعم أن السيد ترك أخبر بنكها بالخطأ أنها هدية زفاف.
- 4- ليس هناك ما يشير إلى ارتكاب مخالفات من قبل الأميرة بياتريس أو الأمير أندرو.
- 5- أعاد دوق يورك الآن 750.000 جنيه إسترليني للسيدة إسبلين.
- 6- وكان السيد ترك قد رفض المزاعم التي وجهت ضده.

Appendix (3)

Omitted and additional words

These tables show the omitted and additional words in the two parts of the machine work, from English into Arabic, and vice versa, that table (1) demonstrates the total statistics, and the rest of the tables below (from 2 to 5) explain the details of the types of the omitted and additional words, whether it is noun, pronoun, verb, adjective, adverb, preposition, or conjunction, it is worthy to mention that the total words of part (1) Arabic into English is (589), and part (2), from English into Arabic (465).

(1)

Item	Omitted		Additional		Total Words
	frequency	%	frequency	%	
Arabic into English	8	1.3	96	16.2	589
English into Arabic	26	5.5	18	3.8	465

A/ Arabic into English:

Omitted words:

(2)

Item	N		Pron.		Verb		Adj.		Adv.		Prep.		Conj.		Total words
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Total words	0	0	0	0	1	12.5	0	0	0	0	5	62.5	2	25	8

Additional words:

(3)

Item	N		Pron.		Verb		Adj.		Adv.		Prep.		Conj.		Total words
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Total words	14	14.5	39	40.5	5	5.2	0	0	3	3.2	18	18.8	17	17.8	96

B/ English into Arabic:

Omitted words:

(4)

Item	N		Pron.		Verb		Adj.		Adv.		Prep.		Conj.		Total words
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Total words	6	23	9	34.6	1	3.9	0	0	1	3.9	2	7.7	7	26.9	26

Additional words:

(5)

Item	N		Pron.		Verb		Adj.		Adv.		Prep.		Conj.		Total words
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Total words	0	0	3	16.7	3	16.7	2	11.1	0	0	7	38.8	3	16.7	18

To shed more light on the machine performance in this study, it is important to review the omitted and additional words of the process from Arabic into English and vice versa, according to its type, (noun, pronouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, prepositions, and conjunctions), as following:

- From Arabic into English **12.5%** of the **omitted** words are verbs, **62.5%** prepositions, and **25%** conjunctions, and there is no omitted nouns, pronouns, adjectives, and adverbs.
- But the additional words in the same part, there is **55%** nouns and pronouns, 5.2% verbs, 3.2% adverbs, 18.8% prepositions, and 17.8% conjunctions, but there is no additional adjective.
- In the second part (English into Arabic), 57.6% of the omitted words are nouns and pronouns, 3.9% verbs, also 3.9% adverbs, 7.7% prepositions, and 26.9% conjunctions, there is no omitted adjective.
- In the same part 16.7% of the additional words are pronouns, also the verbs are 16.7% and same for conjunctions (16.7%), **11.1%** adjectives, **38.8%** prepositions, and there is no additional nouns and adverbs.
- The omitted words in the translation process (Arabic into English), are **(8)** words, which represents **1.3%** of the total words of this part **(589)** words, while the omitted words of the process (English into Arabic) are **(26)** words, and represents **5.5%** of the total words this part **(465)** words.
- The additional words of the process (Arabic into English) are **(96)** words, represents **16.2%** of the total words of this part **(589)** words, while the additional words of the translation process (English into Arabic) are **(18)** words, and represents **3.8%** of the total words of this part **(465)** words.